

A EUROPEAN ROADMAP ON SOILS AND LAND MANAGEMENT

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ABBREVIATIONS

CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
CSA	Coordination and Support Actions
DG	Directorate-General
EU	European Union
HE	Horizon Europe
JRC	Joint Research Centre
LH	Light Houses
LL	Living Labs
MB	Mission Board
MS	Member State
R&I	Research and Innovation
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
SMO	Soil Mission Objectives
SMS	Soil Mission Support
SOC	Soil Organic Carbon

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Soil health is vital for many ecosystem services and crucial for achieving the Sustainable Development Goals and the European Green Deal's goals. The Horizon Europe (HE) Mission “A Soil Deal for Europe” aims to accelerate the transition to sustainable soil and land management, and healthy soils through an ambitious transdisciplinary research and innovation (R&I) programme, largely based on actor engagement, Living Labs and Lighthouses. The H2020 Soil Mission Support (SMS) project supports the implementation of the HE Mission and aims to improve the coordination of R&I on sustainable soil and land management. Through a co-creation process together with actors, SMS collates available knowledge, actors R&I needs and identifies R&I gaps that need to be addressed for successful transition towards sustainable soil and land management.

The presented R&I roadmap on soils and land management is a strategic document outlining the actions and the pathway to address R&I needs from different actors and sectors, as well as societal challenges. The roadmap presents the most important R&I knowledge gaps for each Soil Mission Objective, which were identified in collaboration with stakeholders from all relevant sectors and based on the key findings of the project. To ensure that the R&I elements of the roadmap can effectively contribute to the desired transformation of land and soil management, the impact pathways approach was chosen as the analytical framework. The impact pathways are key component of the roadmap and describe several research actions that should be taken up to address the knowledge gaps and show what results we can expect from these actions that will lead to a short, medium- and finally long-term impact. The results show that to reach the eight Mission Objectives a common understanding of soil health is needed, as well as research and innovation in both natural sciences as well as social and economic spheres. The actions identified in the roadmap should be closely integrated. Future projects should focus more on finding systemic approaches to highlight synergies and minimise or avoid trade-offs while addressing the individual soil mission objectives.

1 INTRODUCTION TO THE ROADMAP ON SOILS AND LAND MANAGEMENT

Soil health is key for sustainable food provision, the delivery of energy and biomaterials, to reach climate neutrality, as well as climate change adaptation, biodiversity below and above ground and a wide range of further ecosystem services. Thus, soil health is crucial for achieving the Sustainable Development Goals and the European Green Deal's goals.

Nevertheless, one third of the global land is considered to be degraded and about two thirds of European soils are deemed to be in an unhealthy condition (EC, 2021). Land use, including deforestation, intensive agriculture, and rising urbanisation, is exerting pressure on land and soil. This pressure is growing due to competing demands for food and bio-based products, urbanisation and industrial activities. Sustainable soil management that satisfies the increasing demand and avoids soil degradation requires coordinated research and innovation (R&I), evidence-based and integrated policies and involvement of a large variety of actors, from producers to citizens.

The European Mission “A Soil Deal for Europe” aims to accelerate the transition to sustainable soil and land management and healthy soils by 2030 through actions in 100 living labs and light-houses, a transdisciplinary research and innovation (R&I) programme, a harmonised soil monitoring framework and improved soil literacy and communication to engage citizens (EC, 2021). The mission addresses eight objectives. The first six relate to different soil threats, while objectives 7 and 8 deal with more cross-cutting issues of improving soil health (see figure 1). One of the main aims of the mission is to build capacities and the knowledge base for better soil and land management by co-creating an ambitious transdisciplinary R&I programme. This programme should be largely based on actor engagement from all relevant land use sectors to overcome the current fragmented research landscape in the EU.

Figure 1: The eight Soil Mission Objectives (own elaboration)

Achieving the eight soil mission objectives (SMOs) is essential for the success of the EU Green Deal and its related strategies, including the Soil Strategy, the EU Farm to Fork strategy, the Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, the New Forest Strategy, the Zero Pollution Action Plan and the upcoming EU Nature Restoration Law, as well as the Soil Health Law. Additionally, the mission aims to work with the future Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) and its European Innovation Partnership on Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability (EIP AGRI) to put new knowledge into practice and promote innovative land management approaches in the agricultural sector.

The H2020 Soil Mission Support (SMS) project aimed to support the implementation of the Soil Mission, inter alia by developing this roadmap for R&I on soil and land management – in collaboration with stakeholders – to improve coordination in this field. The activities included a literature-based mapping of existing knowledge and an analysis of knowledge needs involving stakeholders regarding sustainable soil and land management. As a result, key knowledge gaps, including socio-economic aspects, were identified.

The presented roadmap aims to provide an overview of R&I needs and actions to achieve the eight SMOs. The roadmap is structured as follows: Chapters 1 and 2 describe the context and objective of the roadmap, Chapter 3 provides details of the process towards the presented results, Chapter 4 summarises the identified R&I actions to achieve the eight soil mission objectives, and Chapter 5 gives an outlook of what comes next.

2 THE OBJECTIVE OF THE ROADMAP

Sustainable soil and land management is the key to improving soil health and addressing societal challenges such as climate mitigation and adaptation, rational use of biomass, curbing land-take, maintaining ecosystem services and biodiversity, improving disaster control, and reducing soil degradation in Europe and globally.

For successful sustainable soil and land management, it is necessary to improve the linkages between different land use sectors and sectoral knowledge to break existing silos. This is why the SMS project covered all relevant land use sectors from agriculture and forestry to urban areas and industrial zones as well as natural conservation areas (see figure 2).

The R&I roadmap on soils and land management is a strategic document outlining the R&I needs from different actors and sectors to implement the soil mission.

The roadmap presents the most important R&I knowledge gaps for each SMO, which were identified in collaboration with stakeholders from all relevant sectors. The identified knowledge gaps cover different knowledge domains such as basic knowledge production, data management and monitoring, technical and economic innovations, modelling, but also awareness raising, education and science-based policy support. To ensure that the R&I elements of the roadmap can effectively contribute to the desired transformation of land and soil management, the impact pathways approach was chosen as the analytical framework. This approach not only ensures that the knowledge gaps are identified, but also provides concrete actions that lead to a specific result and outcome.

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Figure 2: The five land use sectors relevant for soil and land management addressed by the SMS project (Source: Nougues & Brils et al., 2022)

What is the purpose of the roadmap? The R&I roadmap on soils and land management is a strategic document outlining the actions and the pathway to address R&I needs from different actors and sectors, as well as societal challenges. It will guide and inform the future R&I agenda to meet the eight soil mission objectives. The roadmap will thus support the soil mission implementation plan and inform the development of upcoming Horizon Europe work programmes and the individual roadmaps for each soil mission objective, which will be further elaborated as part of the follow-up project (HORIZON-MISS-2021-SOIL-02-01).

What is the scope of the roadmap? The roadmap serves as an operational framework for R&I needs and identifies future research topics and needs based on a gap analysis (Mason et al., 2022). Previous projects and initiatives (e.g. EJP Soil, CIRCASA, INSPIRATION; see also Löbmann et al., 2021, Löbmann et al., 2022) have been taken into account to avoid repetition and instead create a complementary document. The overall timeline horizon is 2050, for which the roadmap includes short-, mid- and long-term targets and actions, with a midterm checkpoint in 2035.

Who are the end-users of the roadmap? The primary end-user of the roadmap is the European Commission (DG Agriculture and DG Research and Innovation), which is responsible for implementing the soil mission in terms of R&I actions. A second target group we want to inform are the key stakeholders who have an interest in soil health and the follow-up projects. Key actors include policy makers at European, national and regional levels, researchers and management, land managers and land users, investors, stakeholders from the private sector and industries, service providers, administration and consumers as well as citizens. These key actors play an essential role in implementing measures and achieving the soil mission objectives.

3 THE PROCESS TOWARDS THE SOIL MISSION ROADMAP

To develop a roadmap that reflects the needs and requirements of the targeted end-users, a genuine co-creation process was implemented, involving all potential end-users and key actors from the beginning to the final product, as well as the SMS consortium. The roadmap was developed iteratively in shorter work cycles, which allowed for early feedback and continuous improvement. The co-creation process, including the assessment of R&I gaps, is summarised in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Co-creation concept for developing the roadmap

In addition to involving a wide range of actors through surveys and workshops, a key element was the establishment of an **expert group (Step 1)** to provide regular input. The expert group consisted of 13 actors from key European organisations representing all the different potential actor groups (academia, industry, land owners and users, policy makers, NGOs) and land use sectors of the roadmap (e.g. agriculture, forestry, urban areas, industry, protected areas).

As a first step, an expert group workshop was organised to co-create a **“product vision (Step 2)”** for the roadmap and to clarify what kind of information these key actors actually need and in what format and what are the benefits and added value of the roadmap. Based on the outputs of this workshop and feedback from the consortium partners, as well as from the European Commission, a **joined outline (Step 3)** was elaborated, defining the focus and scope of the roadmap.

In parallel, the R&I gaps were assessed as part of another deliverable (Mason et al., 2022) by comparing existing R&I knowledge emerging from a comprehensive scientific literature review with stakeholder needs (Maring et al., 2022) and supplemented by knowledge gaps identified by other relevant projects e.g. EJP Soil, CIRCASA, INSPIRATION (Löbmann et al., 2021; Löbmann et al., 2022) (see Box 1).

Box 1: R&I gap assessment

The SMS project compiled available knowledge, actors R&I needs and derived from this R&I gaps that need to be addressed for successful transition towards sustainable soil and land management. The existing R&I knowledge stock was identified through a keyword-based analysis of more than 15,000 scientific articles related to sustainable soil and land management (Mason et al., 2022). The literature review addressed the full range of societal challenges, soil health objectives, land use types and knowledge areas required to capture the socio-ecological complexity of soil health. In order to obtain a practice-oriented picture of the current state of knowledge and R&I needs, stakeholders were consulted through online workshops and surveys (Maring et al., 2022). The identified knowledge gaps are the result of comparing existing knowledge and stakeholder needs. These were validated as described in step 4 and served as the basis for the content of the roadmap.

The identified knowledge gaps were then validated and completed with a representative group of key actors in a series of **validation workshops (Step 4)**, each focussing on a different land use (agricultural, forestry, natural, industrial, and urban) and one workshop addressing the EU global footprint on soils (SMO7). Around 100 participants from 20 different EU countries attended the workshops. Participants include the expert group, advisory board members, HE Mission board members and experts as well as initiatives that were identified within the project (László et al., 2022).

Based on the results of the validation workshops eight **impact pathways (Step 5)** were developed, one for each SMO, adapting the impact pathway logic of Horizon Europe projects (EC, 2022). The impact-pathways are a key component of the roadmap and summarise the key findings for each SMO and are presented in Chapter 4. They describe the identified key R&I needs, specific research actions to address these needs, and the expected results that will lead to short-, medium- and, ultimately, long-term impacts for each Soil Mission objective. These impact pathways were evaluated by the expert group. In a following step, more detailed factsheets based on the impact pathways for each of the identified aggregate knowledge gaps were developed together with consortium experts (see Annex). The factsheets include additional information on end-users, key actors, the relevant land use sector, specific regional scope, intermediaries, synergies and potential barriers for each aggregated knowledge gap, thus providing important information for successful implementation and on the actors to be involved. It also identified the urgency of specific actions and proposed milestones needed to achieve the outcomes and long-term impacts by 2050 and to measure progress. A **final review (Step 6)** of each SMO and its set of factsheets were done by external experts, consortium experts and the external project reviewers. This feedback was taken into account and the roadmap has been adjusted accordingly. This document presents the final roadmap.

4 RESEARCH ACTIONS TO ACHIEVE THE SOIL MISSION OBJECTIVES

This section presents the research needs and actions needed to achieve the SMOs. The main knowledge gaps have been identified for each individual SMO and are presented below in sections 4.1-4.8. For each identified knowledge gap, an impact pathway has been elaborated, which includes concrete actions to address the

knowledge gap and specifies the results and outcomes that can be expected from these actions. In addition, the detailed factsheets for each identified knowledge gap can be found in Annex I-VIII, which provides further details on end-users, key actors, the relevant land use sector, the specific regional scope, intermediaries, synergies and potential barriers. The factsheets also identify the urgency of specific actions and propose milestones needed to achieve the outcomes and long-term impacts by 2050 and to measure progress. In addition, indications of limitations and potential for further development of the impact pathways and factsheets are provided for each SMO.

While each SMO has very specific gaps which are addressed in the subsequent sections, the analysis revealed knowledge gaps and needs that are common to several SMOs and require a more coordinated approach to address them. Common research needs encompass:

- Clear definitions and ontologies for “soil health” and SMOs (e.g. land degradation, soil sealing, soil footprint) to create a common understanding and provide a basis for measuring progress
- Agreed, shared, harmonised indicators for all SMOs, accompanied by interpretative values (e.g. threshold, normal operating ranges, target values) reflecting on soil type, land use, climate to support decision-making
- Cost-effective methods for calculating and measuring the harmonised indicators to facilitate their implementation in large-scale monitoring programmes and collect relevant data
- Development and testing of new methods of monitoring soil status using remote sensing, citizen science and field sensors
- Spatial maps to identify areas impacted by degradation or pollution, hotspots of biodiversity or carbon stocks, eroded land or land prone to erosion, etc., to support decisions and actions to address these impacts
- Appropriate models to simulate soil health dynamics (degradation or remediation) and to assess the impact of changes in land management on soil functions such as soil organic carbon storage, greenhouse gas emissions, biological activity, or water retention to prevent droughts and floods
- Assessment of socio-economic conditions and barriers for implementing solutions and practices, accompanied by new business models for land users/owners
- Synergies and trade-offs between soil health objectives and human health, climate action, water cycle/quality, biodiversity, and food security.
- Development of (action- and practice-oriented) guidelines and decision-making tools for stakeholders involved in soil management and remediation, bringing together existing knowledge. To ensure the accessibility, relevance and acceptance of such guidelines and tools, they should be developed jointly with the target group in a co-development process.

In the following, the key knowledge gaps for each SMO are presented by first summarising the most important points and then providing a table listing all key knowledge gaps, required research actions and expected results along the impact pathway. At the end of each sub-chapter, an additional assessment of the limitations and possible further developments of the content is included. Detailed factsheets for each knowledge gap are provided in Annex I outlining in addition the relevant land use sectors, regional scope, urgency, synergies with other SMOs, end user, key stakeholders to involve, intermediaries as the role of living labs and lighthouses. Living labs are seen as highly valuable areas in which to develop this research and achieve these goals by building bridges between soil users, land managers, scientists and citizens (see Box 2).

Box 2:

The Soil Mission sees living laboratories (LLs) and lighthouses (LHs) as instruments to accelerate the creation and uptake of solutions to meet the specific objectives across farms, forest, landscapes and urban settings in a diversity of geographical and socio-economic contexts (EC, 2021). The implementation plan proposed a set of criteria to describe Soil Health Living Labs and Light Houses. Maring et al. (2022) further elaborated these criteria by characterising LL and LH as following:

	LL	LH
Scale	Multiple experimenting or test sites; orchestration of the LL sites is conducted on regional/landscape scale	Site: farm, cooperation of number of farms, urban site, forest exploitation, etc.
Aims	Aimed at achieving societal and environmental impacts / benefits in relation to the soil mission objectives by means of co-creation or co-design processes	Aimed at demonstrating exemplary performance in terms of soil health and ecosystem services in relation to the soil mission objectives
Activities	Co-creation/co-design/co-development of research and innovation in a transdisciplinary and multi-actor approach and robust setup Monitoring/evaluation on soil health /ESS of the research /innovation influence	Activities aimed at demonstration, dissemination and exploitation of a high-performance (e.g. overall management system) to other parties (soil managers, public, policy arena)
Participants	Multiple participants in a public-private-people partnership, including real users	PPP partnerships and active engagement of potential future users and target audiences
Context	Participatory and open approach in a real-life context (place-based) and within a context familiar to the users (agricultural, urban, forest). Living Labs are conducted on the (middle to) long term	Place-based and well-defined system boundaries in a real life demonstrative context

4.1 Reduce land degradation relating to desertification (SMO1)

Land degradation and desertification is associated with a loss of soil productivity and other soil ecosystem services. Both human activities and climate change have an impact on these processes. The focus is on arid areas, but other pedo-climatic zones are also affected. While the agricultural sector, including forests, has traditionally been the focus of action because it suffers directly from the loss of productivity, it was highlighted that urban and industrial sites too should receive more attention. Three important knowledge gaps have been identified:

Lack of definitions and knowledge on degradation processes and drivers (SMO1-1) There is a need to co-develop proper definitions of when soils are degraded for all sectors (separately). Long-term experiments on land degradation and desertification processes in different climatic regions and land use types are urgently needed to understand how land degradation processes are set in motion and what impacts they have (e.g. human health) from the field to the landscape level. Both the socio-economic drivers and the changing climate conditions in the short, medium, and long term need to be studied and models developed to assess how areas at risk will change in the future and to identify hotspot regions for prevention measures.

Lack of indicators, thresholds, and monitoring system to quantify soil degradation in Europe (SMO1-2) It is highlighted that there is an urgent need to develop and agree on a set of easily measurable, cost-effective indicators and data management approaches to take stock of where desertification processes occur in the EU. This set of indicators should include early warning signals and thresholds for different types of soil degradation, soils, and sectors. EU expert groups should be involved to push for their use and implementation

at both EU and national levels. The results could be used to set targets for different land use sectors, to report on the effects of soil policies at national/local level and to inform citizens about the state of soils. Guidelines should be developed and training offered to farm advisors in order to disseminate the knowledge to land managers and help them track transitions and changes in management.

Lack of appropriate and cost-effective prevention and restoration options for degraded soils (SMO 1-3)

There is a short-term need to fund long-term research on cost-effective prevention and restoration options, including the assessment of trade-offs for different land use types and pedo-climatic zones with a focus on arid regions. Such research should involve socio-economic scientists as well as land managers, farm advisors and agri-business to co-develop mutually accepted solutions, e.g. in living labs. To foster a wide uptake of the measures by land managers, cost-impact assessments of soil degradation are needed to show the agronomic effects of different conservation and restoration measures. The knowledge gained should be incorporated into agricultural education and advisory services and used to harmonise funding instruments at EU level.

Table 1: Impact pathway for SMO1 - Reduce land degradation relating to desertification

Long-term impact: Due to the widespread uptake of effective prevention measures by land managers, no new soil degradation is occurring in line with SDG 15.3 and highly degraded soils have been restored.			
Key knowledge gap	SMO 1-1 Lack of definitions and knowledge on degradation processes and drivers	SMO 1-2 Lack of indicators, thresholds, and monitoring system to quantify soil degradation in Europe	SMO 1-3 Lack of suitable and cost-effective prevention and restoration options for different pedo-climatic zones and land use types
Sub-knowledge gaps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lack of definition on when land is degraded for different land uses 2. Lack of knowledge on how land degradation processes initiate and impact soil and human health from a field to landscape scale. 3. Lack of knowledge on the interplay of climate change and socio-economic drivers to cause multiple land degradation processes 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lack of harmonised, easy to measure, cost-effective indicators that take into account a multitude of desertification processes and thresholds to ecosystem collapse, land remediation and international reporting requirements - also for urban and industrial areas 2. Lack of knowledge where land degradation and desertification take place in Europe including urban and industrial areas and how this is likely to change due to climate change and the loss of biodiversity 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Lack of cost-impact assessments of land and soil degradation and agronomic effects of different conservation measures (especially in arid regions) 4. Lack of prevention options and knowledge of their impact, trade-offs and durability in different pedo-climatic zones and land use types 5. Lack of restoration options addressing a wide range of soil functions and land uses and knowledge of their impact on soil health and durability in different pedo-climatic zones 4. Lack of harmonised policies to replace harmful subsidies to prevent desertification
Actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop proper definitions of land degradation for different land uses and sectors - Identify (socio-economic) drivers for land degradation and assess related desertification processes on different scales, including urban and industrial areas - Assess and model the impact of climate change and other drivers on land degradation across 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop a set of easy measurable, cost-effective indicators including early-warning signals, thresholds, and approaches for data management for different types of soil degradation and sectors. - Taking stock of where desertification processes occur in the EU and how the areas at risk will change in the future due to climate change and the loss of biodiversity. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identify suitable prevention and restoration options for land degradation and assess trade-offs for different land use types and pedo-climatic conditions in the EU - Establish and evaluate long-term records of prevention and restoration measures (for different land use systems) with a focus on cost effectiveness. - Include prevention and restoration measures for desertification in agricultural education and advisory services

	Europe in short, medium and long term		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mainstream preventing and restoring land degradation in all policies as a priority action including different incentive schemes - Include prevention and restoration measures for desertification in National Adaptation Plans
Output	Clear definitions of 'degraded land' and knowledge about drivers, processes and impacts related to degradation/desertification for different land uses	A comprehensive set of indicators and thresholds to measure and monitor desertification processes is ready to use in all land uses and regions of Europe	Comprehensive climate, soil and land use specific overview of desertification prevention and restoration options including cost-benefits, synergies, and trade-offs to guide land managers
Outcome (Short- and medium-term effects)	Improved definitions and understanding of what land degradation is, which processes underlie desertification and how drivers such as climate change impact land degradation across Europe.	Increased measurability of land degradation and desertification in all land uses and implementation of a harmonised EU-wide monitoring system.	Increased uptake of effective land degradation prevention and restoration measures.

Limitations:

Given the diverse character of complex environmental topics such as desertification and soil degradation, and the added factor of the European scope of this report, only the surface can be scratched. The here presented fact sheets summarize overarching gaps that need to be addressed in order to achieve the Soil Mission Objective 1.

Further development:

While some of the here presented gaps may be partially addressed by previous, or ongoing projects, more detailed and, most of all, location and community specific knowledge, paired with a common understanding of the problems and possible solutions, are needed. Going into such detail was not possible here, but is an urgent challenge for future projects and initiatives. Hence, many of the here presented gaps should help as guidelines for Living Labs in order to create such local knowledge and understanding.

4.2 Conserve and increase soil organic carbon stocks (SMO2)

Conserving and increasing soil organic carbon (SOC) stocks is the key to ensuring the functioning and productivity of soils, but also to achieving climate goals, as increasing SOC concentration and stock allows CO₂ to be removed from the atmosphere. A particular focus is on areas with high SOC content such as peatlands and wetlands, but also rangelands and agriculture areas which are negatively impacted by intensification and/or degraded and are therefore losing their capacity to capture CO₂. Four important knowledge gaps have been identified:

Lack of knowledge of the effects of different soil properties and management practices on SOC and its threshold levels, stability, and ecosystem services (SMO2-1) There is an urgent need to develop and maintain long-term experiments and living labs where SOC can be measured and monitored under different environmental and management conditions to build robust evidence on the links between soil and land management and SOC. Researchers as well as land managers and advisors, landowners and managers should be involved in the research, development and implementation of living labs and the communication of results. Research activities should lead to targeted guidelines on suitable management options and enable the development of an interactive map of historical land use and status of SOC stocks in the EU, linked to the management guidelines and SOC forecasting tools, showcasing the potential for SOC increase.

Lack of short and long-term, in-field and remote SOC testing methods and knowledge of SOC storage potential for EU soils (SMO2-2) To address this gap, new methods and approaches to measure and monitor SOC, as well as maps for SOC stocks/storage potential, need to be developed and tested by researchers. Moreover, harmonised SOC testing methods are needed to develop an EU-wide database of SOC baselines and potentials where policy makers can set requirements for reporting templates. Mapping the SOC storing potential at global, national and regional levels can support the development of tailored land management strategies and raise awareness of the importance of SOC. Overall, there should be a particular focus on high SOC areas, critical hotspots of SOC losses, as well as regional fire risks.

Lack of short and long-term business models for economic effects of loss/storage of SOC and pedo-climatic specific guidelines for increasing SOC (SMO2-3) In the short term, guidelines, and monitoring, reporting and verification (MRV) protocols need to be tested under field conditions and reviewed by policy makers to avoid double counting. MRV also needs to capture long-term SOC dynamics to address permanence and reversibility issues. Realistic business models the economic impacts of SOC loss/storage and contribution to climate change mitigation targets must be developed in close collaboration between economists, soil scientists and the agri-business to ensure their robustness and link to carbon farming schemes. These business models are expected to incentivise carbon storage and conservation. The results, such as an economic assessment of land management systems and recommendations for management practices to be implemented and included in carbon markets, can support the financing of sustainable land management practices.

Lack of effective policies, incentives, and emissions trading and reporting platforms for SOC conservation (SMO2-4) There is an urgent need to define policies on SOC emissions trading (e.g. to remove the potential for double counting between CAP and carbon farming). Such measures can encourage industry and investors to participate in emissions trading so that they can offset carbon emissions while ensuring benefits for land managers. This would also require the development of reporting platforms for national SOC stocks reporting and emissions trading, business models on which these platforms are based and the establishment of suitable MRV systems.

Table 2: Impact pathway for SMO 2 - Conserve and increase soil organic carbon stocks

Long-term impact: A net increase in carbon stored in European soil, with minimal SOC loss from anthropogenic activities, due to EU-wide implementation of measures as a result of scientific research and stakeholder knowledge, aided by EU policies and government-backed incentive schemes.				
Key knowledge gap	SMO 2-1 Lack of knowledge of the effects of different soil properties and management practices on soil organic carbon (SOC) and its threshold levels, stability, and ecosystem services	SMO 2-2 Lack of short and long-term, in-field and remote SOC test methods and knowledge of SOC storage potential for EU soils	SMO 2-3 Lack of short and long-term business models for economic effects of loss/storage of SOC and pedo-climatic specific guidelines for increasing SOC	SMO 2-4 Lack of effective policies, incentives, and emissions trading and reporting platforms for SOC conservation
Sub-knowledge gaps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of information on and demonstrating effects and potential of various management practices on SOC storage, conservation and losses for different soil types and depths Lack of knowledge about the threshold levels and stability of 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of harmonised and user-friendly in-field test methods for SOC Lack of a systematic and long-term SOC monitoring (remote and in-field) Lack of information on SOC stocks and 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of short and long-term economic effects of increased SOC and losses at farm-level and business models to incentivise carbon storage and conservation Lack of information on trade-offs of funding schemes including carbon farming 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of effective and fair private-public payment schemes (together with financial institutions) and functional incentives for preserving and enhancing soil carbon sequestration (see also SMO2-3) including the promo-

	<p>soil carbon under different management, climatic conditions, soil properties (e.g. soil type, farming system, tillage system, nutrient levels, soil microbiome) the role of biodiversity and under climate change</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Lack of knowledge about the short and long-term effects and co-benefits of SOC on ecosystems services 4. Lack of knowledge about the effects soil nutrient status and balance (in particular for nitrogen and phosphorus) for SOC storage and conservation 	<p>storage potential for EU soils</p>	<p>payment schemes as well as funding in less effective measures</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Lack of regional and pedo-climatic specific guidelines including measures to maintain (e.g. prevent from degradation) and increase SOC 	<p>tion of non-peat alternatives for horticultural purposes</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Lack of knowledge of the effectiveness of policy instruments for increasing soil carbon stocks 3. Lack of platforms for national SOC stocks reporting and emissions trading
Actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Monitor changes in SOC in response to different management practices and identify factors which help to stabilise SOC including the role of biodiversity in the long-term for different soil types at different soil depths - Explore short and long-term benefits of increases in SOC on ecosystem services - Identify the ability of different soils under different climate conditions to sequester and store SOC - Explore the effects of different nutrient management systems in combination for a range of agricultural systems on SOC 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop harmonised methods to quantify SOC stocks and soil organic matter quality and indicators to assess SOC dynamics (remote and in-field) to use in Monitoring, Verification and Reporting (MRV) or incentive systems - Identify a baseline for current SOC stocks and quantify potential storage for EU soils for different location and climate conditions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identify economic effects of increased SOC sequestration and losses and develop business models for different sectors (e.g., agriculture, forestry, urban sector) to provide the financial basis for trading carbon - Analyse the effectiveness and trade-offs of funding schemes - Develop regional guidelines to promote SOC storage under different management and pedo-climatic conditions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identify priority areas where public support for SOC improvement is most needed and develop subsidy-frameworks for carbon sequestration - Evaluate the effectiveness of existing and future policy instruments including models for projected policy outputs, consider economic impact - Develop emission factors for different soil types, pedo-climatic conditions and management for national SOC stocks reporting and emissions trading
Output	<p>Overview of the potential of soils to store carbon under specific conditions and measures to increase and preserve SOC in relation to soil types and climate as</p>	<p>Robust MRV systems (in-field and remote) and overview of the potential and current carbon stock of European soils</p>	<p>Decision support tools and tailored guidelines including socio-economic effects for different sectors and farming systems under various pedo-climatic conditions</p>	<p>Carbon payment schemes (incl. carbon farming) that promote conservation and enhancement of SOC including wider economic impacts based on scientific research</p>

	well as their corresponding ecosystem responses in the short and long-term			
Outcome (Short- and medium-term effects)	Increased understanding of soil organic carbon dynamics under management and effects on ecosystem services in the short and long term	EU-wide implementation of a harmonised monitoring system and identification of most critical hotspots of SOC storage and losses	Increased awareness and widespread uptake of measures to store and conserve SOC across different sectors	EU-wide implemented effective policy measures including payment schemes to maintain and foster SOC sequestration and increased SOC accounting in national and European GHG inventories

Limitations:

The identification of knowledge gaps for SMO6 considered all kinds of land uses, soil types and climatic conditions resulting in a large collection of practices and technologies that may be applied to conserve and/or increase soil organic carbon stocks. However, as we are still lacking knowledge on the desirable levels and the stability of soil carbon under different land uses, management and climatic conditions, soil properties (e.g. soil type, farming/forest/urban system, nutrient levels, soil microbiome) it is rather difficult to recommend any practices and/or technologies to be universally adopted or pushed. The same is true concerning trade-offs between carbon stocks maintenance and improvement and other environmental issues such as N₂O emission or herbicides use.

Further development:

The knowledge identified within the SMS project should be combined with other existing projects (e.g. EJP SOIL actions on agricultural soils, HOLISOIL actions on forest soils) to develop for each land use regional guidelines to promote SOC storage under different management and pedoclimatic conditions. Doing so, proper practices and technologies may be promoted.

4.3 No net soil sealing and increase the reuse of urban soils (SMO3)

The progressive sealing of soils and land consumption due to urbanisation and infrastructure developments usually lead to a complete loss of soil functions and services. Targeted actions are needed to achieve the no net land take target by 2050. This mainly concerns urban areas and industry, but also agriculture and forestry areas, which are at risk of being sealed.

Lack of indicators to monitor soil sealing and land take processes and their impact (SMO3-1) Indicators need to be developed to map and monitor the dynamics of land use and soil sealing and their impacts on soil functions and services, problems and opportunities. On this basis, European regions should set targets for land use and soil sealing by 2030 and 2050 that can be monitored regularly to measure progress against an established baseline. Researchers are asked to analyse monitoring data on the status and trend of soil sealing and land take and inform policy makers on the necessary future measures.

Lack of guidance for avoiding soil sealing and reusing land and soil and conserving soil functions (SMO3-2) There is a great need to identify, assess and demonstrate measures to reduce/prevent soil sealing and rehabilitate soils and enhance soil reuse, as well as to develop effective tools to analyse soil quality and track soil transportation. These findings should inform the development of guidelines aimed at the building sector, regional spatial planning authorities and policy makers to assist them in avoiding soil sealing and reusing soils. In this context, compensation schemes for unavoidable soil sealing also need to be developed, which can be made mandatory to ensure that the loss of soil functions is compensated.

Lack of awareness of the benefits and values of unsealed soils and urban green and blue infrastructure (GBI) and nature-based solutions (NBS) (SMO3-3) In the short term, tailored education material should be developed for all European regions to increase awareness of the benefits of functional /unsealed soils, GBI and NBS, prevention measures for different target groups (decision makers, urban planners, citizens and kids), and the potential of a nature-based economy for the local and regional economic development. To enable effective communication, the material should be designed so that it can be easily adapted to different contexts, translated into all EU languages, and disseminated through large city and education networks.

Lack of policies and assessment/support tools at municipal level to reduce soil sealing and land take (SMO3-4) There is a strong need to support local policy makers with tools to evaluate development plans and ecosystem service delivery and tools to support green public procurement and other economic instruments prevent soil sealing or compensate soil sealing impact. Moreover, support is needed to develop effective policy framework programmes, new governance models and co-creation approaches for more integrated urban planning that will allow local and regional governments and planning departments to redesign existing planning frameworks and practices and improve administrative procedures.

Lack of spatial planning tools and architectural innovations (SMO3-5) There is an urgent need to develop tools and concepts that support integrated planning and soil health and enable collaboration with practitioners targeting regional spatial planners. It is recommended making use of living labs and lighthouses to carry out pilot projects and expand the knowledge base. It is equally important that architects work with the construction industry to develop architectural innovations that free up as much functional soil as possible that can be used for GBI and NBS.

Table 3: Impact pathway for SMO 3 – No net sealing and increase the reuse of urban soil

Long-term impact: No net land take in Europe by 2050 by effectively preventing soil sealing and land take and rehabilitating/re-using industrial soils and brownfields by providing actionable knowledge, approaches, and tools to empower policy and decision makers, planners to take adequate action					
Key knowledge gap	SMO 3-1 Lack of indicators to monitor soil sealing and land take processes and their impact	SMO 3-2 Lack of guidance for avoiding soil sealing and reusing land and soil and conserving soil functions	SMO 3-3 Lacking awareness about the benefits and values of unsealed soils and urban green and blue infrastructure and nature-based solutions	SMO 3-4 Lack of policies and assessment/ support tools at municipal level to reduce soil sealing and land take.	SMO 3-5 Lack of spatial planning tools and architectural innovations
Sub-knowledge gaps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of indicators and holistic approaches to assess the impact of land take and soil sealing and their dynamics and impacts on soil functions Lack of monitoring of land take and soil sealing processes at different scales and the loss of soil functions 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Lacking guidance for reusing land and soil conserving soil functions including (cost-)effective tools to analyse soil quality and track soil transportation ("soil passport") Lack of concepts for adequate replacement options and rehabilitation measures for soil sealing to increase water infiltration and generate 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of knowledge about the wider educational, social & environmental impact of unsealed soil and co-created urban green and blue infrastructure (GBI) and nature-based solutions (NBS) Lack of knowledge about the barriers and potential stimulation of a nature-based economy that creates green 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of assessment tool for local policy makers to evaluate development plans and ecosystem service delivery Lack of support tools for green public procurement at municipal level. Lack of robust EU and national policies, programmes, legal frameworks, and regulations including short- and 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of integrated urban and landscape planning and management approaches Lack of knowledge about the inclusion of the concept of "healthy soils" and the weighting of soil functions in spatial planning Lack of architectural innovations to contribute to sus-

		<p>multiple benefits</p> <p>3. Insufficient knowledge of using organic waste for soil rehabilitation and creating synergies with circular economy</p> <p>4. Lack of methods to identify areas for de-sealing measures</p>	<p>jobs, avoid soil sealing and apply regenerative practices.</p>	<p>long-term strategic targets and economic instruments that help to reduce/avoid land take or compensate the impacts of soil sealing.</p> <p>4. Lack of concepts and models to increase cooperation among different (sectoral) administrations</p>	<p>tainable solutions (including innovations in the architectural and building sector regarding the densification of existing urban areas to avoid building on green areas)</p>
Actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop and test indicators for mapping and monitoring land take and soil sealing dynamics and their effects on soil functions & services, problems, and opportunities - Develop and promote databases for land consumption and indicators for environmental effects of urban development also (informing policy processes such as Strategic Environment Assessment) at different scale 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identify, assess, and demonstrate measures to reduce/prevent soil sealing and rehabilitate (industrial/brown-field) soils, safe and cost-effective soil reuse, and increase water infiltration (NBS, regenerative agriculture, permeable surfaces etc.) - Explore methods and develop effective tools to analyse soil quality and track soil transportation and create new soils (constructed techno soils) from excavated soils and organic wastes - Explore and assess the potential, benefits, and trade-offs to combine circular economy approaches with reusing soils 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop and test tailored education material to increase awareness about i) benefits of functional/unsealed soils, GBI and NBS, ii) preventing measures for different target groups (decision makers, urban planners, citizens, kids, etc.), and iii) the potential of a nature-based economy for the local and regional economic development - Identify and engage with soil ambassadors at different levels 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identify and assess the legal and socio-economic dimension of land take across Member States - Develop targets for unsealing and for reusing sites - Develop effective framework programmes and economic tools (e.g. taxes, incentives, eco-budgeting schemes) to prevent soil sealing or compensate soil sealing impacts - Develop decision frameworks for local policy makers for evaluating development plans and ecosystem service delivery - Identify and develop new governance models and co-creation approaches for more integrated urban planning to improve acceptance of innovation and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop integrated landscape planning and management approaches that balance different demands for land use and bring together key stakeholders for joint action to prevent soil sealing, minimise negative impacts, increase urban recycling of land and foster multifunctional land use (e.g. local Green Deals) and efficient use of urban space - Develop guidelines how to weight and integrate soil functions and services (soil health) in urban and spatial planning - Develop architectural and building solutions to minimize soil sealing

				<p>reduce reluctance from regulatory bodies, breaking administrative silos and foster stewardship and inclusion</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identify and developed approaches to include cross-departmental and cross-sectoral collaboration in integrated planning, in combination with mainstreaming a net-zero soil sealing target - Develop ways to utilise policy levers such as collaboration platforms, financing support schemes or public procurement and planning strategies such as compact city planning, sustainable land management, landscape-level approaches, and rural-urban partnerships 	
Output	Overview/tool of validated standard procedures (including indicators) for quantification and evaluation of the impacts of land take and soil sealing.	Guidance for prevention and rehabilitation measures (incl. benefits, trade-offs, design, applicability, requirements, costs)	Tailored education material and tools on benefits and values of unsealed soils and urban green and blue infrastructure for different audiences	Overview of policy instruments, approaches, and tools for effective decision-making to prevent and reduce soil sealing	Overview of integrate landscape planning and management approaches including architectural solutions and guidance how to include soil functions in spatial planning and to reduce the impact of soil sealing.
Outcome (Short- and medium-term effects)	Wide adoption of standard procedures with the result that soil sealing is reduced and the loss of soil functions can be quantified and compensated for	Increased understanding and uptake of options to prevent soil sealing/rehabilitate soils at among decision-makers and planners.	Increased awareness about benefits of unsealed soils and green infrastructure leads to behavioural change at different levels (i.e. house owners, spatial planners, developers	EU-wide implementation of policy instruments and targets to reduce and compensate soil sealing and avoid/reduce land take	EU wide implementation of concepts for integrated spatial planning and landscape management approaches to minimize the impact of soil sealing

Limitations:

The factsheets of SMO3 consider the whole cycle of the phenomenon soil sealing. Research can only go as far as to measure and monitor a phenomenon, develop and test new methods to avoid, mitigate or compensate for the impacts, produce awareness raising and educational material, provide guidance for the policy level and involve the relevant economic sectors (in this case the building sector). All these aspects are covered.

Further development:

In view of the overall goal “no net land take by 2050” avoidance of land take and compensation of soil sealing are urgently needed. Compensation of soil functions is not well established and hardly implemented (with the exception of Germany and Switzerland). Future projects should focus on methods to compensate for the impact of soil sealing, architectural innovation in order to reduce land take, multidisciplinary research and the development of “no net land take living labs”.

4.4 Reduce soil pollution and enhance restoration (SMO4)

Reducing soil pollution and fostering soil restoration is essential for soil and human health. Industrial agriculture as well as urban and industrial activities are major polluter of soils. Nevertheless, all land use sectors and regions as well as society as a whole, benefit directly from addressing this soil threat. Five key knowledge gaps were identified:

Lack of knowledge of the fate and impact of pollutants (SMO 4-1) There is a need to improve the understanding of short- and long-term fate and impact of (combined) soil pollutants including emerging contaminants (e.g. microplastic or antibiotic resistant bacteria) and pollution threats in terms of circular economy on soil and human health under different conditions. To fill this knowledge gap, on the one hand, studies are needed on a large number of polluted soils across Europe, and on the other hand, long-term observations at the same sites are needed. Findings should be taken up by policy maker and administration to integrate them in regulatory safety assessments.

Lack of cost-effective methods for mapping and monitoring of pollution (SMO 4-2) To assess the status of soil pollution in the EU there is a need for specific indicators to assess soil health of polluted and remediated soils and robust, smart, (cost-)effective and harmonised methods to map and monitor soil pollution. The assessment of soil type-specific pollution factors is required to map heavily or irreversibly polluted soils. In the short-term projects should concentrate on exploring the state-of-the-art of monitoring and mapping methods and facilitate knowledge exchange to share experiences among initiatives across Europe with the result of agreed monitoring schemes. Digital transformation, the development of innovative sensing methods and the use of existing data and machine learning hold great potential.

Lack of suitable approaches and innovations regarding prevention and remediation (SMO 4-3) Innovative approaches, cost-effective measures and nature-based solutions are needed to prevent soil pollution and remediate polluted soils. The development of new measures and approaches should be wide-ranging and take into account technical, legal, organisational and awareness-raising approaches. Risk assessments and material reuse solutions are needed to prevent the risk of new pollution in the context of the circular economy. Living labs and lighthouses can be a vehicle for research and the co-development of guidelines on verified and accepted sustainable soil management measures and approaches. The most cost-effective way is to prevent further pollution. For this, machine learning should be used to predict future risks, including from emerging contaminants.

Lack of knowledge exchange and capacity building on measures to avoid soil pollution (SMO 4-4) To increase capacities within and among EU Member states there is a need to develop effective communication, dissemination, and knowledge exchange methods. The communication strategies should address land managers, consultancy firms and companies (e.g. specialised in soil remediation) to inform them about best and

new methods to prevent pollution and restore soils. Knowledge exchange between more and less experienced Member States and organisations on soil remediation and brownfield management should be promoted. There is also a need for communication strategies and improved knowledge transfer on the impacts and prevention of soil pollution to other stakeholders, including schools and citizens. Living labs and lighthouses could play an important role in demonstrating solutions and best practices.

Lack of targets and incentives to start restoration (SMO 4-5) There is an urgent need to develop guidance on how to set realistic and effective remediation targets, prioritise polluted sites considering cost-effectiveness and reuse materials in the light of circular economy on the EU level. To incentivise the restoration of polluted soils in Europe, EU and national funding programmes and business models need to be co-developed.

Table 4: Impact pathway for SMO 4 – Reduce soil pollution and enhance restoration

Long-term impact: Reduced use, risk and release of hazardous substances to soils/the environment and enhanced restoration of polluted soils, to meet the 2050 target that soil pollution is reduced to levels no longer considered harmful to human health and natural ecosystems.					
Key knowledge gap	SMO 4-1 Lack of knowledge of the fate and impact of pollutants	SMO 4-2 Lack of cost-effective methods for mapping and monitoring of pollution	SMO 4-3 Lack of suitable approaches and innovations regarding prevention and remediation	SMO 4-4 Lack of knowledge exchange and capacity building on measures to avoid soil pollution	SMO 4-5 Lack of effective targets and approaches to prioritise and incentivise restoration
Sub-knowledge gaps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Lacking or insufficient knowledge of short- and long-term impacts of Contaminants of Concern (CoC - especially emerging, microplastics, antibiotic resistant bacteria and chemical mixtures) on soil health, ecosystem services, food chains and human health Lacking or insufficient knowledge of pollution threats in terms of circular economy (e.g. material (re)use, such as biochar, sand and compost) 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of EU-wide harmonised, robust and smart monitoring methods for mapping and monitoring soil pollution in Europe Lack of (cost-)effective tools and indicators to assess soil health of polluted and remediated soils Lack of knowledge in the use of existing data to predict future risks, e.g. through machine learning 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Lacking or insufficient knowledge of sustainable pollution prevention and remediation <u>approaches</u> including how 'land stewardship' can improve the overall performance of ecosystem services Knowledge of pollution prevention and of remediation <u>measures</u> including nature-based solutions and methods for safe circular reuse of materials with a special focus on cost- and energy-effectiveness and technical, organisational, and legal implementation 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of communication methods and capacity building for measures that can cause or prevent pollution and thus affect soil health Lack of professional training on soils and groundwater in schools, universities, relevant authorities and companies Lack of sufficient methods to improve the exchange of knowledge between Member States on remediation techniques and the management of polluted sites 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of EU and national soil pollution prevention and remediation targets (incl. for emerging contaminants) Lack of methods to prioritise polluted sites in Europe Lack of adequate incentives, programmes, funding mechanisms, business models and control mechanisms to start restoration Lack of knowledge of how pollution hinders circular economy, e.g. (re)use, of materials such as biochar, sand, compost

<p>Actions</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Long- and short-term effects and risks of CoC, especially emerging contaminants, Substances of Very High Concern (SVHC) and chemical mixtures on the ecosystem (soil health) and human health from polluted sites across Europe and under different soil management regimes and land uses. For achieving long-term observations subsequent projects should preferably be executed at the same sites. - Integrate assessments of the impacts of chemicals on both soil and human health as part of the regulatory safety assessment, especially for pesticides. - Identify and assess the risks and potential of the reuse of materials (sand, clay, gravel, biochar, compost etc.) in the light of circular economy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop a set of indicators related to soil health specifically for polluted/remediated sites - Explore the state-of-the-art of (smart) monitoring and mapping methods - Assess the potential of digital transformation and develop innovative sensing methods and tools - Exchange monitoring and mapping methods through initiatives (incl. networks, platforms, research infrastructures) to further harmonise these methods throughout Europe - Develop ways to use machine learning to predict risks of pollutants 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identify and develop cost effective measures to prevent pollution and to deal with emerging contaminants including microplastic in soils. Make use of machine learning to predict future risks. - Identify target values in the context of restoring soils in relation to their use. - Develop, verify and approve more cost and energy efficient remediation techniques and nature-based solutions - Develop legal, financial and awareness-raising approaches for the prevention of contamination and restoration of contaminated sites and brownfields (such as land stewardship concepts) - Identify methods and approaches to reduce the risks of the reuse of materials (sand, clay, gravel, biochar, compost etc.) including testing, cleaning, monitoring, financial, legal and governance aspects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop education material and professional training on the effects and the prevention of soil pollution for different stakeholder groups including schools and citizens - Define priorities and develop effective dissemination methods for measures (incl. alternatives) that can cause pollution or affect soil health in order to prevent these - Develop methods to increase knowledge exchange between more and less experienced member states and organisations on remediation techniques, soil restoration and brownfield management 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop for all member states guidance on how to set remediation targets, prioritize polluted sites, reuse materials and on how to draft a soil management strategy - Develop a prioritisation method and nature-positive incentives/funding mechanisms/programmes for contaminated sites and brownfields in Europe
<p>Output</p>	<p>Characterisation of the main environmental pollutants in soil and insights on their fate and</p>	<p>Agreed and shared robust monitoring schemes based on (cost) effective monitoring methods to assess the status</p>	<p>Guidance on sustainable site management measures and approaches that prevent contamination</p>	<p>Dissemination and capacity building methods for sustainable soil management measures and techniques to avoid</p>	<p>Regulation, policy standards, targets and programmes for remediation on the European scale</p>

	transport under different soil management regimes	and changes in soil pollution in Europe	tion and a comprehensive overview of applicable verified and accepted sustainable, cost and energy efficient remediation techniques	soil pollution within Europe.	
Outcome (Short- and medium-term effects)	Improved understanding of short- and long-term fate and impact of soil pollutants on soil and human health and under different circumstances	In-depth insights in the status of and changes in soil contamination in Europe to inform policy	Improved possibilities to accelerate remediation processes in Europe at lower costs and avoid or reduce further negative impacts on the environment	Improved exchange and increased knowledge on and use of techniques and methods that prevent pollution or restore polluted sites and thus protect or restore soil health	Better implementation of sustainable remediation of polluted soils in all Member States

Limitations:

The knowledge gaps identified for SMO4 focus more on research and less on demonstration of good practice and wider adaptation of these practices. However, there is a solid knowledge base on this topic including good practice and policy. Risk assessment methods for sites have been developed through previous R&I projects over the last decades and have been incorporated into the legal and policy schemes of most Member States. Further elaboration of risk assessment for the reuse of materials to support the circular economy is considered in the factsheets. However, the inclusion of 'soil health' as a receptor of soil contamination is worth further elaboration of risk assessment methods. This will be taken up in a follow-up project under the HORIZON-MISS-2022-SOIL-01 call.

Further Development:

Future actions should focus more on how to promote better adaptation of good practices and thus better dissemination and exploitation in all Member States. Capacity building and learning by doing (e.g. in a LL setting) is key to implement these good practices. Follow up projects on the roadmap development for SMO4 (e.g. the SOLO project) as well as the projects under mission call HORIZON-MISS-2022-SOIL-01 should further elaborate the knowledge gaps for methods and approaches to tackle 1) large scale diffuse contaminations and portfolios of sites and 2) so-called "left-behind areas" within Europe. The latter being e.g. mining sites that are impacted by the European green transition that next to impacted land can deal with less favorable socio-economic circumstances. These are not emphasized in the factsheets but still have a large number of challenges and should be further elaborated.

4.5 Prevent erosion (SMO5)

The loss of fertile soil through erosion is a significant problem, especially in (but not limited to) the Mediterranean and in mountainous regions. Changing erosion dynamics can be expected with climate change. Nutrients and pollutants are transported with the soil leading to offsite impacts such as sediment transport and eutrophication of freshwater systems. In agriculture, erosion is associated with declining yields. Therefore, all land use sectors are concerned by this threat. The following key knowledge gaps were identified:

Lack of knowledge on trade-offs and synergies between soil erosion, climate change and ecosystem services (SMO 5-1) To improve a holistic understanding of the effects of soil erosion and to increase awareness among soil users and policy makers there is a need to assess trade-offs and synergies between erosion (control) and ecosystem services, socio-economic impacts, and the impact of climate change. Models are needed to quantify fluxes of soil organic carbon induced by soil erosion at regional level to be able to include data in

regional and national greenhouse gas emission budgets.

Lack of suitable erosion prevention and restoration measures that are socio-economically viable (SMO 5-2) There is a need to better link erosion control and restoration measures to local (soil) conditions and to assess the socio-economic factors that influence the adoption of these measures by land managers. Research on this topic should therefore be based on participatory approaches and conducted for different land uses and pedo-climatic zones. Solutions for soil restoration should focus on highly eroded landscapes. Lighthouses and living labs are suitable spaces for co-developing measures and telling success stories in regions with erosion problems. The outcomes should be used to design or adjust policy and market instruments to support implementation of erosion prevention and restoration measures.

Lack of monitoring and planning tools for erosion control (SMO 5-3) More research is needed on developing monitoring tools and models to assess the full erosion process for all kinds of erosion and practical tools for erosion control planning to evaluate management choices, assess trade-offs and drive decision making on plot and landscape level. These tools should include not only the detachment part of the process but also the deposition and help to assess the connectivity of the landscape and how sediments (including pollutants, nutrients and soil organic matter) move through the landscape. Actions should combine remote sensing and on-site measurements and be based on a co-design process involving land managers.

Lack of communication strategies regarding effective erosion preventing measures (SMO 5-4) There is a need for tailored education and communication material to raise awareness of the impact of erosion as well as erosion prevention measures for each land use sector. This dissemination material should include maps of erosion risk, possible measures to prevent erosion and material that shows both negative effects of management choices and positive sustainable alternatives that are profitable focussing on local champions.

Table 5: Impact pathway for SMO 5 - Prevent erosion

Long-term impact: The area at risk of erosion is reduced to a sustainable level by raising awareness among land managers and planners and the uptake of local, adapted prevention measures, and soils at risk of erosion are restored.				
Key knowledge gap	SMO 5-1 Lack of knowledge on (socio-economic) trade-offs and synergies between soil erosion, ecosystem services and climate change	SMO 5-2 Lack of suitable erosion prevention and restoration measures that are socio-economically viable	SMO 5-3 Lack of monitoring and planning tools for erosion control	SMO 5-4 Lack of communication strategies and policy tools regarding effective erosion preventing measures
Sub-knowledge gaps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of knowledge of effects and trade-offs of land management (e.g. no-tillage), water management (irrigation and drainage) and climate change including GHG emissions Lack of knowledge on trade-offs and synergies between soil erosion regulation and other ecosystem services both on and off site (field, river, catchment) 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of erosion prevention measures (nature based) better linked to local conditions, economic factors and practitioners' needs (participatory research) for different land uses and pedo-climatic zones Lack of proven restoration options in highly eroded landscapes Lack of knowledge on socio-economic factors influencing the adoption of erosion preventing management 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of evaluation tools for trade-offs of land and water management choices Lack of good monitoring and modelling techniques to assess all kinds of erosion and effects on- and off-site Lack of local "severity maps" that indicate hotspots where immediate action is required (for practitioners and policy makers) Lack of methods to conduct probability estimates of soil erosion events under climate change 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of communication strategies and material to raise awareness (including schools and citizens) Lack of implementation of existing knowledge for erosion prevention by land managers Lack of integration of knowledge about erosion prevention measures into policy

			5. Lack of evaluation tools for trade-offs of land and water management choices	
Actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Study and determine effects, trade-offs and synergies of erosion with a focus on land and water management practices as well as water provision and future impact of climate change on vegetation, soil functions and ecosystem services (from plot to catchment). - Investigate the role of soil hydrology and soil functions like infiltration capacity to reduce the risk of water erosion which is e.g. essential after heavy rains and mild winters in the North. - Investigate the socio-economic impacts, trade-offs and synergies of erosion, including soil erosion induced organic carbon fluxes to be included in regional and national greenhouse gas emission budgets. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Combine socio-economic and participatory research with biophysical research to improve understanding and uptake of prevention measures - Investigate the role of crop rotation by grasses, and the availability for markets for that biomass due to soil improvement by alive and intensive grass rooting, e.g. biogas and dairy. - Develop and test restoration options in eroded landscapes or that are under erosion risk in different pedo-climatic zones under different land uses - Evaluate land use change options to find the right land use or land use combination for each location - Co-design policy and retail (marketing) environments that encourage erosion prevention measures 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop tools for local erosion control planning including trade-offs of land and water management choices on plot and landscape level combining remote sensing and on-site measurements - Develop understanding for the need of soil drainage to avoid excess water flows which cause water erosion - Develop monitoring and modelling tools that can assess the full erosion process (detachment, transport and deposition) in a cost effective, but precise way, including the effect of land management options 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop awareness raising material for all stakeholder types and show sustainable alternatives and how they can be profitable. - Develop attractive alternative sustainable narratives (e.g. for regenerative agriculture and organic farming and agroecology) - Provide maps (regional, national) of applicability and relevance of sustainable soil management strategies to mitigate soil erosion tailored to land use sector (agriculture, forestry, nature, industry, mining, urban) to be used for integrating into policy tools
Output	Holistic overview of effects of erosion and land and water management measures on soil functions and ecosystem services	Overview of prevention and restoration measures in different pedo-climatic zones under different land uses and socio-economic conditions and improved understanding of preventing and promoting factors for swift implementation of good practice	Planning tools and models to evaluate and monitor erosion processes and trade-offs of land and water management practices	Developed and disseminated tailored education and communication material to raise awareness of the impact of erosion and erosion prevention measures
Outcome (Short and medium effects)	Improved understanding of best practices to prevent erosion and minimize trade-offs of different land and water management practices in different pedo-climatic zones.	Improved uptake and choice of prevention and restoration measures based on local conditions and increased understanding of socio-economic and cultural factors	Improved consideration of erosion in land management decision making and planning processes	Increased awareness of the consequences of erosion and of options for preventing and restoring degraded soils that are sustainable from a socio-economic and biophysical perspective and better integration into policy

Limitations:

The identified knowledge gaps and related factsheets for SMO5 are wide-ranging and do not include a summary of existing best practices to prevent soil erosion for each pedoclimatic condition. However, there are already many well-known practices such as cover crops, chipped pruned branches and spreading straw.

Further development:

Research needs to be tailored to different pedoclimatic situations (e.g. How much soil cover from cut branches is needed to reduce erosion in region y by x%?). More collaboration with the social sciences (sociology and economics) is also needed to further develop the content of the fact sheets so that erosion risk mitigation can be implemented on a large scale. There is a need to better understand the barriers and opportunities for upscaling, taking into account existing economic assessments of the costs of land degradation, including externalities, and estimates of the direct benefits of changes in land and soil management.

4.6 Improve soil structure to enhance habitat quality for soil biota and crops (SMO6)

Raising awareness of the links between soil structures and soil biodiversity and its effects for crop production and soil health and implementing practices that support soil biota and create good structure are key issues across all regions and sectors. The following key knowledge gaps were identified:

Lack of knowledge about links between soil structure and functional soil biodiversity including processes in the microbiome as well as their effects on crops (SMO 6-1) In the short term, relevant practices and technologies in long-term experiments (LTE), demonstrating the beneficial relationship between soil management, soil structure, soil functions, microbial activities and crop health, should be described, financed and implemented at larger scale. Moreover, there is a need to develop and test new measuring techniques, support innovations on management practices, new captors, and materials in LTEs to reduce soil compaction and improve soil structure. It is paramount that researchers and land managers collaborate to identify and promote suitable solutions that need to be funded, implemented, and driven by policy makers and agribusiness. The results are expected to identify the main management options, materials and technologies that have a positive impact on soil properties, provide guidance to support the development of the identified options, which should then be implemented and tested in living labs, and finally promote the wider implementation of successfully implemented measures in all regions.

Lack of harmonised indicators to monitor soil structure and functional biodiversity (SMO6-2) All regions are concerned by the development and testing of indicators/benchmarks values to assess and monitor soil structure and functional biodiversity. The aim is to develop in collaboration with the targeted end-users (such as scientists but also land managers, foresters, citizens, land planners) easy applicable indicators. This would also include discussing benchmark values used to interpret the results of the indicators. It is suggested to use a sample of long-term experiments for the indicator development and produce guidelines to support the wider use of indicators in living labs under real situations.

Lack of socio-economic research including cost-benefits assessment and barriers for the uptake of management measures to improve soil structure (SMO 6-3) There is an urgent need to conduct socio-economic and technological research to assess the benefits and trade-offs of improving soil structure including the internal and external costs of changing management practices and the use of smart technology and machinery (e.g. for adapted tillage and traffic), for different land uses. This requires a collaboration of researchers from different disciplines with land managers. The results will help identify cost-effective management options and technologies and ways to inform the right way to change practices. In addition, the results will inform the development of economic incentives, market contracts or labels to encourage the use of appropriate management practices and technologies to reduce soil compaction.

Table 6: Impact pathway for SMO 6 - Improve soil structure to enhance habitat quality for soil biota and crop

Long-term impact: The risk of soil compaction is significantly reduced and soil structure is improved by developing knowledge and raising awareness about soil structure, functional soil biodiversity and soil health and fostering the uptake of new management practices and technologies to mitigate soil compaction.			
Key knowledge gap	SMO 6-1 Lack of knowledge about links between soil structure and functional soil biodiversity including processes in the microbiome as well as their effects on crops	SMO 6-2 Lack of harmonised indicators to monitor soil structure and functional biodiversity	SMO 6-3 Lack of management innovations and associated socio-economic research including cost-benefits for the uptake of management measures to improve soil structure and biota
Sub-knowledge gaps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of knowledge about the links between soil properties (e.g soil type, soil structure), functional soil biodiversity including processes in the microbiome, plant-soil-biome interactions, soil functions and ecosystem services for different land uses Lack of knowledge about the links between soil management practices (e.g. amendment, tillage, conservation agriculture, de-sealing) and soil properties and the resulting functions as crop support Lack of knowledge about management/technical innovations including the use of digitalisation to improve/mitigate soil compaction and improve soil structure for the benefit of soil biota and crops 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of harmonised indicators to measure/monitor soil structure and soil biodiversity (species/functionality) and their dynamics, as well as benchmark values for data interpretation Lack of indicators for functional biodiversity and its links to crop health Lack of measurement protocols for non-scientists to assess soil for different land uses Lack of knowledge on the ecological status of industrial sites Lack of maps of soil-borne disease and parasitic pressure 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of management innovations including the use of digitalisation to reduce soil compaction and improve soil structure for the benefit of soil biota and crops Lack of knowledge on the design of improved field arrangements and landscape elements to avoid compaction and improve soil structure Lack of economic research including cost-benefits assessments to value the role of soil/plant health and related ecosystem services, in link with appropriate management practices in different land uses Lack of socio-economic research to identify potential barriers to adapt new management practices
Actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identify and review existing knowledge Develop and support long-term experimental (LTE) research sites, for different land uses, pedo-climatic condition and management options, to in deep study soil properties, soil functioning and related ecosystem services. Each site should include an in-depth study of soil physic, chemistry and biodiversity and soil functions as well as the improvement/development of in situ/instant measuring methods (e.g. new captors to follow changes in soil status and functioning) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop and test indicators to assess soil structure/soil biodiversity for different soil types (also including industrial/urban sites), climate conditions and land management practices and set up interpretation/benchmark values (i.e. threshold, normal, target values) and link results to crop health. Develop and test different measurement protocols for different land uses, soil types, climate conditions and management practices together with end-users (scientists, citizens, land planners etc.) Promote the development of commercial labs and accessible protocols to measure at low cost those indicators Install monitoring programmes at different scales (EU, national, local) to assess soil/crop status and health. Data should be collected, centralised and accessible to monitor progresses. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identify barriers to adapting management and developing guidelines and decision support tools with a focus on socio-economic factors for land managers based on the results from LTE and LL to share and communicate good practices Identify key actions and innovations (i.e. management practices, new technologies for soil tillage, crop/timber harvest, sealing/de-sealing) to be tested and adapted in living labs across EU Support technology and practice innovations for soil structure Identify and communicate success stories (e.g. via Lighthouses) to showcase the benefits of soil health for soil managers incomes and for society. Develop training initiatives and soil ambassadors to help land managers and soil users to adopt new management practices improving soil health

			- Implement financial support to help transition, e.g. market solutions, incentives, insurances or labels
Output	Overview of site-specific knowledge on the relationship between soil management, soil structure, soil functions, microbial activities and soil/crop health and respective links to land use and management practices. New techniques/technologies/materials (including digital ones) to report on soil status and functioning and prevent soil compaction.	A set of site-specific indicators measurable by commercial labs or trained people to report on soil structure and functional biodiversity (and soil status/health in general) and monitor the effect of changes in management practices.	Tailored guidelines, decision support tools and trainings for land managers to improve soil structure and functional biodiversity and soil and crop health in general
Outcome (Short- and medium-term effects)	Improved site-specific knowledge on the links between soil properties, soil functions/services and crop health and improved adapted management options for different land uses to maximise the provision of soil ecosystem services and reduce soil compaction.	EU- wide adoption of standardized procedures to monitor soil status/health usable by different land users resulting in large datasets able to inform on trends	Wide acceptance and adoption of management practices to improve soil and crop health due to proper incentives, market contracts, labels and identification of barriers

Limitations:

As the knowledge stocktaking for SMO6 within the SMS project concentrate on “soil compaction” and “soil biodiversity” it may not include all kind of knowledge on “soil structure” and on “soil biota”. In particular, the links between soil structure and soil habitat may not have been fully highlighted within this process. Nevertheless, it is assumed that the main gaps were identified.

Further development:

Future projects should concentrate more on the links between soil structure maintenance and improvement and consequences on soil biota and crops to fully cover this Soil Mission Objective. Based on the results the presented impact pathways may be slightly modified (e.g. existing indicators and/or efficient soil management practices may be identified and highlighted).

4.7 Reduce the EU global footprint on soils (SMO7)

The reduction of the EU global footprint on soils is essential for soil health and long-term economic and social stability outside of Europe. The global footprint of European activities should be holistic and go far beyond land consumption but also include a differentiated trade analysis. There is a need to differentiate in terms of world regions, as different regions are differently affected by European consumption patterns, trade regulations and policies. Four key knowledge gaps were identified:

Lack of global soil footprint definitions, problem statements, clear research questions, and building on those, clear science-based metrics, and indicator standards (SMO 7-1) There is a need to define clear research questions and problem statements regarding the importance of global soil health for Europe and the impact of European consumption, trade, production, and policies on soil health outside Europe. Based on the resulted scope of an EU global soil footprint an agreement on definitions for a global footprint on soil health is needed, followed by science-based metrics and indicator standards. The derived indicators may then be included in monitoring systems and regulations.

Lack of suitable data and monitoring systems for assessing the EU global soil footprint (SMO 7-2) To evaluate the impact of industrial activities, consumption pattern, trade regulations and policies in and outside of the EU there is a need to holistically assess soil health dynamics and monitor indicators related to the global footprint on soils. Research projects should identify suitable data sources for soil footprint calculations, develop monitoring schemes elaborating on land use and management-based monitoring systems and economic monitoring and accounting. Data gaps need to be identified and closed, and an international agreement on data and monitoring systems needs to be reached.

Lack of awareness about the importance of the global soil footprint for living conditions outside Europe and communication of practical examples (SMO 7-3) To increase awareness on the importance of the global soil footprint and linkages between domestic consumption and international impacts on soil health among civil society, industry, and business there is a need to develop practical examples and models to show the impact of future consumption-production patterns. Examples and modelling results should be used to develop communication and education campaigns. Collaboration and knowledge exchange could be fostered by identifying and establishing networks and coalitions at EU and global levels.

Lack of mainstreaming of the global soil footprint in EU policies (SMO 7-4) There is a need to assess the impact of EU policies on the global soil footprint and to explore new instruments to reduce negative impacts and trade-offs. Projects should identify hotspots for improvements and propose ways to include indicators and soil footprint concerns in the policy cycle (objective setting, instrument development, ex-ante assessment, monitoring, ex-post assessment).

Table 7: Impact pathway for SMO 7 - Reduce the EU global footprint on soils

Long-term impact: Reduce the EU global footprint (food, timber and biomass imports) on soils and land degradation in Europe (by 20-40%) and significantly outside of Europe by developing and implementing soil health indicators and standards and methods to assess EU global footprint on soils				
Key knowledge gap	SMO 7-1: Lack of global soil footprint definitions, problem statements, clear research questions, and building on those, clear science-based metrics and indicator standards	SMO 7-2: Lack of suitable data and monitoring systems for assessing the EU global soil footprint	SMO 7-3: Lack of awareness about the importance of the global soil footprint for living conditions outside Europe and communication of practical examples	SMO 7-4: Lack of mainstreaming of the global soil footprint in EU policies
Sub-knowledge gaps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of knowledge on the impacts of European consumption, trade, production, European and international policies on soil health deterioration and related environmental and socio-economic challenges outside Europe Lack of knowledge on the feedback loops of soil degradation outside Europe on global social security, food security, human health Insufficient understanding of potential time lags between action in Europe (consumption and production conditions) and impact outside Europe 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Insufficient systemic understanding of qualitative and quantitative aspects of the global footprint linking production and consumption activities (telecoupling) inside the EU to soil health outside EU Lack of knowledge on which existing databases are useful for soil footprint calculations (including present land and soil use and soil quality/health) Lack of monitoring of indicators related to the EU global footprint on soils (see SMO 7-1) 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of awareness about and recognition of the importance of the global soil footprint for living conditions outside Europe Lack of practical examples demonstrating the telecoupling between European activities and soil health outside Europe Lack of simulation/foresight models addressing telecoupling and soil health implications of biomass and food trade on soil health as showcases and scenarios 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of awareness about the importance of the global soil footprint and soil health concerns in national and international policy debates (e.g. EU/UN activities) Lacking knowledge on the impact of EU and global policies (incl. trade and market) on EU global soil footprint and instruments/measures to reduce trade-offs and negative impacts Lacking consideration of soil footprint concerns in national and international policies and trade agreements

	<p>4. Lack of definition of soil footprint (incl. ontologies), indicators, baselines, thresholds, and standards (going beyond land consumption)</p> <p>5. Lack of concepts (metrics/benchmarks) for comparing regions in terms of the relative impacts on soil and soil health of consumption and use of resources</p> <p>6. Lack of sufficient consideration of soil in the Global Footprint Standards¹</p>			
Actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Define clear research questions and problem statements to clarify the aim of having an EU soil footprint. - Develop a holistic definition (incl. ontologies), indicators, baseline, and standards for a global footprint on soils/soil health - Develop approaches to conduct systems analyses spatially linking consumption and production and considering spatial-temporal scales in system boundaries inside EU to soil health outside EU - Conduct research to better understand the impacts of soil degradation on social security, food security, human health - Determine the range of safe operability (of biomass, timber, food production) and thresholds for points of no return - Develop a proposal to include soil in the 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identify and analyse suitable existing data sources for soil quality and resource flows - Develop methods/approaches to holistically assess the global footprint including soil health dynamics - Elaborate on i) land use and management-based monitoring systems including soil health (quality) data, ii) environmental and natural resource use parameters in economic monitoring and accounting 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identify and establish networks/coalitions to foster collaboration and gather/exchange knowledge at EU/global level on the global soil health - Develop campaigns to illustrate impacts on global soil footprint (based on consumption, management impacts, policy impacts, etc.) - Develop foresight scenarios of future consumption - production patterns and simulation models i) on global soil health impacts of EU activities including resource flows; ii) to up-and downscale between global resource flows and local soil management and soil quality 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Assess the impact of EU and global policies (incl. trade and market) on EU global soil footprint - Include indicators for global footprint assessment in ex-ante impact assessment of agricultural, environmental, fiscal policies etc. - Explore new (holistic) policy instruments/mechanisms to reduce trade-offs and negative impacts on global soil footprint - Identify sectors, agents, and relevant policies (in the EU) that affect soil health inside and outside the EU - Develop an overview of resource-efficient and low-impact practices (regarding soil health) - Consider the diverse and variable range of land uses in production systems in policy objectives, measures, legislation and certification systems - Establish supportive policies for resource-

¹ https://www.footprintnetwork.org/content/images/uploads/Ecological_Footprint_Standards_2009.pdf

	Global Footprint metrics			efficient practices and the re-use of old materials
Output	Agreed set of indicators and standards for the global soil health impacts of EU activities	Overview of data sources and monitoring protocols agreed upon in EU and member states to monitor soil global footprint	Soil footprint assessments, scenarios/simulation models and overview of resource-efficient practices to established awareness of the linkages between consumption in Europe and soil health outside Europe	Overview of policy impact in global soil footprint, mitigation strategies to reduce negative impacts and trade-offs and establishment of policy pathways that ensure a support of sustainable practices and prevention of unsustainable practices
Outcome (Short- and medium-term effects)	Wide implementation of standardised indicators for the global soil health impacts of EU activities in monitoring and reporting systems across economic/soil use sectors	Established monitoring and reporting systems for all land use sectors, including monitoring of the global soil footprint originating from specific regions (inside or outside the EU), land use sectors, practices, products, and policies.	Strengthened understanding of impacts of EU activities on global soil footprint and increased willingness of consumers and industry to modify their strategy and actions towards more sustainable consumption/production	Global soil footprint is adequately considered in relevant policies and political discussions

Limitations:

The consideration of soil health (soil quality) in footprint assessment is a completely new topic that requires moving the state of the art on land footprint assessments and its derivatives (water footprint, carbon footprint) and adding a qualitative component. While the land footprint is based on a 'simple' quantification of the acreage used for producing goods outside Europe and being consumed in Europe, the soil footprint would also need to analyse how the land is used and what it means for soil health / soil degradation at specific locations.

Further development:

Since the topic addresses the international level, international organisations (e.g. FAO, UN Environment) should be involved in the development of methods for the soil footprint assessment and in the formulation of data requirements. The method development would also need to involve expertise on global economics and trade.

4.8 Increase soil literacy in society across Member States (SMO8)

Capacity building for awareness raising, training, education and communication on the importance of soils and measures to achieve soil health for people and their well-being is crucial to establish the link between people and soils. This issue concerns citizens and their participation in soil and land-oriented activities, but also policy makers, land managers and landowners, and companies that manage or work with soils. The following three key knowledge gaps were identified:

Lack of insight into the level of awareness, knowledge of soil services and benefits, and concerns of different stakeholders (SMO8-1) In the first place, key stakeholder groups relevant to achieve soil health need to be identified and their level of awareness, knowledge, practices, values, and concerns key stakeholders related to soil should be assessed. Moreover, there is an urgent need to explore successful means of sharing,

updating knowledge and co-learning as well as actors, which can facilitate such a process. Insights retrieved will help policy makers at different scales as well as civil society actors or farm advisory services to design effective actions toward soil literacy and to integrate this topic into current outreach and communication practices.

Lack of effective soil health education and trainings (SMO8-2) There is a pressing need to assess the current state of soil education in school curricula at all levels and co-develop tailored education programmes for different education levels (universities, vocational schools/practical application, high school) for students as well as effective soil health trainings for targeted stakeholder groups such as land managers, as well as businesses and policy makers. Key processes to consider in this context are means to promote co-creation and multidirectional learning, as well as exploring lifelong learning opportunities and digitalisation to make new soil health knowledge accessible to different stakeholder groups.

Lack of effective and appropriate communication strategies and methods to enhance soil literacy (SMO8-3) There is an urgent need to develop a coming understanding and language to build the basis for soil health communication addressing the wide range of stakeholder groups from citizens, policy makers, land managers and educators to business. As these groups have different needs and practices and work in different contexts, communication strategies and methods need to be adapted and diversified accordingly to be effective. Establishing national soil ambassador networks across all EU Member States and active at the local level could be a powerful tool to enhance the knowledge of soil-related activists. Moreover, there is also a need to provide opportunities to exchange knowledge on soil health and related management and to stimulate interactions between different stakeholders (e.g. via digital hubs, living labs).

Table 8: Impact pathway for SMO8 - Increase soil literacy in society

Long-term impact: Increased awareness and understanding for the value of soil amongst EU citizens, key stakeholder groups, practitioners and policy makers through a common language and tailored information, so that sustainable soil and land management plays a central place in future changes			
Key knowledge gap	SMO 8-1 Lack of insight into the level of awareness, knowledge of soil services and benefits, and concerns of different stakeholders	SMO 8-2 Lack of effective soil health education and trainings	SMO 8-3 Lack of effective and appropriate communication strategies and methods to enhance soil literacy
Sub-knowledge gaps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lack of understanding and assessment on the level of awareness on the significance on soil health for citizens and other stakeholder groups such as soil and land managers, policy makers, business etc. 2. Lack of insights in the knowledge on the soil services (provided in different soil types) for citizens and key stakeholders 3. Lack of insight in current practices, values and concerns of key stakeholders and citizens 4. Lack of knowledge about the wider educational, social & environmental impact of co-created soil health solutions 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lack of effective soil health education optimised for different education levels 2. Lack of tailored trainings offered to specific stakeholder groups 3. Lack of knowledge about the effectiveness of and potential improvements to existing school curricula of the different educational levels 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lack of effective communication methods tailored to stakeholder values, practices and needs and channels for soil (services, health issues, etc.) 2. Lack of clear definitions and ontologies for “soil health” and SMOs (e.g. land degradation, soil sealing, soil footprint) to create a common understanding 3. Lack of policy and communication tools for policy makers to enhance soil literacy

Actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identify the key stakeholders, their role, awareness, and communication channels at different levels - Develop and implement a methodology to gain insights into citizens' and key stakeholders' knowledge about soil services and benefits - Identify current channels, practices, values and concerns of key stakeholder groups and citizens to inform education programmes - Analyse how new knowledge about soil health can be fed into identified channels (using effective means/processes). - Exploring ways to share relevant knowledge (local/national or solution-oriented) with different actors Solution-oriented knowledge 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Co-develop effective education programmes, toolkits, and engagement measures for different education levels together with targeted stakeholders and Members States (and thereby addressing stakeholder needs but also local opportunities and solutions) - Enhance co creation and multidirectional learning, e.g. in communities of practice considering also demonstration of good practices and hands-on education - Explore the opportunities for lifelong learning and digitalisation for putting new soil science/soil health knowledge to be accessible for different actor groups - Assess the current state of soil education in school curricula at all levels and monitor changes - Co-develop soil literacy courses in relevant degrees (agronomy, environmental sciences, environmental engineering etc.) e.g. for universities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop a transparent communication platform and system. Incorporating both communication channels and methodologies (such as storytelling) - Identify and assess good examples and solutions for knowledge transfers - Identify and train Mission Ambassadors to increase awareness at the local level and enhance the knowledge of soil-related activists - Develop a common language - Stimulate interactions between different stakeholders interested e.g. in different soil types/working at different soil scales as part of the living labs - Developing methods of stakeholder involvement addressing co-design, co-implementation and co-assessment (citizen science) of both problems and solutions. - Develop communication tools close cooperation with key stakeholders and citizens to raise awareness on soil health and best management practices to inform citizens, planners, politicians, and other stakeholder on the benefits provided by soils
Output	Database/Reports on i) Key stakeholder groups and their soil-related awareness (baseline) and, ii) current practices, values and concerns of key stakeholder groups and citizens, iii) successful/effective ways and means of knowledge transfer for specific stakeholders, iv) process for identifying priorities for the need for new knowledge	Assessment report of the state of soil related education and training in the EU and a best of resources repository on soil education and soil trainings for different stakeholder groups and scales	Established (digital) hubs and networks targeting different stakeholders and scales (e.g. national level), provide the best communication on soils and create a forum for knowledge exchange; methodologies that allow for co-design, co-implementation and co-assessment to address challenges and derive solutions; a policy framework that enables the enhancement of soil literacy (including policy instruments, such as guidelines, subsidies and institutional frameworks/ infrastructure
Outcome (Short- and medium-term effects)	Better understanding of awareness, and practices, values and concerns of citizens and key stakeholders on the societal role and value of soil in the EU	Wide integration of soil health in educational curricula at all levels to enable behavioural change	Improved awareness of the societal role and value of soils and involvement of public, private and societal stakeholder in soil and land-related issues at all levels (local, regional, national, international) and integration of "Enhancing soil literacy" as an objective and part of relevant national and integrated policies

Limitations:

The SMO8 objective to increase soil literacy in society is a very broad objective. The objective looks at increasing soil literacy about six of the other mission objectives (SMO1 – SM6) and is aimed at all target groups (varying age, education, work background etc.). In the developed factsheet, no strong distinction was made between specific target groups, and instead a more general factsheet was developed suitable to all target groups. Other – in the same line of reasoning – limitations are that the procedure is described without current knowledge of the different educational, cultural and institutional settings of the different countries. Although the factsheets mentions that these should be mapped/assessed – on an EU level – this is a specific point of attention for each EU member state and perhaps even when it comes to subnational regions.

Further development:

A possible future development for these factsheets is to add these distinctions between the different target groups. For instance, for the SMO 8-3 key knowledge gap on developing effective and appropriate communication strategies and methods, a distinction could be made between how to best approach this from an educational point of view, a citizen science point of view, research oriented means or a political point of view. Depending on the aimed target group, slightly different plans of action should be composed. The same goes for the actual design of the soil literacy products. It would be recommended that local/regional/national organisations are involved to make sure there is a fit with the local/regional/national context (education, culture, institutions).

5 OUTLOOK

Soil health is of central importance to society and the Mission ‘A Soil Deal for Europe’ is a new instrument to address the transition towards healthy soils in and outside Europe. To reach this broad objective and the underlying eight Mission Objectives, common understanding of soil health is needed (see Box 3), as well as research and innovation in both natural sciences as well as social and economic spheres.

New research should emphasise interactions between different sectors and actors, as well as involve citizens to foster social innovations and co-design approaches. Living labs and lighthouses can be one essential component to bring together stakeholders and actors from different fields, co-develop solutions and to raise awareness in society about the importance of soil. In fact, there is a need to increase soil literacy among all key actors involved in soil and land management, but also among decision-makers and the general public. This requires tailored communication on the role of soil (e.g. for food and water security, climate regulation, biodiversity and human health) and solutions to ensure that soil services and benefits can be provided. Depending on the target audience, a wide range of tools and formats can be used to facilitate impactful communication. These include using narratives, success stories and storytelling, developing dedicated education programmes for schools, creating field schools and demo farms for land managers, demonstrating how consumption impacts the global (soil) footprint, and identifying and commissioning soil ambassadors at different levels.

Soil health is also very much reliant on economic viability of sustainable soil management. Therefore, economic considerations including solution-oriented push (costs of inaction) and pull factors (benefits from sustainable soil use) based on e.g. ecosystem services should be an important aspect in all research actions. Cost-benefit analyses can help to identify suitable and accepted solutions. However, while estimating the costs of implementing measures is often feasible, monetising the benefits of sustainable soil management is more challenging.

Even successfully addressing all the knowledge gaps identified in the roadmap will not be enough to mainstream sustainable soil management. For this, we need a transformation of the entire land use and management system, which comes with trade-offs that likewise need to be identified and considered. There is a risk

in addressing each mission objective separately with individual measures and thereby missing these necessary systemic changes. The actions identified in the roadmap should be closely integrated. Future projects need to focus more on finding systemic approaches to highlight synergies and minimise or avoid trade-offs while addressing the individual soil mission objectives.

Climate impacts will exacerbate most soil degradation processes. At the same time, healthy soils make an important contribution to climate change mitigation (e.g. soil organic carbon storage) and to climate change adaptation (e.g. water retention, flood control, cooling functions). Implementing action to improve soil health is therefore a fundamental concern in addressing the climate crisis.

Steering Research and Innovation activities and establishing new ways to achieve the soil mission objectives requires a supporting financing and policy framework. This includes a coherent mix of innovation funding as well as a mix of policy instruments such as regulations, pricing mechanisms and new governance approaches. Several EU policies and strategies with associated instruments and funding already have a direct link to sustainable soil and land management and to one or several Mission Objectives. This includes, for example, the European Green Deal and the related EU Farm to Fork strategy, the Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, the Soil Strategy, the New Forest Strategy, the Zero Pollution Action Plan, the proposal for an EU Nature restoration law and the upcoming Soil Health Law, and, most importantly, the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). Within the new framework of the CAP, which is the central element of the incentives for European land managers to implement sustainable soil management, Member States are already required to address the targets of the European Green Deal. In the second pillar of the CAP, sustainable soil management is addressed by the specific objective 5, although the implementation of the measures varies widely across Member States. However, the first pillar is not yet sufficiently aligned with the soil health objectives. Better coordination of existing and future actions is needed to harness the full potential and synergies of all policies for sustainable soil and land management. Fostering a coherent policy framework for soil and land management requires identifying and removing inconsistencies between policies at European and Member State level and building on identified synergies between these policies to streamline actions and fundings streams.

Moreover, it is crucial to ensure a continuous integration of new research findings into the whole policy cycle: objective setting, instrument development, ex-ante assessment, monitoring and ex-post assessment. In this context it is important to identify intermediaries and find ways to transfer knowledge to end-users, including policy makers. The SMS project has taken first steps in this regard (see the factsheet). Follow-up projects should take up and further develop these initial findings.

The active involvement of stakeholders from all relevant sectors in research activities following an inter- and transdisciplinary approach is essential, as they have the internal knowledge and power to make or block decisions (policy) and actions (management) and can ensure the relevance and acceptability of the outcomes. When stakeholders participate effectively in achieving the goals of the soil mission, they become active players in soil and land management.

Box 3:

Within the SMS-project, a first attempt was made for a soil and land management ontology to support the development of a common languages and to facilitate multi-stakeholder processes (Nougues & Brils et al., 2022). The ontology report should be regarded as a living document that matures by interaction with stakeholders. Thus, it is recommended to promote the use of this document in any SMS follow-up project that aims to support the Soil Mission, including use in Living Labs and Lighthouses. Whenever the need arises in these projects, the document may be updated.

Next steps

Once this is completed and the deliverable is accepted, the roadmap and the factsheets will be given a professional layout and then published.

6 LITERATURE

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ANNEX I: DETAILED FACTSHEETS SMO1 - REDUCE LAND DEGRADATION RELATING TO DESERTIFICATION

SMO 1	Reduce land degradation relating to desertification
Key knowledge gap	SMO 1-1 Lack of definitions and knowledge on degradation processes and drivers
Sub-knowledge gaps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lack of definition of when land is degraded for different land uses. 2. Lack of knowledge on how land degradation processes initiate and impact soil and human health from a field to landscape scale. 3. Lack of knowledge of how socioeconomic and climate change factors interact to generate various forms of land degradation.
Relevant land use sector	Sub knowledge gap 1-3: all sectors
Regional scope	All regions are concerned by this lack of knowledge.
Research actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop proper definitions of land degradation for different land uses and sectors • Identify (socio-economic) drivers for land degradation and assess related desertification processes on different scales including urban and industrial areas • Assess and model the short-, mid-, and long-term effects of climate change and other variables on land degradation across Europe.
Output/Results	Clear definitions of 'degraded land' and knowledge about drivers, processes and impacts related to degradation and desertification for different land uses.
Urgency (short-term: until 2027, mid-term: until 2035, long-term until: 2050)	<p>Short term: Finance long-term experiments on land degradation and desertification processes in different socio-economic contexts and climatic regions and identify geophysical as well as socio-economic drivers.</p> <p>Medium term: Set up a group of experts from different sectors to agree on definitions of land degradation for different land uses.</p>
Synergies	Soil degradation and desertification are very closely related to soil organic carbon stocks (SMO2), soil structure (SMO6) and erosion (SMO5), thus these SMOs also benefit from a better understanding of degradation processes and their causes.
End users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Land managers, foresters and advisors: Direct soil users will benefit from this knowledge as they will be provided with information on unsustainable management practices that lead to land degradation. • Researchers will have a better knowledge on degradation processes and drivers to be used in further research and modelling.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU policymakers can use the knowledge to guide agri-environmental policy.
Key stakeholders	To first understand the causes and processes of land degradation, researchers should be involved. They need to work in field conditions with land managers and urban and industrial stakeholders to face real situations.
Intermediaries	Farm advisors and farm associations could serve as intermediaries between researchers and land managers. They simplify research outputs, write guidelines and train direct soil users.
Barriers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial barrier: Research into all ecosystems requires time and money (different soil types, climates, land uses) • Cultural barrier: Insufficient awareness of the problem of soil land degradation. Results of changed management will only be visible in the long term.
Living lab/ light-houses	<p>Living labs are needed to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Co-develop definitions of degraded soils together with practitioners and scientists. • Examine and assess deterioration and desertification processes over the long term and in relation to particular management decisions by using practitioners' sites as continuous, long-term experiments. • Test sustainable forest management strategies in different climates, develop recycling techniques in forest-based industries, breed and test drought-tolerant cereal varieties - in terms of yield in different drought-stress circumstances
Outcome	Improved definitions and understanding of what land degradation is, which processes underlie desertification and how drivers including climate change impact land degradation across Europe.

Milestones	<p>Milestone 1: R&I projects carried out to specify the understanding of degradation and desertification processes (short term) Long-term experiments on land degradation and desertification in in different socio-economic contexts, climate regions and land uses are funded.</p> <p>Milestone 2: Drivers for land degradation identified and related desertification processes on different scales assessed (medium term) Based on the results definitions on degradation for different land uses are proposed and drivers for land degradation identified. A final agreement is made on definitions.</p> <p>Milestone 3: Assessment of future trends (medium term) Models to assess the impact of future changes including climate change are available.</p>
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SMO 1	Reduce land degradation relating to desertification
Key knowledge gap	SMO 1-2 Lack of indicators, thresholds, and monitoring system to quantify soil degradation in Europe
Sub-knowledge gaps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lack of harmonised, easy to measure, cost effective indicators (also for urban and industrial areas) that take into account a multitude of desertification processes and thresholds to ecosystem collapse, land remediation and international reporting requirements. 2. Lack of knowledge where land degradation and desertification take place in Europe (including urban and industrial areas) and how they will change due to climate change and the loss of biodiversity.
Relevant land use sector	Sub knowledge gap 1-2: all relevant land use sector.
Regional scope	All regions are concerned by this lack of knowledge.
Research actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop a set of easy measurable, cost-effective indicators including early-warning signals, thresholds, and approaches for data management for different types of soil degradation and sectors. • Taking stock of where desertification processes occur in the EU and how the areas at risk will change in the future due to climate change and the loss of biodiversity.
Output/Results	A comprehensive set of indicators and thresholds to measure and monitor desertification processes is ready to use across all categories of land use and all regions of Europe.

<p>Urgency (short-term: until 2027, mid-term: until 2035, long-term until: 2050)</p>	<p>Short term: Take stock of possible indicators for all types of degradation and desertification and land uses and identify and test a first set of indicators (e.g. at EU scale on LUCAS network and country level).</p> <p>Medium term: Agree on and validate the set of indicators and threshold values with the involvement of all relevant actors.</p> <p>Medium term to long term: Collect data in all EU Member States and assess the status and trends of soil degradation and desertification in Europe</p>
<p>Synergies</p>	<p>The development of easily measurable indicators and their implementation into monitoring schemes will facilitate the early detection of trends and thus prevent soil degradation through erosion or soil sealing (SMO3 and SMO5) and can be part of the EU global footprint (SMO7) and improve soil literacy (SMO8).</p>
<p>End users</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policymakers could use developed indicator sets to report on the effects of soil policies at the national/local scale and to set targets. • Land managers could use data to follow transitions and changes in management. • Citizens will be better informed of the status of soils.
<p>Key stakeholders</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers provide the scientific basis for suitable indicators. • Land managers and land user from all sectors should be involved in assessing whether the measurements are easy to manage, and the early-warning indicators are understandable.
<p>Intermediaries</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU expert groups can push for the integration and implementation of indicators at EU and national scale. • Farm advisors can help land managers recognise early-warning signals and take appropriate action.
<p>Barriers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial barrier: Analysis costs are very high. • Political barrier: No political willingness to adopt the set of indicators to monitor soil status at EU/national level.
<p>Living lab/ light-houses</p>	<p>Living Labs can help to co-create a set of indicators and agree on thresholds.</p>
<p>Outcome</p>	<p>Increased measurability of land degradation and desertification in all land uses and implementation of a harmonised EU-wide monitoring system.</p>

Milestones	<p>Milestone 1: Selection of a minimum set of indicators and threshold values for degradation and desertification (short term) Soil indicators are assessed and tested across EU and on national/EU monitoring sites in e.g. Living Labs. A minimum set of indicators is proposed with threshold values.</p> <p>Milestone 2: Validation of a set of indicators and threshold values (medium term) Relevant actors have validated and agreed on a set of soil/region/sector specific indicators and threshold values. Guidelines are available to support the development, training, and use of the identified set of indicators.</p> <p>Milestone 3: Implementation of a broad monitoring scheme (medium/long term) A synthesis is made and communicated to policymaker so that they can promote relevant indicators and thresholds in monitoring policies (e.g. through CAP payments)</p>
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SMO 1	Reduce land degradation relating to desertification
Key knowledge gap	SMO 1-3 Lack of suitable and cost-effective prevention and restoration options for different pedo-climatic zones and land use types.
Sub-knowledge gaps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 6. Lack of cost-impact assessments of land and soil degradation and agronomic effects of different conservation measures (especially in arid regions). 7. Lack of prevention options and knowledge of their impact, trade-offs and durability in different pedo-climatic zones and land use types. 8. Lack of restoration options addressing a wide range of soil functions and land uses and knowledge of their impact on soil health and durability in different pedo-climatic zones. 9. Lack of harmonised policies to replace harmful subsidies to prevent desertification.
Relevant land use sector	Sub knowledge gap 1-4: all relevant land use sector.
Regional scope	Prevention and restoration options are needed for different pedo-climatic zones and land use types with a focus on arid regions.
Research actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify suitable prevention and restoration options for land degradation and assess trade-offs for different land use types and pedo-climatic conditions in the EU. • Establish and evaluate long-term records of prevention and restoration measures (for different land use systems) with a focus on cost effectiveness.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Include prevention and restoration measures for desertification in agricultural education and advisory services. • Mainstream preventing and restoring land degradation in all policies as a priority action including different incentive schemes. • Include prevention and restoration measures for desertification in National Adaptation Plans.
Output/Results	Comprehensive climate, soil and land use specific overview of desertification prevention and restoration options including cost-benefits, synergies, and trade-offs to guide land managers.
Urgency (short-term: until 2027, mid-term: until 2035, long-term until: 2050)	<p>Short term: Finance long-term research on prevention and restoration options including socio-economic factors and cost-benefit analysis for land degradation for different land use types, pedo-climatic and socio-economic conditions in the EU.</p> <p>Medium term: Identify suitable prevention and restoration options for land degradation and assess trade-offs and barriers to implementation for different land use types and pedo-climatic conditions in the EU. Assess the EU policy framework to identify trade-offs of incentive schemes.</p> <p>Medium/long term: Promote effective prevention and restoration measures in agricultural education, advisory services and include measures in national adaptation plans. Harmonise funding instruments at EU level and ensure that land degradation is considered and prioritised.</p>
Synergies	Supporting the transition to more sustainable land management by better addressing soil degradation and restoration in the EU policies and advisory services as well as overcoming technological, social and financial barriers will also contribute to conserving soil organic carbon stocks (SMO2), improving soil structure (SMO6) and preventing erosion (SMO5).
End users	The main end-users will be land managers and land users from all sectors (who implement measures) and policymakers. To understand how the changes in management practices will impact the costs of production and what kinds of incentives should be developed to help and support transition. Assessing trade-offs will also help to highlight the reluctance to changes from the land users/managers and possible ways to motivate them.
Key stakeholders	Researchers - including socio-economic scientists - should design and conduct research studies with land users/managers on Living Labs. Industry and agrobusiness should also be involved in developing new cost-effective technologies.

Intermediaries	Farm advisory and farm associations will pass the knowledge about suitable management options on to land managers. EU expert groups will translate the results to policymakers and businesses.
Barriers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cultural barriers: Reluctance to change, significant divergences from traditional solutions. For example, forestry works on a large time scale, regeneration of the tree population (renewal) takes a long time, the results will only be visible in the long term. • Capacity building: New technologies needed, lack of knowledge transfer and training, limited exchange among practitioners who already have experience with good practice. Lack of independent advisory services, which costs money. • Financial barriers: No financial resources to invest in new technologies.
Living lab/ light-houses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Foster the co-development of location-specific, socio-economically viable solutions. • Promote regional and EU-wide exchange with and between practitioners who already follow good practices.
Outcome	Increased uptake of effective land degradation prevention and restoration measures.
Milestones	<p>Milestone 1: R&I projects involving socio-economic aspects in different regions and land uses are implemented (short term) Socio-economic research studies and research on new technologies are developed to assess the benefits of land degradation and restoration measures for different land use types and pedo-climatic conditions.</p> <p>Milestone 2: Expand implementation and testing (medium term) The outcomes of the studies are synthesised and cost-effective land degradation prevention and restoration measures identified. Recommendations are derived and ways to communicate them are developed.</p> <p>Milestone 3: Build foundations in policy to implement effective prevention and restoration measures (medium/long term) Incentives, market instruments and further support (including communication, training, technical and economical) are developed to promote cost-effective prevention and restoration options for degraded soils.</p>

ANNEX II: DETAILED FACTSHEETS SMO 2 - CONSERVE AND INCREASE SOIL ORGANIC CARBON STOCKS

SMO 2	Conserve and increase soil organic carbon stocks
Key knowledge gap	SMO 2-1 Lack of knowledge of the effects of different soil properties and management practices on soil organic carbon (SOC) and its threshold levels, stability, and ecosystem services
Sub-knowledge gaps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lack of information on and demonstrating of effects and potential of various management practices on SOC storage, conservation and losses for different soil types and depths. 2. Lack of knowledge about the threshold levels and stability of soil carbon under different management, climatic conditions, soil properties (e.g., soil type, farming system, tillage system, nutrient levels, soil microbiome) the role of biodiversity and climate change. 3. Lack of knowledge about the short- and long-term effects and co-benefits of SOC on ecosystems services. 4. Lack of knowledge about the effects of soil nutrient status and balance (in particular for nitrogen and phosphorus) for SOC storage and conservation.
Relevant land use sector	<p>Sub-knowledge gaps 1,2 and 4 : agriculture, forestry</p> <p>Sub-knowledge gap 3: all sectors</p>
Regional scope	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information is needed on regional land management practices, and on regional soil climate types, as each of these could affect SOC differently. • Compare regional land management practices with studies of more sustainable land management practices and the suitability of these practices in different soil and climate types. • Consider past land use to derive suitable management practices.
Research actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monitor changes in SOC in response to different management practices and identify factors which help to stabilise SOC including the role of biodiversity in the long term for different soil types at different soil depths. • Explore short and long-term benefits of increases in SOC on ecosystem services. • Identify the ability of different soils under different climate conditions to sequester and store SOC. • Explore the effects of different nutrient management systems in combination for a range of agricultural systems on SOC.
Output/Results	Overview of the potential of soils to store carbon under specific conditions and measures to increase and preserve SOC in relation to soil types and climate as well as their corresponding ecosystem responses in the short and long-term.

<p>Urgency (short-term: until 2027, mid-term: until 2035, long-term until: 2050)</p>	<p>Short term: Develop/maintain long-term experiments and LL where SOC can be measured depending on climate, soil type, biodiversity, land uses and management practices to learn more/quantify/model the links between soil/land management and SOC and all side effects.</p> <p>Medium term: Based on the knowledge, propose benchmark values and best management practices adapted to soil type, climate, land use. Develop guidelines to train actors. Accumulate a list of land management practices to conserve SOC relative to each soil, farming system and climate type, and land use history. Ideally regional SOC baseline testing would be required on each farm.</p> <p>Long term: Monitor/report the effects of management changes.</p>
<p>Synergies</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increasing/maintaining carbon stocks will contribute to the reduction of soil degradation (such as erosion, desertification, etc.), the increase of soil structure and to the general improvement of the soil ecosystem (SMO1, SMO4, SMO5, SMO6). • Improving soil carbon stocks will contribute to soil restoration (SMO4, SMO7). • Increased SOC is a result of increased soil organic matter, which acts as a food source for soil fauna, leading to improvement of the habitat (SMO6).
<p>End users</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Land managers will be provided a range of science-backed measures to improve SOC sequestration suitable to their regional soil and climate type and historical land use. • Advisors will have a compilation of land management practices to advise landowners on the best practices suitable to regional situation (as above). • Researchers will have a large dataset produced in R&I to be used in further research • Policymakers can utilise information generated in soil carbon stock changes to guide agri-environmental policy (e.g., CAP strategic plan & carbon farming policy) • Industry/other stakeholders should utilise information generated in carbon farming business models
<p>Key stakeholders</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers should be involved in the research and development of Living Labs and the communication of results

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Land managers and advisors, landowners, soil and farmer organisation - should be involved in consultations with researchers to agree on workable management practices according to what the research suggests and also involved in research in LL.
Intermediaries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers will pass on scientific data and information to all other end-users. • Land management advisors will pass on information and guidelines to landowners. • Research initiatives will pass on scientific information to other end-users.
Barriers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial barriers: Costs of research (regional and pedo-climatic research for a wide range of land management scenarios, SOC baseline analysis on a regional and local level). Costs related to implementing measures or through lower income due to non-harvestable crops for SOC storage. • Political barriers: Time - this objective requires long-term research which may be a barrier to achieving some of the short-term goals. • Capacity building: Lack of sufficient and affordable carbon quantifying methods to carry out monitoring on a large scale. Lack of coherent systems across Europe for guiding land managers on suitable practices.
Living lab/ light-houses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research farms with long-term experiments to investigate management practices on SOC • Use existing forest sites that employ different management practices to investigate their effects on SOC • Use agroforestry farm sites to investigate SOC changes and their potential for different farming practices (i.e. cattle, tillage) • Monitor SOC on regional farms with varying management practices (history of land use and management should be available and taken into account)
Outcome	Increased understanding of soil organic carbon dynamics under management and effects on ecosystem services in the short and long term
Milestones	Milestone 1: Identification of proper management options (medium term) A list of regional and pedo-climatic specific land management practices are compiled and guidelines for increasing SOC developed. The identified management options are based on research and demonstration in Living Labs and Lighthouses.

	<p>Milestone 2: Past and current status of SOC in the EU (medium term) An interactive map of historical land use and current status of SOC stocks in the EU is developed. The map is linked to the pedo-climatic specific land management guidelines for a streamlined view of soil status and potential actions to increase/preserve SOC.</p> <p>Milestone 3: Forecasting tools for SOC in EU (medium term) Interactive map of SOC threshold and potential in EU soils are available, linked with prospective economic and scientific models to show potential for SOC increase in our soils as a result of good management practices.</p>
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SMO 2	Conserve and increase soil organic carbon stocks
Key knowledge gap	SMO 2-2 Lack of short and long-term, in-field, and remote SOC test methods and knowledge of SOC storage potential for EU soils
Sub-knowledge gaps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lack of harmonised and user-friendly in-field test methods for SOC 2. Lack of a systematic and long-term SOC monitoring (remote and in-field) 3. Lack of information on SOC stocks and storage potential for EU soils
Relevant land use sector	All sub-knowledge gaps: agriculture, forestry, natural, urban
Regional scope	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regional information on SOC storage potential is needed for EU soils as different management practices, crop cover, soil and climate types can affect storage potentials. • Advancements in remote sensing to deliver data that can be processed to deliver spatial information on SOC and changes in SOC. • Regional information can be extracted from soil spectral libraries to estimate SOC and reduce the costs of measuring SOC in soil samples.
Research actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop harmonised methods to quantify SOC stocks and soil organic matter quality and indicators to assess SOC dynamics (remote and in-field) to use in Monitoring, Verification and Reporting (MRV) or incentive systems • Identify baseline for current SOC stocks and quantify potential storage for EU soils for different location and climate conditions
Output/Results	Robust Monitoring, Reporting and Verification (MRV) systems (in-field and remote) and overview of the potential and current carbon stock of European soils

<p>Urgency (short-term: until 2027, mid-term: until 2035, long-term until: 2050)</p>	<p>Short term:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop and test new methods and approaches (e.g. remote sensing) to measure and monitor SOC • Develop maps for C stocks/storage potential (using information in soil spectral libraries, remote sensing/quantification as well as data from existing extensive monitoring networks based on soil samples) • Harmonise SOC testing methods - to develop an EU wide database of SOC baselines and potentials, each region must be using the same methods <p>Medium term: Develop and test MRV procedures for use in all regions.</p> <p>Long term: Implement the MRV procedures in EU to report the same way everywhere.</p>
<p>Synergies</p>	<p>SOC stocks will be considered in coming indicators for soil footprint and thus having harmonised methods to measure and estimate SOC will benefit SMO7.</p>
<p>End users</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers can use measurement tools, SOC maps and MRV procedures in future research. • Land management advisors can use SOC stock information and measurement tools to provide specific and science-backed advice to landowners. • Landowners can utilise SOC maps to make informed decisions about land management options and can use measurement tools for in-field testing to plan for sustaining soil quality and land value. • Land developers to receive information on SOC stocks/storage potential of sites could be used in planning, i.e. degraded sites should be used for new developments. • Policymakers can use data collected in MRV for carbon accounting/farming, novel measurement tools that may benefit stocktaking in carbon farming.
<p>Key stakeholders</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers should be involved in development of measurement tools, SOC maps and SOC stock taking on a regional and EU level. • Policymakers can provide uncertainty requirements of measurement and mapping methods, which can inform templates for measurements and reports that are easily comparable/compatible. • Industry and agrobusiness may benefit from the developments, in particular new methods for labs, companies offering new services for MRV.

Intermediaries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers and research initiatives will pass on information on SOC stocks and potentials, and development of measurement systems to other stakeholders and end-users as farm advisory services, farm associations, networks, EU expert groups, business companies and laboratories. • Land management advisors will use data collected and measurement tools to pass on information to landowners - can use this information to suggest best management practices. • Commercial labs, MRV companies, carbon credits sold by companies should pass on information and data collected to stakeholders and end-users.
Barriers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Institutional barriers: Lack of developments and advancements of monitoring technology and lack of standardised and large-scale SOC measurement tools may be a barrier to achieving results. When working with commercial laboratories and MRV companies, obstacles may arise due to data ownership and data protection regulation. • Financial barriers: The numerous factors affecting SOC storage potential (soil type, location, climate, management practices, historical land use etc.) - makes quantifying SOC storage potential very difficult, costly and time-consuming on a large scale.
Living lab/ light-houses	Monitoring methods can be tested on research farms, forestry, natural and urban sites. MRV systems can be implemented on research sites but should also be tested on farm and landscape scale.
Outcome	EU-wide implementation of a harmonised monitoring system and identification of most critical hot spots of SOC storage and losses
Milestones	<p>Milestone 1: Mapping storage potential and high SOC land at global/national/regional levels (short to medium term) Soil types and pedoclimatic zones are used to map SOC storage potential at global, national and regional/local level. The potential is presented in an interactive map to make the results available to all stakeholders and should be used in advisory and planning measures for land management strategies. This allows each landowner to tailor management practices to the soil health in their region. Specific focus should be on mapping high SOC land, in particular peatlands and organic soils, which are critical for pursuing protective measures. These lands have more carbon than most other soils (together).</p>

	<p>Milestone 2: Mapping of regional SOC storage potentials (medium term) Identify regional/local soil types and pedoclimatic zones for use in mapping SOC storage potential.</p> <p>Milestone 3: Mapping of critical hotspots of SOC losses and potential (short term) Soil carbon hot spots to be protected, areas losing SOC and areas which need to be restored because of their great potential are identified. These areas are the most urgent to implement SOC preservation measures and should be the target areas for SOC research.</p> <p>Milestone 4: Mapping of regional fire risks (short term) Areas where fire risk exists under current and projected climatic conditions were identified to show the extent of projected fire risk areas under climate change. This information is presented in a map with current fire risk zones to be targeted for immediate protection measures and predicted fire risk zones to be targeted for preventative measures.</p> <p>Milestone 5: Development of universal MRV system (mid term) Effective and accurate MRV system to support carbon credits/farming are in development. This MRV system is applicable to and adopted by all EU countries to enable a streamlined system for carbon farming.</p>
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SMO 2	Conserve and increase soil organic carbon stocks
Key knowledge gap	SMO 2 (3) Lack of short and long-term business models for economic effects of loss/storage of SOC and pedo-climatic specific guidelines for increasing SOC.
Sub-knowledge gaps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lack of short and long-term economic effects of increased SOC and losses at farm-level and business models to incentivise carbon storage and conservation. 2. Lack of information on trade-offs of funding schemes including carbon farming payment schemes as well as funding in less effective measures. 3. Lack of regional and pedo-climatic specific guidelines including measures to maintain (e.g., prevent from degradation) and increase SOC.
Relevant land use sector	All sub-knowledge gaps: agriculture, forestry, natural, urban, industry

Regionalscope	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Guidelines for regional land management practices to promote storage and conservation of SOC - specific to regional soil types and climate effects. • Business models for increased/decreased SOC for each land use sector in each region/country. • Carbon farming schemes may have to be adapted for regional needs and capacities (economic ability, SOC potential, number of stakeholders, etc.).
Research actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify economic effects of increased SOC sequestration and losses and develop business models for different sectors (e.g., agriculture, forestry, urban sector) to provide the financial basis for trading carbon, i.e. how the open market will operate for carbon trading (carbon farming). • Analyse the effectiveness and trade-offs of funding schemes. • Develop regional guidelines to promote SOC storage under different management and pedo-climatic conditions.
Output/Results	Decision support tools and tailored guidelines including socio-economic effects for different sectors and farming systems under various pedo-climatic conditions.
Urgency (short-term: until 2027, mid-term: until 2035, long-term until: 2050)	<p>Short term: Guidelines/ Monitoring, Verification and Reporting (MRV) protocols to be tested in LL or in real field conditions. Short term business models for economic effects of SOC loss/storage to be developed.</p> <p>Medium term: Harmonised/shared guidelines/MRV protocols to be generalised (e.g., through EU policies as CAP). Business models to be updated, if necessary, based on changes in economic effect due to guideline implementation. It is also key to align monitoring at the farm scale with national inventories.</p> <p>Long term: Long-term business models to be developed/finalised based on resulting changes in land management practices.</p>
Synergies	SOC stocks will be considered in coming indicators for soil footprint and thus generalising measurement of SOC within carbon markets will also benefit SMO7.
End users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policymakers can use business models to aid in developing policy • Land use advisors use regional guidelines and business models to provide effective advice to landowners • Landowners can use regional guidelines to promote SOC storage, in turn benefiting carbon farming schemes if adopted

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Urban developers may use business models in selecting of sites for urban development (reusing brownfields/building on soil that is less favourable for SOC storage may be more economically beneficial - business models needed)
Key stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers should be involved in development of pedo-climatic specific guidelines for conservation of SOC and working with economists on business models. • Economists should be involved in development of business models for economic effects of SOC loss/storage and carbon farming schemes • Agribusiness should contribute to development of business models for economic effects of SOC loss/storage and carbon farming schemes • Policymakers should develop methods that can capture farm and landscape measures in natural inventories and avoid double counting
Intermediaries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers/Research initiatives will pass on science-backed land management practices to promote SOC for pedo-climatic specific regions to expert groups and networks. Will also pass on the recommended practices to economists for development of business models • Farm advisors in collaboration with expert groups and networks will identify and select relevant MRV protocols to be applied and implemented by business and policymakers. • Policymakers will assist in development of business models by recommending policy and developing systems for transparency and to avoid double counting.
Barriers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Capacity building: No universal way of measuring and reporting (MRV) system. A streamlined and universally used MRV system is needed to accurately develop business models that are relevant across all EU countries. • Financial and political barriers: Carbon storage in soil is not permanent (may be reversible) – difficult to develop long-term business models for SOC storage. Furthermore, without efficient and cost-effective methods to verify carbon storage in soil, verification is yet too expensive to recommend and implement.
Living lab/ light-houses	Living labs can be used at the beginning to test regional land management practices and then share/agree on minimal rules
Outcome	Increased awareness and widespread uptake of measures to store and conserve SOC across different sectors

Milestones	<p>Milestone 1: Economic assessment of existing and forthcoming initiatives (short term) An economic assessment including trade-offs of current and potential carbon initiatives on land and development prices has been carried out.</p> <p>Milestone 2: Economic assessment of land management systems (short term) Comparative economic analyses of regional land management system scenarios on SOC for all land management types in Europe has been carried out. This will be used to determine the best management options for both stakeholders and soil health.</p> <p>Milestone 3: List of management practices to be implemented and included in carbon markets (short term) List of regional land management practices for each sector are developed in Living labs, guidelines developed and disseminated to stakeholders.</p>
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SMO 2	Conserve and increase soil organic carbon stocks
Key knowledge gap	SMO 2-4 Lack of effective policies, incentives, and emissions trading and reporting platforms for SOC conservation
Sub-knowledge gaps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lack of effective and fair private-public payment schemes (together with financial institutions) and functional incentives for preserving and enhancing soil carbon sequestration (see also SMO2-3) including the promotion of non-peat alternatives for horticultural purposes. 2. Lack of knowledge of the effectiveness of policy instruments for increasing soil carbon stocks. 3. Lack of platforms for national SOC stocks reporting and emissions trading.
Relevant land use sector	All sub-knowledge gaps: agriculture, forestry, natural, urban, industry
Regional scope	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information (economic and social) is needed on effectiveness of current policies implemented in each region/country. • Platforms for national SOC stocks reporting and emissions trading connected to a global/EU platform. • Incentives for carbon storage may have to be adapted for different regions and industries.

Research actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify priority areas where public support for SOC improvement is most needed and develop subsidy-frameworks for carbon sequestration. • Evaluate the effectiveness of existing and future policy instruments (including models for projected policy outputs), consider economic impact. • Develop emission factors for different soil types, pedoclimatic conditions and management for national SOC stocks reporting and emissions trading.
Output/Results	Carbon payment schemes (incl. carbon farming) that promote conservation and enhancement of SOC including wider economic impacts based on scientific research.
Urgency (short-term: until 2027, mid-term: until 2035, long-term until: 2050)	<p>Short term: Defined policy on emissions trading for SOC (e.g., remove potential for double counting between CAP and carbon farming).</p> <p>Medium term: Standardised and secure reporting platform for landowners to record SOC conservation/sequestration activities which underpin a carbon certification programme and can be linked with Monitoring, Verification and Reporting (MRV) systems. (to confirm that appropriate soil management (that will result in carbon sequestration or maintenance) is taking place; and to protect the parties involved (i.e. the land owner and entity paying for the carbon credits).</p> <p>Long term: Agreed on and harmonised models/indicators for soil carbon MRV (increased risk for landowners to join emissions trading scheme - standardised indicators needed to reassure land managers).</p>
Synergies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SOC stocks will certainly be considered in coming indicators for soil footprint and thus generalising measurement of SOC within carbon markets will also benefit SMO7. • The extension of carbon markets will also draw attention to soils improving soil literacy by companies, policy officers, governments and finally citizens (SMO8).
End users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Land manager and landowner can receive additional income (through incentives and payment schemes) for preserving SOC, improve soil quality and increase SOC. • Industry will engage in emissions trading, allowing them to offset carbon emissions. • Business/investors: e.g., airlines, banks involved in emissions trading to offset carbon emissions.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agrobusiness/Agriculture need to offset their other emissions (N₂O, CH₄).
Key stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU, national and regional policymakers should be involved in creating policies and effective incentives to promote SOC conservation. • Researchers can provide scientific information to inform policy and incentive development. • Industry & agribusiness should be involved in designing business platform for MRV and carbon accounting.
Intermediaries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers/research initiatives to pass scientific information/data to policymakers/experts to aid in policy development. • Developers & economists will pass on developed tools for MRV and carbon accounting and trading to end-users.
Barriers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Capacity building: Lack of robust scientific results to affect policy change. This will most likely be a short-term effect, due to the lack of sufficient short-term data and results from long-term experiments. (Significant changes in SOC are commonly only seen during a study period of 10+ years. As a result, there may not be sufficient data/results in the short term to trigger policy change). Lack of knowledge on trade-offs with other emissions (N₂O, CH₄) from the measures implemented to increase SOC. • Financial barriers: Cost of setting up effective and efficient MRV systems; to recoup the investment, they would have to be set up on a large scale.
Living lab/ light-houses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social science/acceptability of business model could be evaluated. • Long-term studies can be used to evaluate the sensitivity and efficiency of MRV platforms.
Outcome	EU-wide implemented effective policy measures including payment schemes to maintain and foster SOC sequestration and increased SOC accounting in national and European GHG inventories
Milestones	<p>Milestone 1: Reporting platforms (short term) Platforms to gather data on activities for national SOC stocks reporting and emissions trading are in development.</p> <p>Milestone 2: Business model on which the platform is based (short term). The business model underpins the running of the trading scheme and the financial relationship that both parties agree to. Concrete subsidies/minimum monetary incentives for adoption of management practices to increase carbon sequestration</p>

	<p>are developed. Socio-economic appraisal of the emissions trading/carbon accounting platform has been carried out. An assessment of the acceptance by companies (user-friendliness, security of investment etc.) has been conducted. Development of a transparent system that avoids double counting and includes implementation in national inventories.</p> <p>Milestone 3: Testing MRV systems (medium term) Suitable MRV system/model are developed and tested.</p>
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ANNEX III: DETAILED FACTSHEETS SMO 3 – NO NET SEALING AND INCREASE THE REUSE OF URBAN SOIL

SMO 3	No net sealing and increase the reuse of urban soil
Key knowledge gap	SMO 3-1 Lack of indicators to monitor soil sealing and land take processes and their impact
Sub-knowledge gaps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lack of indicators and holistic approaches to assess the impact of land take and soil sealing and their dynamics and impacts on soil functions 2. Lack of monitoring of land take and soil sealing processes at different scales and the loss of soil functions
Relevant land use sector	All sub-knowledge gaps: agriculture, forestry, urban, industry, infrastructure
Regional scope	At the regional level monitoring accuracy needs to be about 10m x 10m to spot individual buildings and land parcels
Research actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop and test indicators for mapping and monitoring land take and soil sealing dynamics and their effects on soil functions and services, problems and opportunities • Develop and promote databases for land consumption and indicators for environmental effects of urban development - also at different scales (informing policy processes such as Strategic Environment Assessment)
Output/Results	Overview/tool of validated standard procedures (including indicators) for quantification and evaluation of the impacts of land take and soil sealing.

<p>Urgency (short-term: until 2027, mid-term: until 2035, long-term until: 2050)</p>	<p>Short term: All subsequent steps to lessen soil sealing and land taking are initiated by indicators for monitoring soil sealing and land take. Create a baseline for monitoring requirements and carry out a preliminary round of monitoring.</p>
<p>Synergies</p>	<p>Land take and soil sealing are forms of land degradation. By monitoring them, the extent of land degradation can be measured and the effectiveness of implemented measures observed (SMO1). Sealed soils cannot capture soil organic carbon (SOC). By monitoring soil sealing on a regular basis, a key threat to SOC conservation can be observed (SMO2).</p>
<p>End users</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers can obtain monitoring data to analyse the status and trends of soil sealing and land take to derive further measures towards a positive trend • Policy makers and managing authorities at different levels can assess the progress towards established targets and the overall impacts of soils sealing/land take
<p>Key stakeholders</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers develop and improve indicators on land take and soil sealing and test those in practice • Policymakers and managing authorities at different levels validate whether the proposed tool of validated standard procedures and indicators i) is suitable and aligned with respective policies and ii) can be implemented in practice
<p>Intermediaries</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU managing authorities/research authorities will inform Member States about standard procedures and indicators and provide training/guidance for its applications • National governments will transfer new knowledge to regions • City networks will inform their members about effective monitoring approaches
<p>Barriers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial barriers: Monitoring land take and soil sealing requires additional human resources, leading to extra costs. Costs can be reduced by limiting the monitoring to a 3-year cycle and by adopting high resolution data from the Copernicus Land programme (free data sets). • Capacity building: Monitoring land take and soil sealing requires training at the regional level. Lacking guidance on data sources and their implementation.

Living lab/ light-houses	Urban livings labs and lighthouses can use soil monitoring data as a tool in combination with implementing measures to reduce soil sealing.
Outcome	Wide adoption of standard procedures with the result that soil sealing is reduced and the loss of soil functions can be quantified and compensated for.
Milestones	<p>Milestone 1: Regional land take / soil sealing targets (short term) i) All European regions (ideally at level NUTS3) have already defined intermediate targets for 2030 with a view to the EU target "achieving no net land take by 2050" ii) a baseline for land take and soil sealing has been defined, and iii) a regular monitoring of land take and soil sealing (at least every three years) has started.</p> <p>Milestone 2: First review of land take and soil sealing at regional level (medium term) First regional review after two rounds of monitoring conducted, trends definition is available and measures to be implemented are defined.</p> <p>Milestone 3: Second review of land take and soil sealing at regional level (long term) Second regional review after four rounds of monitoring conducted, trend definition is available and future measures to be implemented are defined.</p>

SMO 3	No net sealing and increase the reuse of urban soil
Key knowledge gap	SMO3-2 Lack guidance for avoiding soil sealing and reusing land and soil, and conserving soil functions
Sub-knowledge gaps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lack of guidance for reusing land and conserving soil functions including (cost-)effective tools to analyse soil quality and track soil transportation ("soil passport") 2. Lack of concepts for adequate replacement options and rehabilitation measures for soil sealing to increase water infiltration and generate multiple benefits 3. Insufficient knowledge of using organic waste for soil rehabilitation and creating synergies with circular economy 4. Lack of methods to identify areas for de-sealing measures
Relevant land use sector	All sub-knowledge gaps: industry and urban
Regional scope	Regions with a high land take (outskirts of urban centres) are particularly in need of the above-mentioned tools to minimise their soil sealing trend.

Research actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify, assess, and demonstrate measures to reduce/ prevent soil sealing and rehabilitate (industrial/ brownfield) soils, safe and cost-effective soil re-use, and increase water infiltration (NBS, regenerative agriculture, permeable surfaces etc.) • Explore methods and develop effective tools to analyse soil quality and track soil transportation and create new soils (constructed techno soils) from excavated soils and organic wastes • Explore and assess the potential, benefits, and trade-offs to combine circular economy approaches with reusing soils
Output/Results	Guidance for prevention and rehabilitation measures (incl. benefits, trade-offs, design, applicability, requirements, costs)
Urgency (short-term: until 2027, mid-term: until 2035, long-term until: 2050)	<p>Short term: Develop guidance and knowledge to minimise soil sealing and land take and conserve soil functions at construction sites as far as possible. Explore and define solutions to store excavated soils in an appropriate way at construction sites (if not polluted, to be fit for re-use, either at the site or somewhere else).</p> <p>Medium term: Develop compensation schemes for unavoidable soil sealing. Define actions to reuse excavated soils (if appropriate i.e. not polluted and regional match) when de-sealing from construction sites, thus fostering circular economy.</p>
Synergies	Soil rehabilitation measures and reuse of soil contributes to reduced land degradation (SMO1), enhanced restoration of soils (SMO4), restore and improve soil structure (SMO6), and reduce the footprint on soil by fostering ways of circular economy (SMO7).
End users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The building sector to minimise soil sealing and conserve soil functions at construction sites. • Regional spatial planning authorities to identify and map potential de-sealing areas, which are also suitable for compensation
Key stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers need to develop and test measures, tools, methods and guidance in soil science and regional planning living labs and lighthouses • Regional and national policymakers should test, adjust and implement guidance for control and evaluation • Building sector should test and implement the guidance

Intermediaries	<p>EU managing authorities/research authorities will inform Member States about tools and guidance</p> <p>National governments will transfer new knowledge to regions</p>
Barriers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Capacity building: Training is required and regular exchange among those who are potential implementers • Political barriers: Guidance documents have the tendency to be non-binding and hence too soft. Binding soil sealing targets are necessary to make sure that guidance documents are taken seriously and actually implemented. • Financial barriers: The building sector will complain about extra costs. In the past, the destruction of soils (and hence soil services) was cost free. If these services had a monetary value, the extra costs would be marginal.
Living lab/ light-houses	Urban living labs and lighthouses for development and test implementation of guidance documents
Outcome	Increased understanding and uptake of options to prevent soil sealing/rehabilitate soils at among decision makers and planners.
Milestones	<p>Milestone 1: Guidance and training available (short term)</p> <p>Guidance documents and tools for avoiding soils sealing and reusing soil are available in all EU Member States and ready for implementation. Training workshops for implementation (in particular for the building sector) are available and conducted</p> <p>Milestone 2: Political commitment made (short term)</p> <p>Political commitment in all EU Member States to minimise soil sealing with compulsory implementation of guidance document is made.</p> <p>Milestone 3: Political commitment for compensation of soil sealing and destroyed soil functions (long term)</p> <p>It is compulsory to compensate unavoidable sealing through improving soil functions, which can be achieved by de-sealing or improving soil composition elsewhere.</p>

SMO 3	No net sealing and increase the reuse of urban soil
Key knowledge gap	SMO 3-3 Lacking awareness of the benefits and values of unsealed soils and urban green and blue infrastructure and nature-based solutions

Sub-knowledge gaps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lack of knowledge about the wider educational, social & environmental impact of unsealed soil and co-created urban green and blue infrastructure (GBI) and nature-based solutions (NBS). 2. Lack of knowledge about the barriers and potential stimulation of a nature-based economy that creates green jobs, avoids soil sealing and applies regenerative practices.
Relevant land use sector	All sub-knowledge gaps: urban and industry
Regional scope	Priority should be given to regions with high land take (outskirts of urban centres) because awareness of soil functions needs to be raised there in particular.
Research actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop and test tailored education material to increase awareness about i) benefits of functional/unsealed soils, GBI and NBS, ii) preventing measures for different target groups (decision makers, urban planners, citizens, kids, etc.), and iii) the potential of a nature-based economy for the local and regional economic development • Identify and engage with soil ambassadors at different levels
Output/Results	Tailored educational materials and tools on the benefits and values of unsealed soils and urban green and blue infrastructure for different audiences
Urgency (short-term: until 2027, mid-term: until 2035, long-term until: 2050)	<p>Short term: Produce tailored education materials for all European regions.</p> <p>Medium term: Establish an awareness-raising process about soil function values as part of the school curriculum (from primary education to the more advanced e.g. urban planning education) or in form of a citizen campaign.</p>
Synergies	Awareness-raising activities contribute to SMO8. On a broader level, GBI/NBS can contribute to a reduction of all soil threats on a local level in urban or sub-urban regions (SMO 1-7).
End users	<p>Citizens will profit most from unsealed soils and GBI/NBS due to a higher living comfort (cooling effect), higher recreational level, health and well-being</p> <p>Local policy makers in cities can use the education material and tools to raise awareness among citizens and to actively engage citizens in activities to green the cities</p>

Key stakeholders	<p>Researchers in the field of environmental education should develop i) pedagogic material and provide training sessions for teachers, for local planning experts, and ii) dissemination material (posters and videos) for citizens</p> <p>in co-operation with</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Planners at municipal/local level to ensure the contextuality of the education material • Citizen representatives should be involved to make sure different values and perceptions are being included and that the material is suitable for the target group • The building industry should be involved in the development as they can conserve soil functions by introducing blue and green infrastructure along construction works
Intermediaries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU Research initiatives on education and green urban development disseminate the education material EU-wide • City networks to disseminate the education material among their members • Teachers use the material in their educational programmes.
Barriers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Capacity barrier: No unique way of measuring and reporting (monitoring, verification and reporting -MRV) system. A streamlined and universally used MRV system is needed to accurately develop business models that are relevant across all EU countries. • Capacity building: Awareness raising requires a training scheme and dissemination procedures. This process requires expertise and staff, which is usually scarce. • Institutional barriers: It is very difficult to change school curricula and train teachers. • Financial barriers: Awareness raising costs money, in particular the development of training materials and carrying out training sessions. Low-cost options need to be developed – i.e. educational movies, self-guidance etc.
Living lab/ light-houses	<p>Urban living labs and especially lighthouses could function as incubators by developing awareness-raising materials, conducting training and showing good examples.</p>
Outcome	<p>Increased awareness about the benefits of unsealed soils and green infrastructure leads to behavioural change at different levels (i.e. house owners, spatial planners, developers)</p>

Milestones	<p>Milestone 1: Cost-efficient training material available (short term) Tailored training materials are available in all EU languages and implementation (trainings) in selected living labs and lighthouses.</p> <p>Milestone 2: Regional soil awareness coordinators established (medium term) A region-wide awareness-raising process is in place. In each EU region (NUTS3) a soil awareness coordinator is nominated who takes care of a cost-efficient rollout for key target groups (teachers, building sector, regional planning).</p> <p>Milestone 3: Awareness raising material updated and revised (long term) European soil awareness coordinators exchange their experience in an established network and work together on revising pedagogic material and on taking up emerging topics.</p>
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SMO 3	No net sealing and increase the reuse of urban soil
Key knowledge gap	SMO 3-4 Lack of policies and assessment/support tools at municipal level to reduce soil sealing and land take.
Sub-knowledge gaps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lack of assessment tools for local policymakers to evaluate development plans and ecosystem service delivery. 2. Lack of support tools for green public procurement at municipal level. 3. Lack of robust EU and national policies, programmes, legal frameworks, and regulations including short- and long-term strategic targets and economic instruments that help to reduce/avoid land take or compensate the impacts of soil sealing. 4. Lack of concepts and models to increase cooperation among different (sectoral) administrations
Relevant land use sector	All sub-knowledge gaps: industry and urban
Regional scope	Priority should be given to regions with high land take (outskirts of urban centres) because awareness of soil functions needs to be raised there in particular.
Research actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify and assess the legal and socio-economic dimension of land take across Member States • Develop targets for unsealing and for reusing sites

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop effective framework programmes and economic tools (e.g. taxes, incentives, eco-budgeting schemes) to prevent soil sealing or compensate soil sealing impacts • Develop decision frameworks for local policy makers for evaluating development plans and ecosystem service delivery • Identify and develop new governance models and co-creation approaches for more integrated urban planning to improve acceptance of innovation and reduce reluctance of regulatory bodies, break administrative silos and foster stewardship and inclusion • Identify and develop approaches to include cross-departmental and cross-sectoral collaboration in integrated planning, in combination with mainstreaming a net-zero soil sealing target • Develop ways to utilise policy levers such as collaboration platforms, financing support schemes or public procurement and planning strategies such as compact city planning, sustainable land management, landscape-level approaches, and rural-urban partnerships
Output/Results	Overview of policy instruments, approaches, and tools for effective decision-making to prevent and reduce soil sealing
Urgency (short-term: until 2027, mid-term: until 2035, long-term until: 2050)	<p>Short term Develop tools for local policy makers to evaluate development plans and ecosystem service delivery. Define regional targets for reusing sites and unsealing soils.</p> <p>Short term Develop support tools for green public procurement and other economic instruments (e.g. taxes, incentives, eco-budgeting schemes) to prevent soil sealing or compensate soil sealing impacts at municipal level.</p>
Synergies	If guidance documents are applied and policy makers are committing to ambitious targets, these actions can vitally contribute to reducing land degradation by avoiding sealing and/or ensuring compensation (SMO1), help increasing SOC content in soils if using green and blue infrastructure (GBI) and nature-based solutions (NBS) (SMO2), support restoration of soils (SMO4), restore and improve soil structure (SMO6), and reduce the footprint on soil by (SMO7).
End users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Planning departments at local and regional level: The tools will support them to redesign existing planning practices and improve administrative procedures e.g. by establishing collaborative governance approaches

Key stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spatial planning experts (Other) need to develop assessment tools in collaboration with soil experts (Researchers). • Finance and legal experts (Other) need to develop support tool for public procurement with regional planners (Other) and the building sector (land developers, architects, investors). • Managing authorities (Other) and local & regional policy maker need to be involved in the development to ensure the relevance and uptake of tools
Intermediaries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regional and national governments to inform cities about effective assessment tools and governance approaches and provide guidance • City networks to disseminate the education material among their members
Barriers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Capacity building: Training is required and regular exchange among those who are potential implementers • Political barriers: Political agreement of different sectors (industry, agriculture, nature protection, housing) with opposing interests is required, which is difficult to reach
Living lab/ light-houses	Urban living labs and lighthouses can co-operate with regional administrations and develop tools and conduct pilot implementations.
Outcome	EU-wide implementation of policy instruments and targets to reduce and compensate soil sealing and avoid/reduce land take
Milestones	<p>Milestone 1: National no net soil sealing and land take strategies and strategies are established (short term). Member States have defined and established measurable targets. And local and regional governments have access to tools and supporting material to develop effective framework programmes, new governance models and co-creation approaches.</p> <p>Milestone 2: National strategies and targets are implemented (medium term). EU Member States aim at reaching their national strategies and land take targets: i) national targets are broken down to regional targets, ii) local and regional planning departments evaluate ecosystem service delivery in spatial development plans, iii) green procurement is established in all EU regions, iv) effective governance structures are in place and administrative fragmentation for regional planning is avoided and v) and cross-sectoral planning is enforced.</p> <p>Milestone 3: National strategies and targets are revised (long term). Member States have revised their strategies, tools and targets based on their performance.</p>

SMO 3	No net sealing and increase the reuse of urban soil
Key knowledge gap	SMO 3 (5) Lack of spatial planning tools and architectural innovations
Sub-knowledge gaps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lack of integrated urban and landscape planning and management approaches 2. Lack of knowledge about the inclusion of the concept of "healthy soils" and the weighting of soil functions in spatial planning 3. Lack of architectural innovations to contribute to sustainable solutions (including innovations in the architectural and building sector regarding the densification of existing urban areas to avoid building on green areas)
Relevant land use sector	All sub-knowledge gaps: industry and urban
Regional scope	Priority should be given to regions with high land take (outskirts of urban centres) because awareness of soil functions needs to be raised there in particular.
Research actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop integrated landscape planning and management approaches that balance different demands for land use and bring together key stakeholders for joint action to prevent soil sealing, minimise negative impacts, increase urban recycling of land and foster multifunctional land use (e.g. local Green Deals) and efficient use of urban space • Develop guidelines on how to weight and integrate soil functions and services (soil health) into urban and spatial planning • Develop architectural and building solutions to minimise soil sealing
Output/Results	Overview of integrated landscape planning and management approaches including architectural solutions and guidance on how to include soil functions in spatial planning and to reduce the impact of soil sealing.
Urgency (short-term: until 2027, mid-term: until 2035, long-term until: 2050)	<p>Short term: Researchers from spatial planning, nature protection and agriculture develop planning approaches that also enable co-operation with practitioners. Living Labs and Lighthouses contribute to pilot implementations and an increased knowledge base.</p> <p>Medium term: Architects, along with the building industry, develop architectural innovations in the context of healthy soils.</p>

Synergies	Integrated landscape planning which also considers soil functions and aims for reduced soil sealing and land take, can especially contribute to reduced land degradation by: avoiding sealing and/or ensuring compensation (SMO1), helping increasing SOC content in soils when green and blue infrastructure (GBI) and nature-based solutions (NBS) are used (SMO2), supporting the restoration of soils (SMO4) restoring and improving soil structure (SMO6) and reducing the footprint on soil (SMO7).
End users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regional spatial planners use the concepts in regional development plans and when issuing building permits. They benefit from this approach by keeping as many functional soils as possible available for their communities. Architects and developers implement sustainable (“soil friendly”) architectural innovations in building projects. They benefit from this approach by being able to keep as much functional soils free as possible. These can be used for green and blue infrastructure.
Key stakeholders	<p>Researchers from spatial planning, nature protection and agriculture</p> <p>Business and Industry: Architects and building industry</p>
Intermediaries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Researchers from spatial planning, nature protection and agriculture develop and adopt planning approaches in co-operation with practitioners Architects together with the building industry develop architectural innovations in the context of healthy soils Research initiatives can disseminate use knowledge gained from pilot implementations (Living Labs and Lighthouses)
Barriers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Capacity building. Training is required and regular exchange among those who are potential implementers. Cultural barriers: Architectural innovation is often confronted with criticism and not easy to implement.
Living lab/ light-houses	Urban living labs and lighthouses can co-operate with local planning authorities and architects, in order to test concepts or tools at regional or local level.
Outcome	EU-wide implementation of concepts for integrated spatial planning and landscape management approaches to minimise the impact of soil sealing
Milestones	Milestone 1: Integrated spatial planning including concept for healthy soils available (short term) All European regions, in particular those with high land take, have access to planning tools for integrated spatial planning including a concept for

healthy soils and can readily implement these tools in their regional spatial planning.

Milestone 2: Integrated spatial planning including concept for healthy soils established (medium term) All European regions implement planning tools for integrated spatial planning including a concept for healthy soils. Architectural innovations contribute to the concept. Knowledge platforms for regular exchange are available.

ANNEX IV: DETAILED FACTSHEETS SMO4 - REDUCE SOIL POLLUTION AND ENHANCE RESTORATION

SMO 4	Reduce soil pollution and enhance restoration
Key knowledge gap	SMO 4 -1 Lack of knowledge of the fate and impact of pollutants
Sub-knowledge gaps	<p>3. Lacking or insufficient knowledge of short- and long-term impacts of Contaminants of Concern (CoC - especially emerging, microplastics, antibiotic resistant bacteria and chemical mixtures) on soil health, ecosystem services, food chains and human health</p> <p>4. Lacking or insufficient knowledge of pollution threats in terms of circular economy (e.g. material (re)use, such as biochar, sand and compost)</p>
Relevant land use sector	<p>Sub knowledge gap 1: all sectors</p> <p>Sub knowledge gap 2: Urban and industry and (urban) agriculture</p>
Regional scope	N/A (relevant to all regions)
Research actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Investigate and assess the behaviour, persistence and long- and short-term effects and risks of CoC, especially emerging contaminants, Substances of Very High Concern (SVHC) and chemical mixtures on the ecosystem (soil health) and human health from polluted sites across Europe and under different soil management regimes and land uses. For achieving long-term observations, subsequent projects should preferably be executed at the same sites. Integrate assessments of the impacts of chemicals on both soil and human health as part of the regulatory safety assessment in particular for pesticides. Identify and assess the risks and potential of the reuse of materials (sand, clay, gravel, biochar, compost, etc.) in light of the circular economy
Output/Results	Characterisation of the main environmental pollutants in soil and insights on their fate and transport under different soil management regimes
Urgency (short-term: until 2027, mid-term: until 2035, long-term until: 2050)	<p>Short term: Investigate effects and risks of pollutants including SVHC on field sites across Europe.</p> <p>Medium term: Set up monitoring experiments for fate, transport and impacts of contaminants.</p> <p>Long term: Integrate findings in effective policy and regulation regarding safety/risk assessment and reuse of materials (CE).</p>
Synergies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> There are synergies with SMO 1 as there are indications that pollution has a negative effect on soil carbon stocks, but this needs further investigation.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There are potential synergies with SMO 7 in terms of CE practices where e.g. soils/composts/sludges/biogenic organic waste are being transported across boundaries. When risks on transporting polluted materials are lowered, this has a positive effect.
End users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU policymakers, national/regional policymakers and international stakeholders are end-users because the information obtained in risk inventory and assessment projects supports policymaking and helps setting up effective (new) regulation (e.g. for emerging contaminants). • Citizens benefits in terms of lower health risks and an improved living environment • Researchers are an end-user because they use the results of these projects to better understand the context and focus their research on the most important pollutants
Key stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The key stakeholders are policymakers who should use the knowledge to improve current and/or develop new policies and inform the design of the soil management strategy, including a programme of measures aimed to achieve SMO 4. • Researchers should be involved to conduct research together with land managers and industrial stakeholders, including consultants.
Intermediaries	<p>Researchers, research initiatives and expert networks can pass results to policymakers and end users to set up effective regulation for the use, avoidance and management of substances and CE practices in land management or production processes. Farm advisory services can support this.</p>
Barriers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial barriers and institutional barriers hampering the continuity of research: It is often not possible to acquire follow-up projects at the same study sites, which hinders long-term monitoring. • In some MS political barriers: There are no soil protection regulations in place and the problems are insufficiently recognised. Political courage and vision are needed. • Others: Underestimation or downsizing of the risk on (business-driven) purpose.
Living lab/ light-houses	<p>This topic of research is not specifically suitable to be taken up in Living Labs (LL) because LL are set up in real-life settings and with co-creation and would therefore rather be focused on remediating (SMO 4 (3)). A more protected test facility</p>

	(such as a “normal laboratory”, or a protected site that is not accessible to the public) would therefore be more suitable for research.
Outcome	Improved understanding of short- and long-term fate and impact of soil pollutants on soil and human health and under different circumstances
Milestones	<p>Milestone 1: Investigate effects and risks of pollutants incl. CoC on sites (short term): First projects on the investigation of the effects and risks of pollutants incl. SVHC on sites started and (in their 2nd or 3rd year) delivered valuable and actionable outcomes for the users. Results have been transferred to them.</p> <p>Milestone 2: Set up monitoring experiments for fate, transport and impacts of contaminants (medium term): Monitoring experiments for fate, transport and impacts of contaminants are put in place.</p> <p>Milestone 3: Integrate findings in effective policy and regulation regarding safety/risk assessment and reuse of materials (CE) (long term): Findings of the research activities are integrated in informed polluted soil policy development and management options. These policies and management options have been put in practice, which notably contributed to achieving of SMO4.</p>

SMO 4	Reduce soil pollution and enhance restoration
Key knowledge gap	SMO 4-2 Lack of cost-effective methods for mapping and monitoring of pollution
Sub-knowledge gaps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Lacking EU harmonised, robust and smart monitoring methods for mapping and monitoring soil pollution in Europe 4. Lack of (cost-)effective tools and indicators to assess soil health of polluted and remediated soils 5. Lack of knowledge in the use of existing data to predict future risks, e.g. through machine learning
Relevant land use sector	Sub knowledge gap 1-3: all sectors
Regional scope	There is no specific regional scope, except that monitoring measures and (cost-) effective methods may differ for point source and regional pollution.
Research actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop a set of indicators related to of soil health specifically for polluted/remediated sites • Explore the state-of-the-art of (smart) monitoring and mapping methods

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assess the potential of digital transformation and develop innovative sensing methods and tools • Exchange monitoring and mapping methods through initiatives (incl. networks, platforms, Research Infrastructures) to further harmonise these methods throughout Europe. • Develop ways to use machine learning to predict risks of pollutants
Output/Results	Agreed and shared robust monitoring schemes based on (cost-)effective monitoring methods to assess the status and changes in soil pollution in Europe
Urgency (short-term: until 2027, mid-term: until 2035, long-term until: 2050)	<p>Short term: Collate, review and synthesise the state-of-the-art and recommend further actions (new developments) on cost-effective, robust and smart monitoring methods. Initiate an innovation programme for innovative sensing methods and tools that can be applied in the medium term.</p> <p>Short term: Activate initiatives (incl. networks, platforms, research Infrastructures) to share monitoring and mapping methods.</p> <p>Medium and long term: Harmonise monitoring and mapping methods including new sensing methods on polluted soil sites on European level.</p>
Synergies	There are synergies with SMO: The proposed CSA and RIA (Research and Innovation Action) projects provide a great opportunity to share information on monitoring and mapping methods for soil pollution and thus improve soil literacy.
End users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU, national and regional policymakers are end-users because the information obtained by mapping and monitoring soil pollution will facilitate the review of the effectiveness of policy instruments and prioritisation of action. • Researchers are an end-user because they can use the monitoring and mapping methods for doing research. • Landowners can make use of the (cost-)effective monitoring and mapping methods to assess the status of soil contamination and the need for remediation. This can lower costs (polluter pays principle).
Key stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The key stakeholders are policymakers who are responsible for monitoring and mapping of soil pollution. • Land managers and industry stakeholders, including consultants, should be involved to assess the applicability in practice.
Intermediaries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers can support the knowledge transfer to users. • Farm advisory, farm associations and e.g. consultants and commercial labs can help to implement monitoring and mapping in practice (also in commission of land owners)

Barriers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Political barrier: Willingness to apply the soil pollution monitoring and mapping methods may be low as ‘no information, no problem to be managed’ Capacity building: Availability and free access of data is often not given.
Living lab/ light-houses	Monitoring and mapping of soil pollution can be part of Living Labs. Lighthouses will become those sites where the innovations and practices have improved soil health.
Outcome	In-depth insights in the status of and changes in soil contamination in Europe to inform policy
Milestones	<p>Milestone 1: Identification of state-of-the-art monitoring methods and further needs (short term): Based on project results an overview is provided ‘where we are and where to go’ with soil pollution monitoring and mapping methods including digital transformation.</p> <p>Milestone 2: Development of new monitoring methods for mapping soil pollution in Europe (short to medium term): New cost-effective and smart techniques including sensing methods are developed, ready to use and disseminated to the users.</p> <p>Milestone 3: Implementation of project results in soil policy (long term): Results of the projects informed polluted soil policy development and harmonisation of methods across Europe.</p>

SMO 4	Reduce soil pollution and enhance restoration
Key knowledge gap	SMO 4-3 Lack of suitable approaches and innovations regarding prevention and remediation
Sub-knowledge gaps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Lacking or insufficient knowledge on sustainable pollution prevention and remediation <u>approaches</u> including how ‘land stewardship’ can improve the overall performance of ecosystem services Knowledge on pollution prevention and of remediation <u>measures</u> including nature-based solutions and methods for safe circular reuse of materials with a special focus on cost- and energy-effectiveness and technical, organisational, and legal implementation.
Relevant land use sector	Sub knowledge gap 1-2: all sectors
Regionalscope	N/A (relevant to all regions)

Research actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify and develop cost-effective measures to prevent pollution and to deal with emerging contaminants including microplastic in soils. Make use of machine learning to predict future risks. • Identify target values in the context of restoring soils in relation to their use. • Develop, verify and approve more cost- and energy-effective remediation techniques and nature-based solutions. • Develop legal, financial and awareness approaches for the prevention of contamination and restoration of contaminated sites and brownfields (such as land stewardship concepts). • Identify methods and approaches to reduce the risks of the reuse of materials (sand, clay, gravel, biochar, compost, etc.) including testing, cleaning, monitoring, financial, legal and governance aspects
Output/Results	Guidance on sustainable site management measures and approaches that prevent contamination and a comprehensive overview of applicable verified and accepted sustainable, cost- and energy-effective remediation techniques
Urgency (short-term: until 2027, mid-term: until 2035, long-term until: 2050)	<p>Short term: Establish “where we are and where to go best” in a single, 3-year CSA project in which to collate, review and synthesise the state-of-the-art and recommend further actions (new developments) on pollution prevention and remediation approaches and measures</p> <p>Medium and long term: Application of pollution prevention and remediation approaches and measures in policy and practice</p>
Synergies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • With SMO 1: There are indications that pollution has a negative effect on soil carbon stocks, but this needs further investigation. If this is indeed the case, prevention and restoration may help carbon conservation. • With SMO 2: Polluted urban soil after restoration increases re-use opportunities. • With SMO 6: Pollution impacts biodiversity. Thus, prevention of pollution will conserve biodiversity and restoration of polluted soil will also enhance biodiversity. • With SMO 8: The proposed CSA and RIA projects also heavily focus on sharing of information on pollution prevention and remediation approaches and measures and thus improve soil literacy.
End users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU, national and regional policymakers can utilise information to develop (and co-design) policy approaches and guidelines for pollution prevention and of the remediation of polluted sites.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consultancy firms and companies specialised in the application of pollution prevention and remediation approaches and measures can use the approaches and methods in their daily work. • Advisors will advise landowners on the best practices that suit farm and regional conditions. • Land managers will be provided with a set of science-based measures to prevent pollution on their farm and in the field.
Key stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policymakers responsible for policy making and initiation of soil management strategies including developing a programme of pollution prevention and restoration measures. • Industry, agrobusiness and land managers know their processes and used products/chemicals best. They should be involved to agree on workable management practices.
Intermediaries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientists can exchange knowledge to policy and practice based on the research performed. • Farm advisory and land management advisors and consultants can pass on information and guidelines to landowners.
Barriers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial barriers: Remediation is often very costly. The longer you wait to remediate, the higher the future cost due to the distribution of the pollution. It is not clear who should pay for it. However, there are different EU countries with appropriate legislation (Polluter pays principle). Space for development (housing, industry) is getting more and more scarce. This means that remediation of sites becomes more and more attractive because these sites are available, and remediation can become financially attractive. • Political and institutional barriers can hamper the start of actions to remediate sites, e.g. because there is no (national) regulation in place, or actors do not trust each other, or when ownership changes make it unclear who is responsible. • Capacity building: Not in all countries is the knowledge available to start up remediation of complex sites or regions.
Living lab/ light-houses	<p>Living Labs can be a vehicle for research where i) the pollution prevention and restoration approaches and measures (resulting from action above) are applied in practice, tested with practitioners and further improved, and ii) this informs policy development and management practice. Lighthouses will become those sites where the innovations and practices have improved soil health.</p>

Outcome	Improved possibilities to accelerate remediation processes in Europe at lower costs and avoid or reduce further negative impacts on the environment
Milestones	<p>Milestone 1: Overview on the state-of-the-art (short term): The projects provide a comprehensive overview on the state-of-the-art in pollution prevention and remediation approaches and measures and recommendations for further developments.</p> <p>Milestone 2: Implementation of project results in soil policy (medium to long term) Results of the projects are taken up in polluted soil policy and available as management options for practice.</p>

SMO 4	Reduce soil pollution and enhance restoration
Key knowledge gap	SMO 4-4 Lack of knowledge exchange and capacity building on measures to avoid soil pollution
Sub-knowledge gaps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lacking communication methods and capacity building for measures that can cause or prevent pollution and thus affect soil health. 2. Lack of professional training on soils and groundwater in schools, universities, relevant authorities and companies. 3. Lack of sufficient methods to increase knowledge exchange between member states on remediation techniques and polluted site management.
Relevant land use sector	Sub knowledge gap 1-3: all sectors
Regional scope	N/A (relevant to all regions)
Research actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop education material and professional training on the effects and the prevention of soil pollution for different stakeholder groups including schools and citizens. • Define priorities and develop effective dissemination methods for measures (incl. alternatives) that can cause pollution or affect soil health in order to prevent these. • Develop methods to increase knowledge exchange between more and less experienced member states and organisations on remediation techniques, soil restoration and brownfield management.
Output/Results	Dissemination and capacity building methods for sustainable soil management measures and techniques to avoid soil pollution within Europe.

<p>Urgency (short-term: until 2027, mid-term: until 2035, long-term until: 2050)</p>	<p>Short term: Identify education strategies and develop materials for different age groups, from primary school to high school and university.</p> <p>Short to medium term: Inventory knowledge needs and improve knowledge exchange by establishing effective knowledge exchange and capacity building between countries (at EU level) that have experience and countries that need the knowledge, e.g. by creating a team of researchers, advisors and policymakers who can support their counterparts abroad to improve knowledge.</p>
<p>Synergies</p>	<p>There are synergies with SMO as it focuses on sharing information and thus the dissemination methods will help to improve soil literacy.</p>
<p>End users</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU, national and regional policymakers - increased knowledge exchange on best practice will help to better identify suitable measures and communication methods will help to transfer information on measures that can prevent or restore pollution. • Land users, consultancy firms and companies specialised in application of pollution prevention and remediation approaches and measures will be more effectively informed about best available methods. • Students and citizens will be better informed about the risks of soil pollution and the need for remediation.
<p>Key stakeholders</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers (including consultants) can help to develop suitable trainings and prioritise measures for dissemination. • Policymakers on EU, national and regional levels need to be involved in knowledge exchange activities.
<p>Intermediaries</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU networks (scientific, industry, farmers, landowners, policymakers) are important in supporting the exchange of knowledge and experiences on EU level. • Farm advisory and (industrial) consultants can have an important role as an intermediary between science, policy and practice and can train people intensively in this field of expertise.
<p>Barriers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Political barriers: When there is no soil policy in place in member states, the need for action and thus knowledge exchange can be strongly hampered. • Institutional barriers: Actors need to trust each other, to collaborate and exchange knowledge not on financial grounds, but with the objective to enhance the situation and contribute to the SMO4.

Living lab/ light-houses	Living Labs and especially Lighthouses (sites with exemplary performance) could be effective tools to demonstrate measures to broader audiences and support capacity building and knowledge exchange.
Outcome	Improved exchange and increased knowledge and use of techniques and methods that prevent pollution or restore polluted sites and thus protect or restore soil health.
Milestones	<p>Milestone 1: Inventory of knowledge needs (short term) - Overview of knowledge gaps and needs of different kinds of actors.</p> <p>Milestone 2: Develop education and awareness raising material (short term) – Based on identified knowledge needs, suitable materials for education and awareness raising is developed.</p> <p>Milestone 3: Setup of an EU exchange network (medium term): Setup of an effective exchange and capacity building network in Europe with scientists, consultants and policymakers that can support their counterparts abroad to even the level of knowledge.</p>

SMO 4	Reduce soil pollution and enhance restoration
Key knowledge gap	SMO 4-5 Lack of targets and incentives to start restoration
Sub-knowledge gaps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lack of EU and national soil pollution prevention and remediation targets (incl. for emerging contaminants). 2. Lack of methods to prioritise polluted sites in Europe. 3. Lack of adequate incentives, programmes, funding mechanisms, business models and control mechanisms to start restoration. 4. Lack of knowledge of how pollution hinders circular economy, e.g. (re)use, of materials such as biochar, sand, compost.
Relevant land use sector	<p>Sub knowledge gap 1-3: all sectors</p> <p>Sub knowledge gap 4: mainly agriculture, urban and industry</p>
Regional scope	N/A (relevant to all regions)
Research actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop for all member states guidance on how to set remediation targets, prioritise polluted sites, reuse materials and on how to draft a soil management strategy. • Develop a prioritisation method and nature-positive incentives/funding mechanisms/programmes for contaminated sites and brownfields in Europe.

Output/Results	Regulation, policy standards, targets and programmes for remediation on European scale
Urgency (short-term: until 2027, mid-term: until 2035, long-term until: 2050)	<p>Short term: Co-develop methods and tools to prioritise polluted sites in Europe including cost-effectiveness.</p> <p>Short term: Establish an expert group of EU and national policymakers, scientists, and other relevant stakeholder groups (e.g. companies for remediation of polluted soils and industrial stakeholder) to develop guidance on how to set remediation targets and how to prioritise polluted sites and how to reuse materials.</p> <p>Medium term: Co-develop EU/national funding programs and business models to incentivise restoration of polluted soils in Europe.</p>
Synergies	Targets and programmes for remediation on European scale will also have a positive effect on SMO 1 (as pollution has a negative effect on soil carbon stocks), SMO 2 (as this will increase re-use opportunities) and SMO 6 (as restoration of polluted soil will also enhance biodiversity).
End users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU, national and regional policymakers need to implement targets and incentives in effective policy and/or regulations to start up restoration. • Land manager and landowners are end-users, while the developed knowledge will make clear where restoration of soil and land is needed, where to start and to what extent. • Consultancy firms will use the knowledge in their work related to soil restoration.
Key stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policymakers are the key stakeholders that need to implement the targets and incentives in policy and regulation. • Researchers need to perform the research to set up realistic and effective targets and incentives to start up soil restoration, together with end-users (all kinds of land users and landowners).
Intermediaries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Here the main intermediaries will be the farm advisory services and consultancies that (in many cases commissioned by the policymaker and/or end-user) can translate the science and policies to practice, or the end users. • Also, European networks can play a strong role here by exchanging the “good examples” and discuss harmonised targets and methods.
Barriers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Political: Reluctance of the MS to set generic, i.e. EU-wide targets. However, the EU Soil Health Law is expected in 2023, which might take away part of this barrier.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Capacity building: Drafting of EU guidance documents is a time-consuming and intensive process which will only be accomplished successfully if MS are willing to support the drafting by a delegation of national experts to help the drafting.
Living lab/ light-houses	N/A
Outcome	Better implementation of sustainable remediation of polluted soils in all Member States.
Milestones	<p>Milestone 1: Expert group is established (short term) An EU expert group including all relevant stakeholder groups to discuss targets and incentives is established (<i>this could be the soil expert group on the soil strategy</i>).</p> <p>Milestone 2: Guidelines and tools for prioritisation developed (medium term) The expert group agreed on how to set remediation targets at EU/national/regional levels and how to prioritise polluted sites.</p> <p>Milestone 3: Guidance is disseminated (long term) Guidance documents including business models are used to develop soil policy development and management options. Based on the guidelines, targets for remediation measures are set at EU, national and regional levels and business models and financing instruments are introduced.</p>

ANNEX V: DETAILED FACTSHEETS SMO 5 - PREVENT EROSION

SMO 5	Prevent erosion
Key knowledge gap	SMO 5-1 Lack of knowledge on (socio-economic) trade-offs and synergies between soil erosion, ecosystem services and climate change
Sub-knowledge gaps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of knowledge of effects and trade-offs of land management (e.g. no-tillage), water management (irrigation and drainage) and climate change including GHG emissions Lack of knowledge on trade-offs and synergies between soil erosion regulation and other ecosystem services both on and off site (field, river, catchment)
Relevant land use sector	Sub knowledge gap 1-2: all sectors

Regionalscope	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Erosion is more prominent in the Mediterranean region, but is not restricted to it. Mountain areas are particularly prone to erosion and control poses a particular challenge. • Changing erosion dynamics can be expected with changes of climate patterns and vegetation due to climate change. For example, in the Baltic coastal areas with erosion-sensitive clay soils, water erosion occurs in milder winters and with fewer frost days.
Research actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Study and determine effects, trade-offs, and synergies of erosion with a focus on land and water management practices as well as water provision and future impact of climate change on vegetation, soil functions and ecosystem services (from plot to catchment scale). • Investigate the role of soil hydrology and soil functions like infiltration capacity to reduce the risk of water erosion which is e.g. essential after heavy rains and mild winters in the north. • Investigate the socio-economic impacts, trade-offs, and synergies of erosion, including soil erosion induced organic carbon fluxes to be included in regional and national greenhouse gas emission budgets.
Output/Results	Holistic overview of effects of erosion and land and water management measures on soil functions and ecosystem services
Urgency (short-term: until 2027, mid-term: until 2035, long-term until: 2050)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short term: Study trade-offs of soil erosion measures on other ecosystem services such as water provision and climate mitigation as well as water conserving measures such as drip irrigation and soil erosion. • Short term: Initiate studies to quantify socio-economic consequences of soil erosion in river basins and coastal areas, including projections of these under climate change • Short term: Initiate modelling studies on fluxes of soil organic carbon induced by soil erosion at the regional level • Medium term: Summarise the outcomes of existing success stories and of the studies on socio-economic consequences of soil erosion at river basin scale, and identify policy or market instruments for each land use sector, that could provide technical and financial support to implement erosion control measures
Synergies	Reduced levels of soil erosion enhance vegetation growth and therefore help to reduce desertification (SMO1), improve soil structure, and enhance soil biodiversity (SMO6), help to keep soil organic matter and plant nutrients in the topsoil,

	safeguarding soil fertility in farmland (SMO 2) and, more generally, keep pollutants in place for all soils (SMO4). Soil erosion is an easily perceptible form of soil degradation. Therefore, it can be used in SMO8 to improve soil literacy in society.
End users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Land managers and landowners (including industry & agro business) will gain awareness of the problem of soil erosion and a basis for decision making on erosion control measures and adapted land and water management measures. • Researchers will gain an increased and holistic understanding of the subject area required to design land and water management options. • Policymakers will gain awareness of the problem of soil erosion and have a foundation for designing and selecting incentives and policy instruments. • Citizens will gain awareness on the importance of erosion measures (especially in agriculture, but also other land uses) for other ecosystem services and general sustainability.
Key stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Beside researchers, land managers and landowners (including farmers, industry and agro business) should be involved in evaluating the socio-economic impacts.
Intermediaries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Environmental agencies and research institutions or initiatives at the European or national level can alert policymakers to the occurrence of trade-offs and synergies between soil erosion, climate change and ecosystem services. • Regional authorities can be intermediaries between the policymakers on one side and land managers and landowners (including business stakeholders) on the other side to provide information on the level of soil erosion in the region and on ways to overcome trade-offs. • Farm advisory services and farm associations can take on this role specifically for land managers, while organised interest groups can take on the role for industry and agro business. • NGOs or private cooperatives can reach citizens to increase awareness of the need to protect land from soil erosion through campaigns and media.
Barriers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Capacity building: lack of measurement/monitoring networks for the assessment of long-term (socio-economic) effects related to erosion.
Living lab/ light-houses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collecting evidence of successful designs for erosion control in farms, industrial terrains, recreation areas including the importance of soil health soil functions (aggregate stability, infiltration capacity) and ecosystem services.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Studies to quantify socio-economic consequences of soil erosion in clusters of farms or recreational areas at the level of river basins, including projections of these under climate change.
Outcome	Improved understanding of best practices to prevent erosion and minimise trade-offs of different land and water-management practices in different pedo-climatic zones.
Milestones	<p>Milestone 1: Trade-offs assessed and overview of management options available (short term): A thorough assessment of the trade-offs of currently available erosion control measures with ecosystem services is undertaken and an overview of suitable management is available based on the findings of 50 cases of agricultural enterprises, industrial terrains subject to soil erosion and regional or national parks with intensive recreational activity.</p> <p>Milestone 2: Synergies of erosion control with ecosystem services identified (short term) Holistic synergies of land and water management practices on soil functions and ecosystem services with specific attention to erosion (from plot to catchment scale) are identified.</p> <p>Milestone 3: Impact of soil erosion on GHG emissions assessed (short term) GHG emission budgets with accounts of soil erosion are modelled for each member state and are ready to be included in national greenhouse gas emission budgets.</p>

SMO 5	Prevent erosion
Key knowledge gap	SMO 5-2 Lack of suitable erosion prevention and restoration measures that are socio-economically viable
Sub-knowledge gaps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of (nature-based) erosion prevention measures better linked to local conditions, economic factors and practitioners' needs (participatory research) for different land uses and pedo-climatic zones. Lack of proven restoration options in highly eroded landscapes. Lack of knowledge on socio-economic factors influencing the adoption of erosion preventing management.
Relevant land use sector	Sub knowledge gap 1-3: all land use

Regionalscope	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Applicable to regions with intolerable erosion risk for the given land-use sectors, agricultural land, especially in new plantations, as well as soil in nature and forestry areas affected by fires. • The regional scope should address an even smaller scale to identify areas where hotspots exist. • In the north, the local particularity are runoffs during milder winters which cause water erosion in fine-textured soils which had been adapted to a frosty period.
Research actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Combine socio-economic and participatory research with biophysical research to improve understanding and uptake of preventive measures. • Investigate the role of crop rotation by grasses, and the availability for markets for that biomass due to soil improvement by alive and intensive grass rooting, e.g. biogas and dairy. • Develop and test restoration options in eroded landscapes or that are under erosion risk in different pedo-climatic zones under different land uses. • Find the best land use or mix of land uses for each site by evaluating potential land use modification choices. • Co-design policy and retail (marketing) environments that encourage erosion prevention measures.
Output/Results	<p>Overview of prevention and restoration measures in different pedo-climatic zones under different land uses and socio-economic conditions and improved understanding of preventing and promoting factors for swift implementation of good practice.</p>
Urgency (short-term: until 2027, mid-term: until 2035, long-term until: 2050)	<p>Short term: Develop technical and socioeconomic studies to evaluate socioeconomic factors that affect the adoption of erosion prevention measures, such as using Lighthouses to include erosion prevention as a subject in regions with erosion problems where strategies for land use change are already developed for climate change adaptation.</p> <p>Choose areas that are particularly vulnerable to soil erosion (such as those that are prone to wildfire, drought, or abandonment) and launch test sites for restoration techniques.</p> <p>Medium term: Design or modify tools for policy and markets to promote the adoption of erosion prevention measures and accompanying communication materials, particularly for regions at risk of erosion, based on the findings of the socio-economic and technical research.</p>

	<p>Long term: Implementation of erosion-control measures should be embedded in a long-term vision such as advocated by https://4returns.commonland.com/getting-started/</p>
Synergies	<p>Reduced levels of soil erosion enhance vegetation growth and therefore help to reduce desertification (SMO1), improve soil structure and enhance soil biodiversity (SMO6), reduce the need to import food and feed crops from elsewhere (SMO7). Preventing soil erosion helps to keep soil organic matter in the topsoil (SMO2) and pollutants in place (SMO 4). Soil erosion is an easily perceptible form of soil degradation. Therefore, it can be used in SMO8 to improve soil literacy in society.</p>
End users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Land managers, landowners (including industry & agro business) and advisors will receive information on options for erosion control they can apply in their business or recommend to clients (advisory services). • Researchers will gain an increased understanding of the functioning and practicability of erosion control or restoration measures in landscapes with high levels of actual erosion or landscapes showing signs of starting erosion. • Policymakers will acquire information on which socio-economic factors are relevant to consider in the design of policy instruments for environmental management.
Key stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers (including engineers): need to develop better NBS that are socially and culturally acceptable as well as economically viable. • Land managers need to implement the measures and should be enabled to evaluate soil protecting measures in terms of practice relevance and find the best balance between investment and benefits for the enterprise • Policymaker and governing bodies: need to create the enabling conditions and regulatory measures, that will ensure the uptake of these NBS. They should develop science-based guidelines and co-design policies that help land manager to find solutions that will allow sustainable business (both biophysical as well as socio-economic) • Industry & Agro-business should find NBS that are economically interesting.
Intermediaries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research institutes, networks and expert groups can communicate results on socio-economic factors relevant to consider by policymakers in the design and planning of erosion control measures (regional or national level).

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Businesses (e.g. agrifood or wood-processing companies, engineering firms) can transfer options for erosion prevention and control to land managers (including recreation areas and industrial sites). • Farm advisory services and farm associations will transfer the knowledge to land managers. • Environmental agencies of national or regional authorities can inform municipalities on nature-based solutions for erosion prevention (e.g. in planning of residential areas). • Environmental NGOs and commercial interest organizations (such as cooperatives and foundations) can inform the public on the need of erosion management in specific areas.
Barriers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial barriers: Economic risk for adaptation is too high; lack of economically viable options for good practice. • Political barriers: no sufficiently-targeted policies to prevent erosion and insufficient knowledge about trade-offs of policies that promote unsustainable practices (e.g. the implementation of drip irrigation on hillslopes).
Living lab/ light-houses	Here, living labs and lighthouses are particularly useful for all activities mentioned above, e.g co-creating a best- practice solution with a wide range of stakeholder.
Outcome	Improved uptake and choice of prevention and restoration measures based on local conditions and increased understanding of socio-economic and cultural factors
Milestones	<p>Milestone 1: Socio-economic aspects of erosion control identified (short term) Based on the outcome of socio-economic and participatory research in combination with biophysical research, suitable prevention measures and land-use options are identified and the uptake of these measures is increased.</p> <p>Milestone 2: Restoration options identified and tested (medium term) In diverse pedo-climatic zones and with various land uses, restoration strategies in damaged landscapes or those that are at danger of erosion are discovered and tested throughout Europe.</p> <p>Milestone 3: Policies promoting NBS for erosion prevention in place (long term) Policies that promote the implementation of NBS for erosion prevention are designed or adjusted and put in place.</p>

SMO 5	Prevent erosion
Key knowledge gap	SMO 5-3 Lack of monitoring and modelling tools for different types of erosion on multiple scales
Sub-knowledge gaps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lack of evaluation tools for trade-offs of land and water management choices. 2. Lack of good monitoring and modelling techniques to assess all kinds of erosion and effects on- and off-site. 3. Lack of local “severity maps” to indicate hotspots where immediate action is required (for practitioners and policy makers). 4. Lack of methods to conduct probability estimates of soil erosion events under climate change.
Relevant land use sector	<p>Sub knowledge gap 1: Agri (tools already available, but to a lesser degree on the larger scale), but also nature and forestry</p> <p>Sub knowledge gap 2: All land uses</p> <p>Sub knowledge gap 3 and 4: All land uses, but especially agriculture, nature, and forestry</p>
Regionalscope	Information on a local scale is scarce. Since erosion hotspots, including those caused by wind and water, are frequently smaller than the regional level, greater effort should be made to fully understand them. However, areas that are susceptible to erosion due to the type of pedo-climatic zone and land use, should be monitored more carefully, incorporating various management techniques in agriculture and forestry.
Research actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop tools for local erosion control planning, including trade-offs of land and water management choices on plot and landscape level combining remote sensing and on-site measurements. • Develop an understanding of the need for soil drainage to prevent excessive water flows that cause water erosion. • Develop monitoring and modelling tools that can accurately and cost - effectively assess the entire erosion process (detachment, transport, and deposition), taking into account the impact of land management options.
Output/Results	Planning tools and models to evaluate and monitor erosion processes and trade-offs of land and water management practices

<p>Urgency (short-term: until 2027, mid-term: until 2035, long-term until: 2050)</p>	<p>Short term/medium term: Create tools for monitoring the erosion process on a farm to landscape scale. These tools should consider both the detaching and the depositing phases of the process, as well as the connectivity of the landscape and the movement of sediment, related components (pollutants/nutrients), and soil organic matter on a range of scales.</p> <p>Medium term: Develop tools to monitor the trade-offs of land and water management strategies at plot to landscape scale.</p> <p>Options for both actions can be found in remote sensing and AI. However, these novel techniques should be combined with existing field survey tools.</p>
<p>Synergies</p>	<p>The development of good tools for assessing soil erosion is also useful for assessing desertification processes (SMO1) and assessing the movement of soil organic carbon (SMO2). This information can also be relevant for soil chemical and biological processes and the possible restoration options (SMO4 and 6). These visual tools can provide images that are useful for informing other stakeholders and enhancing soil literacy among all stakeholders (SMO7).</p>
<p>End users</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Measuring and monitoring opportunities for land managers give them the possibility to get a picture of their situation and to see the effects of their land management measures. • Policymakers and governmental agencies are responsible for monitoring and can use models to provide subsidies for areas with a high erosion risk. • Researchers can develop and use new measurement, monitoring and modeling tools to better understand the process of erosion (detachment, transport, and deposition). As a result, they can provide easy-to-use tools for other stakeholder groups. • Industry can use the developed tools to assess the state of and changes in land quality in terms of erosion and the effects of products they develop.
<p>Key stakeholders</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers need to develop and evaluate new tools. • Industry & agro business need to co-develop tools. • Land managers need to evaluate the usefulness and user-friendliness of tools (e.g. carbon farming tools need to be sufficiently easy to use). • Policymakers need to define the framework of the desired tools.
<p>Intermediaries</p>	<p>New instruments need to be introduced to the end-users (land managers) by advisory services or public-private partnership. European research initiatives and</p>

	networks could support liaisons between knowledge owners and knowledge users.
Barriers	<p>Cultural barrier: Land managers are not ready to use these kinds of sophisticated tools - they may not have the skills to use them.</p> <p>Capacity building: Large amounts of information (monitoring) need to be created on a local scale.</p> <p>Political barriers: Policies do not support the efforts made by end-users to improve their soil condition. Measurement-based evidence to support this is not recognised.</p> <p>Institutional barriers: Some stakeholders do not trust the new technologies.</p> <p>Financial barriers: The new tools and devices that need to be used are too costly, especially for small farms.</p> <p>Others: Tools can be too complicated to use.</p>
Living lab/ light-houses	Test and evaluate the developed tools in practice.
Outcome	Improved consideration of erosion in land management decision making and planning processes.
Milestones	<p>Milestone 1: Monitoring and modelling tools developed (short to medium term) Tools for monitoring and modeling the whole erosion process (detachment, transport, and deposition), as well as the impact of various land management strategies, are developed.</p> <p>Milestone 2: Tools for erosion control planning (medium term) Tools for erosion control planning are developed to assess trade-offs of land and water management strategies at plot to landscape scale. These tools should be co-designed with and tested by land managers.</p>

SMO 5	Prevent erosion
Key knowledge gap	SMO 5-4 Lack of communication strategies and policy tools regarding effective erosion preventing measures
Sub-knowledge gaps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lack of communication strategies and material to raise awareness (including schools and citizens). 2. Lack of implementation of existing knowledge for erosion prevention by land managers. 3. Lack of integration of knowledge about erosion prevention measures into policy.

Relevant land use sector	<p>Sub knowledge gap 1: all land use sectors</p> <p>Sub knowledge gap 2: mainly agriculture and forestry and nature</p> <p>Sub knowledge gap 3: mainly agriculture and forestry</p>
Regional scope	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Terrace destruction due to large scale industrial farming (e.g. https://www.recare-hub.eu/case-studies/canyoles-river-basin-spain#drivers-and-pressures). • Land use change in sloping areas (abandonment of remote and overuse of easy reachable sites). Information and communication are needed to raise awareness about the effects of these land use changes/choices for erosion risk.
Research actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop awareness-raising material for all stakeholder types and show sustainable alternatives and how they can be profitable. • Develop attractive alternative sustainable narratives (e.g. for regenerative agriculture and organic farming and agroecology). • Provide maps (regional, national) of applicability and relevance of sustainable soil management strategies to mitigate soil erosion tailored to land use sector (agriculture, forestry, nature, industry, mining, urban) to be used for integrating into policy tools.
Output/Results	<p>Developed and disseminated tailored education and communication material to raise awareness of the impact of erosion and erosion prevention measures.</p>
Urgency (short-term: until 2027, mid-term: until 2035, long-term until: 2050)	<p>Short term: To be able to launch awareness-raising efforts as quickly as possible, distribution materials including maps of erosion risk, potential preventative actions, and information showing both negative and positive consequences of management decisions must be developed. Different material needs to be developed for different land uses:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • agriculture: focussing on land managers, but also on industry and agricultural investors and governance that give permits for specific interventions (e.g. development of new large-scale farms on sloping areas). • forestry/nature: erosion risk after wildfire - When should one intervene and when not? <p>Short to medium term: Develop attractive narratives to communicate erosion prevention measures by focussing on local champions. These narratives should be embedded in a larger framework of sustainable land use and development (see e.g. the common land approach).</p>

Synergies	Generally, awareness raising for erosion prevention should be merged with other objectives. When promoting erosion prevention, desertification (SMO1), improving soil health (SMO2,4,5) should also be taken into account. Additionally, it promotes soil literacy (SMO8) and demonstrates why it is important for the rest of the world (SMO7) .
End users	All stakeholders (policymakers, researchers, citizens, land managers and industry) are end-users and will increase their knowledge.
Key stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers: all projects need to make sure knowledge is understandable and usable for end-users; listen to end-users' perception of soil erosion. • Policymakers must disseminate information to all stakeholders that are supposed to work towards preventing erosion. • NGOs should use developed narratives to raise awareness among citizens. • Land managers should indicate which communication formats are effective.
Intermediaries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trusted private and/or public organisations that are regionally based play a key role in connecting the different stakeholder groups. • New narratives, local champions and co-created solutions are key to success. If these principles are followed, awareness-raising will ensue.
Barriers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cultural barriers: Farming communities do not want to change and are not interested in new narratives or new practices. • Capacity building: The knowledge base of the effects of land management is so limited that there is no connection with the knowledge brokers that aim to improve soil health and avoid erosion. • Political barriers: At the level of policy making and governance there is a lack of knowledge of the trade-offs of certain measures for soil erosion (e.g. the subsidy for the implementation of drip irrigation in sloping areas where terraces are destroyed, massive amounts of agro-chemicals are used, with enormous amounts of erosion as a result. Moreover, no water is conserved as there was no irrigation before).
Living lab/ light-houses	Living lab and lighthouses can be excellent examples/stories to tell and explain the narratives for sustainable use of soils.
Outcome	Increased awareness of the consequences of erosion and of options for preventing and restoring degraded soils that are sustainable from a socio-economic and biophysical perspective and better integration into policy.

Milestones	<p>Milestone 1: Awareness-raising material for preventing erosion developed (short term)</p> <p>Awareness-raising material for all stakeholder types and all land use sectors showing sustainable alternatives that are profitable has been developed and disseminated.</p> <p>Milestone 2: New narratives developed and disseminated (short term): Attractive alternative sustainable narratives and examples of best practice are developed in Living Labs together with a wide range of stakeholders.</p> <p>Milestone 3: Provision of erosion hotspot maps to decision makers (medium term) Maps (regional, national) of applicability and relevance of sustainable soil management strategies to mitigate soil erosion, tailored to land use sector (agriculture, forestry, nature, industry, mining) have been provided to and applied by spatial planners across European countries.</p>
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ANNEX VI: DETAILED FACTSHEETS SMO 6 - IMPROVE SOIL STRUCTURE TO ENHANCE HABITAT QUALITY FOR SOIL BIOTA AND CROP

SMO 6	Improve soil structure to enhance habitat quality for soil biota and crop
Key knowledge gap	SMO 6-1 Lack of knowledge about links between soil structure and functional soil biodiversity including processes in the microbiome as well as their effects on crops.
Sub-knowledge gaps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. Lack of knowledge about the links between soil properties (e.g soil type, soil structure), functional soil biodiversity (including processes in the microbiome), plant-soil-biome interactions, soil functions and ecosystem services for different land uses. 6. Lack of knowledge about the links between soil management practices (e.g. amendment, tillage, conservation agriculture, de-sealing) and soil properties and the resulting functions as crop support. 7. Lack of knowledge about management/technical innovations including the use of digitalisation to reduce soil compaction and improve soil structure for the benefit of soil biota and crops.
Relevant land use sector	All sub-knowledge gaps: mainly agriculture and forestry
Regional scope	All regions are concerned by this lack of knowledge.

Research actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify and review existing knowledge. • Develop and support long-term experimental (LTE) research sites, for different land uses, pedo-climatic condition and management options, soil properties, soil functioning and associated ecosystem services in depth. Each site should include an in-depth study of soil physics, chemistry and biodiversity and soil functions as well as the improvement/development of in situ/instant measuring methods (e.g. new captors to follow changes in soil status and functioning).
Output/Results	Overview of site-specific knowledge on the relationship between soil management, soil structure, soil functions, microbial activities and soil/crop health and respective links to land use and management practices.
Urgency (short-term: until 2027, mid-term: until 2035, long-term until: 2050)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short term: Identify relevant practices and technologies in LTE to be described, financed and implemented at a larger scale (e.g. in living labs, "normal field" situations). • Short term: Finance scientific and technological research in LTE on the development and testing of new measuring techniques, support innovations on management practices, new captors and materials. • Long term: Validate LTE results and support management options and new technologies/materials that prevent soil compaction and promote soil health by business and regulation (e.g. included in Common Agricultural Policy).
Synergies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improved soil structure will help to reduce the risk of soil erosion and soil desertification (SMO 1). Therefore, management practices which enhance soil structure also contribute to the prevention of soil desertification and erosion (SMO 1 and 5) and the improvement of water infiltration, supply and fertility. • Improvement of soil biodiversity and soil biological activity is generally linked to the diversification of crops (especially roots), the use of organic fertilisers, and practices that increase organic matter in soils (SMO2).
End users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Land managers: Direct soil users (e.g. land managers, forest managers, gardeners) will benefit from new and tailored knowledge as they will maintain soil structure, improve soil functioning (e.g. nutrient cycling, regulation of pests) and the provision of ecosystem services without increasing inputs as fertilizers

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agrobusiness: agricultural machinery and captors' industries, service providers (e.g. using digital technologies) will benefit from research
Key stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researcher should be involved in investigating and deciphering the links between management practices, soil properties and soil functioning, working in field conditions with land managers. • Researchers and land managers should work together to identify and promote suitable solutions that need to be funded, implemented and driven by policymakers and agrobusiness. • Consumers can also play a role by demanding better management to maintain/improve soil properties and functions in the context of sustainable food production.
Intermediaries	<p>Farm advisors and farm associations can act as intermediaries between researchers and land managers to simplify the outputs of research, promote the solutions, write guidelines and train land managers.</p>
Barriers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Capacity building: Time and money needed for investigating different relevant environments (soil types, climates, land uses, managements practices), developing new measurement technologies and identifying/ implementing win-win situations. • Cultural barriers: Reluctance to change and risk aversion may prevent land managers from adopting appropriate management practices. This means that financial support and/or incentives should be identified and implemented by agrobusiness and policymakers. • Financial barriers: Economic obstacles for the agricultural industry, which profits from a status quo.
Living lab/ light-houses	<p>Living labs are needed to identify (improvements made by land managers) and test management options (proposed by researchers) and new technologies/materials (developed by agrobusiness) in different situations. This can enable dialogue and/or negotiation between stakeholders (including consumers) to identify relevant (efficient, cost-effective and acceptable) changes to be promoted elsewhere. These living labs can also serve to educate new entrants.</p>

Outcome	Improved site-specific knowledge on the links between soil properties, soil functions/services and crop health and improved adapted management options for different land uses to maximise the provision of soil ecosystem services and reduce soil degradation
Milestones	<p>Milestone 1: Identification of management options (medium term) The main management options, materials and technologies that have a beneficial impact on soil properties have been identified across the EU under LTE and agreed on by researchers. This has demonstrated the effectiveness of LTE across the EU and the sites are adequately funded.</p> <p>Milestone 2: Development of guidelines (medium term) Guidelines are available to support the development of the identified options to be implemented and tested in living labs (e.g. 40) as well as in "real" situations. Adequate support is available to develop tailored guidance documents, train new entrants and support changes in the introduction of new capture devices, materials and technologies.</p> <p>Milestone 3: Implementation of practices (long term) A synthesis of successfully implemented measures is produced and disseminated to policy makers and companies to promote/introduce appropriate measures, materials, services, equipment, etc. (e.g. through GAP payments, production contracts).</p>

SMO 6	Improve soil structure to enhance habitat quality for soil biota and crop
Key knowledge gap	SMO 6-2 Lack of harmonised indicators to monitor soil structure and functional biodiversity
Sub-knowledge gaps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lack of harmonised indicators to measure/monitor soil structure and soil biodiversity (species/functionality) and their dynamics, as well as benchmark values for data interpretation. 2. Lack of indicators for functional biodiversity and its links to crop health. 3. Lack of measurement protocols for non-scientists to assess soil for different land uses. 4. Lack of knowledge on the ecological status of industrial sites. 5. Lack of maps of soil-borne disease and parasitic pressure.
Relevant land use sector	<p>Sub-knowledge gap 1: agriculture, forestry, nature and urban</p> <p>Sub-knowledge gap 2: agriculture, forestry, natural mainly</p> <p>Sub-knowledge gap 3: all sectors</p> <p>Sub-knowledge gap 4: industry</p>

	Sub-knowledge gap 5: agriculture, forestry, natural mainly
Regional scope	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All regions are concerned by the development and testing of indicators/benchmarks values to assess and monitor soil structure and functional biodiversity
Research actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop and test indicators to assess soil structure/ soil biodiversity for different soil types (including industrial/urban sites), climate conditions and land management practices and set up interpretation/ benchmark values (i.e. threshold, normal, target values); link results to crop health. Develop and test different measurement protocols for different land uses, soil types, climate conditions and management practices together with end-users (scientists, citizens, land planners etc.). Promote the development of commercial labs and accessible protocols to measure those indicators at low cost. Install monitoring programmes at different scales (EU, national, local) to assess soil/crop status and health. Data should be collected, centralised and accessible to monitor progresses.
Output/Results	A set of site-specific indicators measurable by commercial labs or trained people to report on soil structure and functional biodiversity (and soil status/health in general) and monitor the effect of changes in management practices.
Urgency (short-term: until 2027, mid-term: until 2035, long-term until: 2050)	<p>Short term: Based on the outcomes of SMO6-1 a set of indicators/benchmarks values should be identified and tested (e.g. at EU scale on LUCAS network and/or at country level). Different indicators should be developed and tested to be accessible to different end-users (scientists but also land managers, foresters, citizens, land planners etc.).</p> <p>Medium term: Relevant indicators should be standardised (to lower the costs of investigations) and be implemented in all countries for monitoring soil structure and functional biodiversity (as part of soil health). Communication and training to implement the indicators should be organised for end-users.</p> <p>Long-term: Based on collected data a full information on the status of EU soils is available.</p>

Synergies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The development of easily measurable indicators and their implementation into monitoring schemes will help to detect trends early and thus prevent severe soil degradation such as erosion or desertification (SMO1 and 5) and can be part of the EU global footprint (SMO7) and improve soil literacy (SMO8). • The use of simple protocols to measure the status and functioning of soils helps to involve all soil users and contribute to soil literacy (SMO8)
End users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policymakers should report on the effects of soil policies at national/local scale and to communicate to citizens about the status of soils. • Land managers and advisors, landowners, and managers to follow transitions and changes in management. • Researchers to study soil functioning. • Agrobusiness to set goals in production contracts.
Key stakeholders	<p>All stakeholders (except civil society) should be involved at different steps in the development of indicators as all proposed/measured indicators to ensure their relevance. Benchmark values used to interpret the results of the indicators (e.g. threshold/target values) should also be discussed and negotiated.</p>
Intermediaries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Farm advisors are needed to pass on the information to land managers and landowners and making a link to suitable management practices. • EU and national expert groups should also be involved to understand the meaning of the indicators and push for their use and implementation
Barriers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Institutional barriers: Lack of agreement between experts and end-users when it comes to selecting a set of indicators and agreeing on benchmarks values. No adoption of the set of indicators to monitor soil structure and functional biodiversity at EU/national level (may be linked either to costs or lack of agreement or capacity building). • Capacity building: Depending on the indicator, existing commercial laboratories may not be able to perform the analysis or training may not be available to inform/explain the protocols (required to generalise the indicator). • Financial barriers: High cost of soil analysis.
Living lab/ light-houses	<p>Living labs are needed to develop/test the indicators and discuss benchmarks according to management options in different situations (e.g. soil type, climate). The living labs are also a way to train users in the use of indicators. Those living labs</p>

	can also be complemented by long-term experimental (LTE), EU and national monitoring sites.
Outcome	EU- wide adoption of standardised procedures to monitor soil status/health usable by different land users resulting in large datasets able to inform on trends
Milestones	<p>Milestone 1: Selection of a minimum set of indicators with interpretation values are measured (short term): Soil indicators are developed, harmonised and tested on 40 LTE across EU (financial support needed) and on national/EU monitoring sites. A minimum set of indicators is proposed together with first benchmark/interpretation values.</p> <p>Milestone 2: Scaling up the use of indicators (medium term): Guidelines are available to support the development, training and use of the identified set of indicators in living labs but also in "real" situations. This means that adequate support is available to develop guidance documents, train new entrants and test indicators. Based on the results, proper benchmarks/interpretation values are defined and used across EU.</p> <p>Milestone 3: Implementation (medium/long term): A synthesis is made and communicate to policymakers and business so they can promote/impose relevant indicators and benchmarks in monitoring policies (e.g. through CAP payments, production contracts)</p>

SMO 6	Improve soil structure to enhance habitat quality for soil biota and crop
Key knowledge gap	SMO 6-3 Lack of management innovations and associated socio-economic research including cost-benefits for the uptake of management measures to improve soil structure and biota
Sub-knowledge gaps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lack of management innovations including the use of digitalisation to reduce soil compaction and improve soil structure for the benefit of soil biota and crops. 2. Lack of knowledge on the design of improved field arrangements and landscape elements to avoid compaction and improve soil structure. 3. Lack of economic research, such as cost-benefit analyses to evaluate the significance of soil/plant health and related ecosystem services, in conjunction with suitable management techniques in various land uses. 4. Lack of socio-economic research to identify potential barriers to adapting new management practices.

Relevant land use sector	All sub-knowledge gaps: mainly agriculture and forestry
Regional scope	All regions are concerned by this lack of knowledge as soils, crops and management differ across EU and land uses.
Research actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify barriers to adapting management and developing guidelines and decision support tools with a focus on socio-economic factors for land managers based on the results from long-term experiments and living labs to share and communicate good practices. • Identify and support key actions and innovations (i.e. management practices for adapted tillage and traffic, new and smart technologies for soil tillage, crop/timber harvest, sealing/de-sealing) to be tested and adapted in living labs across EU. • Identify and communicate success stories (e.g. via lighthouses) to showcase the benefits of soil health for soil managers incomes and for society. • Develop training initiatives and soil ambassadors to help land managers and soil users to adopt new management practices and apply new technologies improving soil structure. • Implement financial support to help transition, such as market solutions, incentives, insurances or labels.
Output/Results	Tailored guidelines, decision support tools and trainings for land managers to improve soil structure and functional biodiversity and soil and crop health in general.
Urgency (short-term: until 2027, mid-term: until 2035, long-term until: 2050)	<p>Short term: Conduct economical/sociological/technological research studies to assess the benefits of improving soil properties regarding the costs of changing management practices and technologies, for different land uses together with the reluctance to changes using in long-term experiments (LTE).</p> <p>Medium term: Summarise the outcomes of the studies and identify cost-effective management options, technologies and proper ways to communicate on how to change management practices. Test the identified options in living labs and "real" field situations to generalise the first conclusions.</p> <p>Medium/long term: Based on the results, define the needed incentives, market instruments and technical/communication support that needs to be implemented.</p>

Synergies	As soil structure and soil biodiversity are linked to soil erosion, desertification and organic matter content, supporting the transition to more sustainable systems by overcoming technological, social and financial barriers will also contribute to reducing desertification (SMO1), conserving soil organic carbon stocks (SMO2) and preventing erosion (SMO5) as well as preventing floods and providing better water infiltration, supply and balance in the face of climate change (with stormwater events and droughts).
End users	Land managers, agrobusinesses, and policymakers will be the major end users to understand how the changes in management techniques will affect production costs and what sort of incentives should be provided to aid and promote transition. The study will also put forth solutions to the soil users' and managers' resistance to change.
Key stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers should design and conduct the research studies with land managers in living labs. The results will be used by policymakers and agrobusinesses to develop incentives, market contracts or labels to promote the implementation of suitable management practices. • Businesses need to develop solutions for lighter machinery and smart tillage and trafficking, in collaboration with researchers and land manager.
Intermediaries	Farm advisors, farm associations and networks with a large access to actors or specific EU and national expert groups will translate the results to policymakers and agrobusinesses.
Barriers	<p>The following barriers generally apply to changing and adopting new management practices:</p> <p>Cultural barriers: Reluctance of land managers to change traditional practices.</p> <p>Capacity building: Lack of knowledge/training and information for land managers on labour/material needs, new technologies (incl. smart machinery) as well as costs and benefits and potential savings.</p> <p>Financial barriers: Fear of losing money and lack of money to invest among farmers and land managers. And the economic obstacles for the agricultural industry, which profits from an "unchanged" situation.</p>

	<p>Political barriers: The use of smart farming, lighter machinery and robots is a solution to reduce compaction. There are still legal ambiguities for the use of unmanned vehicles. Legal regulations on data ownership and management are not yet in place either.</p>
Living lab/ light-houses	<p>Living labs are the place where dialogue and/or negotiation between actors (including consumers) will occur to identify relevant (efficient, cost-effective and acceptable) changes to be promoted. These living labs can also serve as a showcase to convince newcomers with "real" life results.</p>
Outcome	<p>Wide acceptance and adoption of management practices to improve soil and crop health due to proper incentives, market contracts, labels and identification of barriers.</p>
Milestones	<p>Milestone 1: Develop references on costs and social factors linked to the transition to more sustainable systems that support soil structure and health (short term) Develop economical/ sociological/technological research studies to assess the benefits of improving soil properties regarding the costs of changing management practices, for different land uses together with the identification of reluctance to changes (in LTE).</p> <p>Milestone 2: Expand implementation and testing (medium term) Synthesise the outcomes of the studies and identify cost-effective management options and ways to communicate on how/why to change land management (e.g. benefits of changing in terms of incomes, labour, costs for inputs, impacts on soil/crop health). Implement and test the identified options on living labs and "real" field situations to build evidence and derive recommendations.</p> <p>Milestone 3: Build foundations in policy and business to implement new managements practices (medium/long term) Based on the results of living labs and "real" field situations define the needed incentives, market instruments and further support (including communication, training, technical and economical) to promote cost-effective management options for improve soil structure and soil health in general.</p>

ANNEX VII: DETAILED FACTSHEETS SMO 7 - REDUCE THE EU GLOBAL FOOTPRINT ON SOILS

SMO 7	Reduce the EU global footprint on soils
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Key knowledge gap	SMO 7-1: Lack of global soil footprint definitions, problem statements, clear research questions, and, building on those, clear science-based metrics and indicator standards
Sub-knowledge gaps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lack of knowledge on the impacts of European consumption, trade, production, European and international policies on soil health deterioration and related environmental and socio-economic challenges outside Europe. 2. Lack of knowledge on the feedback loops of soil degradation outside Europe on global social security, food security, human health. 3. Insufficient understanding of potential time lags between measures taken in Europe (consumption and production conditions) and impact outside Europe. 4. Lack of definition of soil footprint (incl. ontologies), indicators, baselines, thresholds. and standards (going beyond land consumption). 5. Lack of concepts (metrics/benchmarks) for comparing regions in terms of the relative impacts on soil and soil health of consumption and use of resources. 6. Lack of sufficient consideration of soil in the Global Footprint Standards²
Relevant land use sector	Sub knowledge gap 1-5: all sectors in-and outside of Europe
Regional scope	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is a need to differentiate in terms of world regions: different world regions are differently affected by European consumption patterns, trade regulations and policies. Furthermore, there is a need to account for different scales when calculating a footprint on soils (EU, national, regional, local, per practice, per product etc.) This is reflected in the sub knowledge gap 1 and 5.
Research actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Define clear research questions and problem statements to clarify the aim of having an EU soil footprint. • Develop a holistic definition (incl. ontologies), indicators, baseline and standards for a global footprint on soils/soil health. • Develop approaches to conduct systems analyses spatially linking consumption and production and considering spatial-temporal scales in system boundaries inside EU to soil health outside EU. • Conduct research to better understand the impacts of soil degradation on social security, food security, and human health.

² https://www.footprintnetwork.org/content/images/uploads/Ecological_Footprint_Standards_2009.pdf

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Determine range of safe operability (of biomass, timber, food production) and thresholds for points of no return. • Develop a proposal to include soil in the Global Footprint metrics.
Output/Results	Agreed set of indicators and standards for the global soil health impacts of EU activities
Urgency (short-term: until 2027, mid-term: until 2035, long-term until: 2050)	<p>Short term: Define clear research questions and problem statements. Agree on definitions, metrics, and indicators within Europe. Create scientific support for these definitions, metrics and indicators and coordinate indicator selection between Mission Objectives to maximise monitoring efficiency.</p> <p>Medium term: Derive international agreements on definitions, metrics, and indicators.</p> <p>Long term: Implementation of the global soil footprint.</p>
Synergies	Metrics and indicators related to soil footprint are useful e.g. for mapping areas with drought and desertification risks (SMO 1), and the data gathered provides new avenues for soil-related meta analyses of practices, consumption patterns, and comprehensive issue evaluations (all SMOs). Such indicators (and monitoring) will also contribute soil literacy (SMO8).
End users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data authorities and administrations in charge of reporting will include the identified indicators and standards in the reporting on the global soil footprint. • Policymakers may include such indicators in regulations (informed decision making). • Scientists will profit from standardised definitions, indicators and methods and broadly collected data/information.
Key stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agronomists, forestry experts, soil scientists, mining experts, economists, trade specialists and foresight experts as well as authorities and administrations dealing with monitoring and reporting at the international level and policymakers from other world regions should be involved in the process of identifying appropriate indicators and standards.
Intermediaries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European research initiatives will pass the results/proposals to expert groups that can be intermediaries between research and authorities, administrations, and businesses. • Definition and choice of indicators etc. need to be a co-development process and should be supported by central bodies (e.g. the EU in form of HE calls). In

	<p>the following, progress needs to be maintained through ongoing public discussions. This could e.g. be maintained by a standing committee on global footprints on soils.</p>
Barriers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Capacity-building barrier: Complexity of the topic, can only be solved in an interdisciplinary systems approach. • Financial barriers: Indicator development is costly - many experts and actors need to discuss diverse related issues and coordinate those on a holistic level; hence, it is time and labour intensive. • Institutional barrier: Current absence of institutions related to a global footprint on soils. This is a completely new topic, so there is basically no previous knowledge present within the 'soil' field (experience in other fields can help); ignorance/lack of awareness from economists and trade experts regarding soil health issues. • Barriers related to societal values: implementing a system of global footprint assessment requires the insight that concern about soil health and human living conditions outside Europe is as relevant as soil health and human living conditions within Europe.
Living lab/ light-houses	None
Outcome	Wide implementation of standardised indicators for the global soil health impacts of EU activities in monitoring and reporting systems across economic/soil use sectors
Milestones	<p>Milestone 1: Overview and suitability assessment on existing indicators established (short term) Research projects (i.e. calls to be launched) on the identification and definitions of relevant metrics and indicators are in place. Based on existing literature and on coming results from the projects possible indicators are identified, tested, and discussed with experts and stakeholders/actors.</p> <p>Milestone 2: Agreement on definitions, metrics, indicators, and standards (medium term) A proposal for an agreement on definitions, metrics, indicators, and standards is drafted and a procedure for negotiating on the proposal established among relevant authorities. As the final product, an agreement is reached on definitions, metrics, indicators, thresholds, baselines and standards.</p>

	Milestone 3: Regional adaptations of definitions and indicators (long term) Finance research projects on the regional adaptation of definitions and indicators e.g. through Horizon Europe projects.
SMO 7	Reduce the EU global footprint on soils
Key knowledge gap	SMO 7-2: Lack of suitable data and monitoring systems for assessing the EU global soil footprint
Sub-knowledge gaps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Insufficient systemic understanding of qualitative and quantitative aspects of the global footprint linking production and consumption activities (telecoupling) inside the EU to soil health outside EU. 2. Lack of knowledge on which existing databases are useful for soil footprint calculations (including present land and soil use and soil quality/health). 3. Lack of monitoring of indicators related to the EU global footprint on soils (see SMO 7-1).
Relevant land use sector	Sub knowledge gap 1-3: all sectors
Regional scope	Spatial differentiation across world regions is needed. Due to the novelty of the topic, an individual assessment is necessary to define regional scope specific to land-use sectors (See also SMO7-1)
Research actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify and analyse suitable existing data sources for soil quality and resource flows. • Develop methods/approaches to holistically assess the global footprint including soil health dynamics. • Elaborate on i) land use and management-based monitoring systems including soil health (quality) data, ii) environmental and natural resource use parameters in economic monitoring and accounting.
Output/Results	Overview of data sources and monitoring protocols agreed upon across the EU Member States to monitor soil global footprint.
Urgency (short-term: until 2027, mid-term: until 2035, long-term until: 2050)	<p>Short term: Agree on data sources and monitoring systems in Europe.</p> <p>Medium term: Derive international agreement on data and monitoring systems, if needed collect new data (e.g. based on monitoring programmes).</p> <p>Long term: Evaluate (and adapt if necessary) the indicators and monitoring processes to improve quality and efficiency.</p>

Synergies	The monitoring of the EU soil footprint should be coordinated with the monitoring of SMO 1 to 6, will help to conduct holistic problem analyses and solution finding (all SMOs). The monitoring of the footprint will directly contribute to an increase in soil literacy (SMO8).
End users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Authorities and administrations commissioned with the reporting on the global soil footprint will be able to use best data sources and agreed monitoring protocols. • Policymakers can use data to evaluate the impact of policies in and outside of the EU. • The interested public and consumers can use data basis for putting targeted pressure on policymakers. • Industries are enabled to assess the impacts of their activities and to eventually reduce it.
Key stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experts and scientists from all soil-use sectors and disciplines e.g. agronomists, forestry experts, soil scientists, mining experts, economists, trade specialists, foresight experts, industry experts, architects, authorities and administrations need to agree on data sources and monitoring protocols.
Intermediaries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU and global networks are intermediaries between researchers and the broader public, including practitioners and citizens. They collate data and monitoring results, process and interpret them. • European research initiatives improve our systemic understanding of qualitative and quantitative aspects of the global footprint, define indicators, thresholds and monitoring protocols. They interpret and share their information within the field, with policymakers and the interested public. • UN and national data authorities collect data and examine monitoring processes.
Barriers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Capacity-building barriers: A global EU footprint for soils covers many topics across all soil and land-use sectors. The diversity of topics, even within specific sectors, is enormous, and many times it will be necessary for indicators to be policy, process, or product-specific. While the level of detail for this will be discussed within SMO 7 (1), it is obvious that the indicators and protocols for calculating the Footprint will be diverse and therefore complex and labour-intensive. In the long term, efficiency can be increased by adapting and reducing the indicators (see above under "Urgency").

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Financial barriers: Due to the complexity and the large number of indicators, monitoring could be very costly.
Living lab/ light-houses	Since the global footprint is about telecoupling between activities in Europe and impacts outside Europe there is no obvious way of addressing the research in Living Labs given their current definitions.
Outcome	Established monitoring and reporting systems for all land use sectors, including monitoring of the global soil footprint originating from specific regions (inside or outside the EU), land use sectors, practices, products or policies.
Milestones	<p>Milestone 1: R&I projects implemented on identifying data, needs and gaps (short term) Project(s) are implemented to identify suitable monitoring schemes/protocols and assess available and relevant data stocks, data gaps and needs.</p> <p>Milestone 2: Overview and suitability assessment on existing data and monitoring schemes (short term) Based on the outcome of the projects, an in-depth suitability assessment is made to increase efficiency. An evaluation of the costs and potential methods for gathering additional data is conducted for newly required data.</p> <p>Milestone 3: Agreement on data use and monitoring (medium term) A proposal for an agreement on data use and monitoring is drafted and a procedure for negotiating on the proposal established among relevant authorities. As final product an agreement on data use and monitoring is made.</p>

SMO 7	Reduce the EU global footprint on soils
Key knowledge gap	SMO 7-3: Lack of awareness about the importance of the global soil footprint for living conditions outside Europe and communication of practical examples.
Sub-knowledge gaps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Lacking awareness about and recognition of the importance of the global soil footprint for living conditions outside Europe Lack of practical examples demonstrating the telecoupling between European activities and soil health outside Europe Lack of simulation/foresight models addressing telecoupling and soil health implications of biomass and food trade on soil health as showcases and scenarios
Relevant land use sector	Sub knowledge gap 1-5: all sectors

Regional scope	The mechanisms related to the global soil footprint are different across world regions. These need to be better identified.
Research actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify and establish networks/coalitions to foster collaboration and gather/exchange knowledge at EU/global level on global soil health. • Develop campaigns to illustrate impacts on global soil footprint (based on consumption, management impacts, policy impacts, etc.). • Develop foresight scenarios of future consumption - production patterns and simulation models i) on global soil health impacts of EU activities including resource flows; ii) to up-and downscale between global resource flows and local soil management and soil quality.
Output/Results	Soil footprint assessments, scenarios/simulation models and an overview of resource-efficient practices to established awareness of the linkages between consumption in Europe and soil health outside Europe.
Urgency (short-term: until 2027, mid-term: until 2035, long-term until: 2050)	<p>Short term: Develop a strategy to inform stakeholders about the global linkages between domestic consumption and international impacts on soil health. Establish campaigns on global footprint education.</p> <p>Medium term: Develop models and foresight scenarios</p> <p>Long term: Maintain, update, and improve models and foresight scenarios and their dissemination. Establish stakeholder-inclusive problem solution pathways.</p>
Synergies	Awareness rising on the importance of the global soil footprint will also contribute to SMO 8.
End users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Civil society & citizens will have better knowledge and understanding of the impacts of their own consumption and actions. • Organisations and authorities dealing with education at formal and informal levels can use the developed materials and models to highlight and illustrate impacts on global soil footprint • Industry and business will have better knowledge of the impact of their production, they can optimise practices and products, and they can advertise good practice and products.
Key stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Civil society and public should be involved in citizen science approaches and suitable awareness-raising campaigns.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Industry and business should be involved in co-development approaches and suitable awareness-raising campaigns that propose concrete, situation-specific improvements.
Intermediaries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU networks with a large access to actors disseminate information. • European research initiative like EJP Soil, JRC perform and support citizen science and co-creational research.
Barriers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Others: Risk of intransparency of model results because of their complexity • Capacity building: Limited time and perceptive capacities of stakeholders could be a limiting factor with regard to the other SMOs. Hence, awareness creation should be prioritised since people cannot be aware of everything at the same time. Need for targeted awareness campaigns (Question to be answered: who needs to be aware of what?)
Living lab/ light-houses	None
Outcome	Strengthened understanding of impacts of EU activities on global soil footprint and increased willingness of consumers and industry to modify their strategy and actions towards more sustainable consumption/production.
Milestones	<p>Milestone 1: Relevant actors and needs identified (short term) All relevant actors from all sectors are identified and it is determined "who should be aware of what".</p> <p>Milestone 2: Develop public 'ongoing' discussion platforms (e.g. in LLs& LHs) (short to medium term)</p> <p>Platforms to mainstream the global footprint, to disseminate practical examples, raise awareness and keep discussion on the global footprint on soils ongoing are established.</p>

SMO 7	Reduce the EU global footprint on soils
Key knowledge gap	SMO 7-4: Lack of mainstreaming of the global soil footprint in EU policies
Sub-knowledge gaps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lack of awareness about and recognition of the importance of the global soil footprint and soil health concerns in national and international policy debates (e.g. EU/UN activities). 2. Lack of knowledge on the impact of EU and global policies (incl. trade and market) on the EU's global soil footprint and instruments/measures to reduce trade-offs and negative impacts. 3. Lack of consideration of soil footprint concerns in national and international policies and trade agreements.
Relevant land use sector	Sub knowledge gap 1-3: all sectors
Regional scope	There is no specific regional scope.
Research actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assess the impact of EU and global policies (incl. trade and market) on the EU's global soil footprint. • Include indicators for global footprint assessment in ex-ante impact assessment of agricultural, environmental, fiscal policies etc. • Explore new (holistic) policy instruments/mechanisms to reduce trade-offs and negative impacts on global soil footprint. • Identify sectors, agents. and relevant policies (in the EU) that affect soil health inside and outside the EU. • Develop an overview of resource-efficient and low-impact practices (regarding soil health). • Consider the diverse and variable range of land uses in production systems in policy objectives, measures, legislation and certification systems. • Establish supportive policies for resource-efficient practices and re-use of old materials.
Output/Results	Overview of policy impact in global soil footprint, mitigation strategies to reduce negative impacts and trade-offs and establishment of policy pathways that ensures the support of sustainable practices and prevention of unsustainable practices.

<p>Urgency (short-term: until 2027, mid-term: until 2035, long-term until: 2050)</p>	<p>Short term: Establish awareness of the problem across all policy sectors and levels and identify key policy fields for which a global soil footprint assessment is appropriate.</p> <p>Short term: Make the global soil footprint assessment a regular part of international discussions and negotiations.</p> <p>Medium term: integrate the global footprint assessment into the regular policy assessment procedure.</p>
<p>Synergies</p>	<p>Integration of EU soil footprint standards across all policy sectors will increase awareness on the impact of soil use (SMO8). The reduction of the soil footprint comes along with increased soil health and thus contributes to all other SMOs.</p>
<p>End users</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policymakers at EU and national levels dealing with international policies and with all policies relevant for land and soil health will be able to mainstream the impact of EU policies on the EU footprint
<p>Key stakeholders</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policymakers from different policy fields engage in co-creational research, get informed and mainstream the global footprint on soils within political decision making. • Researchers actively include policymakers and seeks bilateral exchange for improving relevance of results, educate policymakers, increase awareness and promoting the global footprint on soils. • Civil society representatives formulate concrete demands and increase public pressure on policymakers to efficiently reduce the EU global footprint on soils. • Businesses promote the development of more sustainable practices and support the development of sustainability conducive policies and subsidies.
<p>Intermediaries</p>	<p>Policy consultants, research institutes dealing with global assessments and NGOs should pass on the results to national and EU policy maker.</p>
<p>Barriers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Capacity building: to include EU soil footprint into all sectors might increase the administrative burden. • Financial barriers: businesses/practitioners may be negatively affected if they need to consider a global footprint and to adapt their practices accordingly (e.g. replace soy imports, reduce animal production, adapt architecture to more sustainable building materials, industries need to follow up on their supply chains, etc.).
<p>Living lab/ light-houses</p>	<p>None</p>

Outcome	Global soil footprint is adequately considered in relevant policies and political discussions.
Milestones	<p>Milestone 1: R&I projects assessing the impact of policies on the global footprint of soils (short term) Projects to assess the policy impacts on the soil footprint are in place and solutions including hot spots for improvement identified.</p> <p>Milestone 2: Consistency analysis with policy cycle conducted and procedure developed (medium term) Procedure and indicators on global soil footprint are established and used at each step of the policy cycle: objective setting, instrument development, ex-ante assessment, monitoring, ex-post assessment.</p> <p>Milestone 3: Test cases of global soil footprint assessment in policy assessment conducted and lessons learned (medium term) Illustrative policy examples are available in which the global soil footprint was assessed in all steps of the policy cycle and taken into consideration for decision making.</p>

ANNEX VIII: DETAILED FACTSHEETS SMO8 - INCREASE SOIL LITERACY IN SOCIETY

SMO 8	Increase soil literacy in society
Key knowledge gap	SMO 8-1 Lack of insight into the level of awareness, knowledge of soil services and benefits, and concerns of different stakeholders
Sub-knowledge gaps	<p>8. Lack of understanding and assessment on the level of awareness on the significance on soil health for citizens and other stakeholder groups such as soil and land managers, policymakers, business etc.</p> <p>9. Lack of insights into the knowledge on soil services (provided by different soil types) for citizens and key stakeholders</p> <p>10. Lack of insight into current practices, values and concerns of key stakeholders and citizens</p> <p>11. Lack of knowledge about the wider educational, social and environmental impact of co-created soil health solutions</p>
Relevant land use sector	<p>Sub-knowledge gap 1: Urban, Agri, Forestry, Industry</p> <p>Sub-knowledge gap 2-4: All sectors</p>
Regional scope	None

Research actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify the key stakeholders, their role, awareness, and communication channels at different levels. • Develop and implement a methodology to gain insights into citizens' and key stakeholders' knowledge about soil services and benefits. • Identify current channels, practices, values and concerns of key stakeholder groups and citizens to inform education programmes. • Analyse how new knowledge about soil health can be fed into identified channels (using effective means/processes). • Exploring ways to share relevant knowledge (local/national or solution-oriented) with different actors. Solution-oriented knowledge.
Output/Results	Database/Reports on i) Key stakeholder groups and their soil-related awareness (baseline), ii) current practices, values and concerns of key stakeholder groups and citizens, iii) successful/effective ways and means of knowledge transfer for specific stakeholders, and iv) processes for identifying priorities for the need for new knowledge.
Urgency (short-term: until 2027, mid-term: until 2035, long-term until: 2050)	<p>Short term: Identify key soil stakeholder groups</p> <p>Short term: Determine the degree of knowledge, practices, beliefs, and concerns important stakeholders have regarding soil, as well as effective ways of exchanging and updating knowledge. Additionally, consider which actors can help to assist such a process.</p>
Synergies	Identifying the current soil awareness and current practices, values and concerns of citizens and key stakeholder groups is in synergy with SMO1, SMO2, SMO3, SMO4, SMO5 and SMO6 as information is collected and shared on what is being done, where it is being done and what contributes to improving soil health
End users	<p>Policymakers (national and regional governmental organisations) will increase their efficiency and effectiveness when it comes to their actions toward soil literacy and the integration thereof into their current practices.</p> <p>Civil society and NGOs, farm advisory services etc. will increase their efficiency/effectiveness in terms of their ground-building interventions or the integration of these interventions into their current practices.</p>
Key stakeholders	Policymakers should be involved as key facilitators in identifying stakeholders' awareness of the soil and current practices, values and concerns. They must

	<p>therefore work closely with researchers, who should conduct the research and consolidate the results.</p> <p>Civil society, land managers/landowners and businesses should be involved as co-creators of relevant knowledge and, in the context of living labs, as future users.</p>
Intermediaries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Different (inter)national NGOs with a large member base can be intermediaries between civil society and policymakers by reaching out to their members. • At national level: Organisations with a larger (membership) base, such as horticultural organisations, which often publish their own magazines that have a wide reach. • Policy networks will be able to communicate the practices, beliefs, and issues that stakeholders have identified as well as their understanding of the situation.
Barriers	<p>Cultural barriers: Low level of attention that society in general and institutions pay to soil and the subsoil.</p> <p>Financial barriers: Once the results of the research are available, they must be implemented. The challenge in this situation is that financing is necessary for the study results to be implemented into organisational policies and operations (this is particularly relevant for policymakers and business).</p> <p>Institutional barriers: The right capacities for implementation (also linked to the culture of the country, sector and organisation) are not always in place. Lack of clarity on who is responsible for what and lack of understanding of the soil/subsoil issue.</p> <p>Political barriers: Lack of alignment with different policy agendas (climate, biodiversity, energy, etc. with soil)</p> <p>Other: The obstacle is not always the lack of knowledge itself, but the process of how the right knowledge reaches the right stakeholders at the right level of knowledge (e.g. new scientific knowledge takes time to reach the policy space).</p> <p>If open data is not available in an organised form, knowledge creation and support for decision-making will be limited.</p>
Living lab/ light-houses	<p>The research is already described in the actions to address the knowledge gaps:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interviews, focus groups, surveys, community workshops can all be used as a methodology to get insight in the role, awareness level, and communication channels at different levels.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Co-develop a serious game and use this to test/get insight into the knowledge of citizens and key stakeholders on soil services (executing the game is used to gather empirical data and is also a method to boost soil literacy).
Outcome	Better understanding of awareness, and practices, values and concerns of citizens and key stakeholders on the societal role and value of soil in the EU.
Milestones	<p>Milestone 1: Mapping of key stakeholder groups across the EU (short term) Building on existing work and databases, a mapping of key stakeholders active in each land use sector in the EU has been conducted.</p> <p>Milestone 2: Processes and practices to reach actors are assessed (short term): With priority to a few selected stakeholder groups, processes and practices are assessed for successful awareness raising, knowledge transfer and co-learning. These three levels of engagement and learning better reflect the possibilities of knowledge transfer.</p> <p>Milestone 3: Methodology developed to get insight into current soil services knowledge (short term) Develop a methodology to get insight into citizens and key stakeholders' knowledge on soil services.</p> <p>Milestone 4: Overview of stakeholder practices, values and concerns (short term) Insight in the current practices, values and concerns of key stakeholders and citizens are gathered.</p>

SMO 8	Increase soil literacy in society
Key knowledge gap	SMO 8-2 Lack of effective soil health education and trainings
Sub-knowledge gaps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of effective soil health education optimised for different education levels. Lack of tailored training offered to specific stakeholder groups. Lack of knowledge about the effectiveness of and potential improvements to existing school curricula of the different educational levels.
Relevant land use sector	All sub-knowledge gaps: all sectors
Regional scope	None

Research actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Co-develop effective education programmes, toolkits, and engagement measures for different education levels together with targeted stakeholders and Members States (and thereby addressing stakeholder needs but also local opportunities and solutions). • Enhance co-creation and multidirectional learning, e.g. in communities of practice, also considering demonstration of good practices and hands-on education. • Explore the opportunities for lifelong learning and digitalisation for putting new soil science/soil health knowledge to be accessible for different actor groups. • Assess the current state of soil education in school curricula at all levels and monitor changes. • Co-develop soil literacy courses to be taught as part of relevant degrees (agronomy, environmental sciences, environmental engineering etc.) e.g. for universities.
Output/Results	Assessment report of the state of soil-related education and training in the EU and a “best of” resources repository on soil education and soil trainings for different stakeholder groups and scales.
Urgency (short-term: until 2027, mid-term: until 2035, long-term until: 2050)	<p>Short term: Assess the current state of soil education in school curricula at all levels (vocational schools/practical application, high school, applied science, university).</p> <p>Medium term: Based on the short-term assessment, develop education programmes for different education levels.</p> <p>Medium term: Develop tailored soil health training for targeted stakeholder groups.</p>
Synergies	Developing module-based education programmes and soil health trainings will improve soil health knowledge amongst the stakeholders. Therefore, stakeholders will better understand their soil and the best management practices that can be applied to improve soil health: in synergy with the other seven mission objectives.
End users	Civil society is the end-user of education programmes. Land managers, policymakers, researchers and businesses are the end-users of targeted soil health training.

Key stakeholders	<p>Assess the current status of soil health education and develop effective education programmes and dedicated soil health trainings for different education levels, which should involve:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers: From a science/data perspective, monitoring and learning and the development of the programme. • Land managers: Training programmes for farmers, or other sector organisations. • Business: Professional training organisations, intra- and interorganisational training programmes. • Other: Educational institutions dealing with relevant sectors for both middle school, higher education and universities.
Intermediaries	<p>Policymakers (ministries and regional authorities) dealing with education play a pivotal role in the stimulation of educational programmes and their monitoring and development. They will have to work closely with researchers, land managers, businesses, and educational institutions to develop education programmes and soil health trainings tailored to end-users.</p> <p>Agricultural, forestry, gardening associations can also integrate elements of the educational and training programmes developed in their work/communities or practices etc.</p>
Barriers	<p>Financial barriers: High investment costs can be a barrier. Setting up new curricula and developing soil health trainings is costly, especially when they need to be applied at different educational levels. Public investments are needed here.</p> <p>Cultural barriers: Reluctance to change current curricula may be an obstacle. Including soil health in education programmes means that it may have to replace other educational programmes. Soil health may not be considered as important enough to replace another educational programme.</p>
Living lab/ light-houses	<p>The setting up and the maintenance of Living labs can be used in the soil health trainings for stakeholders working with different soil type.</p> <p>Knowledge gained from living labs can also be implemented in the education programmes to raise awareness on soil health.</p>
Outcome	<p>Wide integration of soil health in educational curricula at all levels to enable behavioural change.</p>

Milestones	<p>Milestone 1: Soil education evaluation (short term) Current state of soil education in school curricula at all education levels (vocational schools/practical application, high school, applied science, university) is assessed. The focus is on the missing components of the soil formation to see what else can be implemented.</p> <p>Milestone 2: Tailored and effective education programmes (medium term) Tailored education programmes for all education levels are developed, based on findings from Milestone 1.</p> <p>Milestone 3: Soil health awareness monitoring (long term) A system is in place to monitor changes in soil health awareness and the impact this may have on behavioural change.</p>
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SMO 8	Increase soil literacy in society
Key knowledge gap	SMO 8-3 Lack of effective and appropriate communication strategies and methods to enhance soil literacy
Sub-knowledge gaps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lack of effective communication methods tailored to stakeholder values, practices and needs and channels for soil (services, health issues, etc.). 2. Lack of clear definitions and ontologies for “soil health” and SMOs (e.g. land degradation, soil sealing, soil footprint) to create a common understanding. 3. Lack of policy and communication tools for policymakers to enhance soil literacy.
Relevant land use sector	All sub-knowledge gaps: all sectors
Regional scope	None
Research actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop a transparent communication platform and system. Incorporating both communication channels and methodologies (such as storytelling). • Identify and assess good examples and solutions for knowledge transfers. • Identify and train Mission Ambassadors to increase awareness at the local level and enhance the knowledge of soil-related activists. • Develop a common language. • Stimulate interactions between different stakeholders interested e.g. in different soil types/working at different soil scales as part of the living labs.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developing methods of stakeholder involvement addressing co-design, co-implementation and co-assessment (citizen science) of both problems and solutions. • Develop communication tools in close cooperation with key stakeholders and citizens to raise awareness on soil health and best management practices to inform citizens, planners, politicians and other stakeholder on the benefits provided by soils.
Output/Results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Established (digital) hubs and networks targeting different stakeholders and scales (e.g. national level), provide the best communication on soils and create a forum for knowledge exchange. • Methodologies that allow for co-design, co-implementation and co-assessment to address challenges and derive solutions. • A policy framework that enables the enhancement of soil literacy (including policy instruments, such as guidelines, subsidies and institutional frameworks/ infrastructure)
Urgency (short-term: until 2027, mid-term: until 2035, long-term until: 2050)	<p>Short term: Develop a common language that will be used by the soil ambassadors and within the national hubs so that all stakeholders are able to communicate effectively.</p> <p>Short term: Set up national soil ambassador networks across all EU Member States. The soil ambassadors should be active at a local level to enhance the knowledge of soil-related activists.</p> <p>Medium term: Create digital hubs (e.g. at national level) that bring together key stakeholders and provide a forum for soil health knowledge exchange. These hubs should be transparent, well-known among all stakeholders and have effective communication to ensure that the hubs outlive individual soil management projects.</p>
Synergies	All SMOs benefit from a common language, common definitions and tailored communication methods.
End users	In theory, the end-users are all stakeholder groups. However, there will be different levels of application/practice: Science, Strategy, Policy, Projects/Practice. It is very important to keep these different contexts in mind when identifying the end-users to make sure that content and form are in line with the end-user practice and knowledge.

	<p>Policymakers will have a well-informed network to discuss their thoughts and issues when implementing new national/regional strategies and policies.</p> <p>Researchers, land managers, civil society and business will have national platforms and networks in which they can share their insights and knowledge and from which they can learn from each other.</p>
Key stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For the development of tools, methods and platform, policymakers, civil society, business, and others (consultancy, software production) should be involved. • Policymakers, civil society, researchers and land managers should be involved in the development of a common language and in the design of stakeholder interactions.
Intermediaries	Intermediaries (such as large international networks) between policymakers, researchers, business, and others (consultancy, software production), civil society and land managers and landowners will be needed to share awareness of the created hubs.
Barriers	<p>Institutional barriers: Regularly changing networks (both on the individual level (people moving to new positions) and on larger (national) levels).</p> <p>Financial barriers: Lack of budget (for individual projects) to keep national communication hubs/platforms online as well as to keep networks connected are possible barriers when looking at the long term.</p>
Living lab/ light-houses	All living labs and lighthouse contribute to this knowledge gap as they stimulate interactions between stakeholders, stimulate stakeholder involvement in co-designing living labs and help raise awareness on soil health issues. These sites can also help to define and test the messages and involve civil society.
Outcome	Improved awareness of the societal role and value of soils and involvement of citizens, private and societal stakeholder in soil and land-related issues at all levels (local, regional, national, international) and integration of "Enhancing soil literacy" as an objective and part of relevant national and integrated policies.
Milestones	<p>Milestone 1: Develop policy and communication tools (short term) Develop policy and communication tools for EU member states in close cooperation with key stakeholders and citizens.</p> <p>Milestone 2: Stimulate stakeholder interaction and involvement (short term) Stimulate interactions between different stakeholders interested in different soil</p>

types/working at different soil scales -as part of the Living Labs that will be developed. Further, develop methods of stakeholder involvement addressing co-design, co-implementation, and co-assessment (citizen science) of both problems and solutions.

Milestone 3: Develop a common language (short term) Develop a common language to ensure that all stakeholders are able to share information and understand each other.

Milestone 4: Mission Ambassadors (short term) Identify and train Mission Ambassadors to increase awareness at the local level and enhance the knowledge of soil-related activists.

Milestone 5: Develop communication hubs (medium term) Develop targeted communication platforms and systems (hubs) for different stakeholders and at different levels, incorporating both communication channels and methods to enhance soil literacy